

The Quadratic Distribution of Integers Relative to Squares and Oblongs

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Abstract: This study explores the application of quadratic distribution principles to the sequences $odds$ and $odds + 2$, and extends the analysis to $odds \pm 2k$ to uncover patterns that contribute to our understanding of number theory conjectures. By examining the behavior of quadratic sequences, particularly those derived from the difference between odd and even squares (and vice versa), we demonstrate that all odd composite numbers are distributed along the numerical line following specific quadratic patterns. This consistent reference to square and oblong numbers highlights the unique quadratic nature of odd composite number distributions. This discovery provides a new perspective on the intrinsic properties of these distributions, suggesting that such patterns can be predicted and modeled through quadratic formulas. These findings reinforce studies previously published in preprints, confirming, and expanding upon the established quadratic distribution principles observed in the distribution of odd composite numbers.

Keywords: Quadratic Distribution; Number Theory; Goldbach's Conjecture; Landau's Problem; Twin Prime Conjecture; Mathematical Modeling; Integer Sequences; Odd Composite Numbers.

2020 Mathematics Subject Classification: 11P32 Goldbach-type theorems; other additive questions involving primes; 11B25 Arithmetic progressions; 11A41 Primes; 11N05 Distribution of primes; 11N36 Applications of sieve methods; 11A51 Factorization; primality.

Never think 'never'.

One day the mind becomes bigger than the body.

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1 Introduction

This study revisits two well-understood concepts in number theory: while it is widely acknowledged that the sum of two squares does not produce all odd integers, the fact that the difference between two squares can generate every odd integer has significant implications for determining primality. Specifically, we explore how an odd integer that can be expressed in multiple ways as the difference between squares (e.g., the number 9 as both $5^2 - 4^2$ and $3^2 - 0^2$) is identified as compound. Conversely, an odd integer expressible in only one way (e.g., 11 as solely $6^2 - 5^2$) is indicative of its primality.

Traditionally, number theory has leveraged algorithmic and analytic methods to unravel the mysteries of numbers. However, this study breaches conventional boundaries by harnessing geometric tools and numerical tables, not to supplant foundational methods but to augment them. This geometric perspective is not just a theoretical enhancement but a practical one, offering simpler, more intuitive pathways to understanding numbers. Particularly, this study pioneers the use of geometric analysis to directly correlate the number of square difference representations with an integer's primality—a facet of number theory that, while hinted at in previous explorations, has never been fully realized until now.

Our approach leverages the difference of squares to generate all odd integers, identifying primal numbers without the need for traditional divisibility tests or factorization. This method highlights that composite odd numbers (odd compounds) can invariably be expressed as the difference of two squares in more than one way because there are at least two distinct odd products $bx = (p - q)(p + q) = p^2 - q^2 = \left(\frac{x+b}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{x-b}{2}\right)^2$ resulting in odd compounds. These products are distinct in their absolute values; merely changing the signs of both 'b' and 'x' simultaneously does not constitute different products. This specificity is crucial because it ensures that each positive compound odd integer is produced by genuinely unique sets of b and x values. While algebraically straightforward, the novel contribution of our study lies in demonstrating how geometry uniquely illustrates that the quantity of square differences determines the primality of a number. Without the geometric perspective and relying solely on algebraic and analytical methods, it might be challenging to discern that the number of distinct square difference expressions directly correlates with an integer's primality.

This study exemplifies how geometric insights can challenge conventional perspectives and enrich our understanding of number theory. By applying these principles, we not only circumvent the computational overhead associated with traditional methods but also open new avenues for efficient and insightful analytical techniques. This geometric approach is a testament to the untapped potential of these methods, asserting their validity and applicability in resolving deep mathematical questions and addressing the criticisms regarding their lack of rigor and generality.

In addition to challenging the prevailing view on the use of geometry in number theory, this study explores how the visualization of the quadratic distribution of compound numbers can provide new insights into numerical relationships. A notable discovery was the identification of the sequence OEIS <https://oeis.org/A371355> through meticulous analysis of table C001767 in section 9.3. This finding not only reinforces the connection between mathematics and computer science but also underscores the relevance and impact of our methodological approach.

In this study, we adopt the terms 'primals' and 'compounds' in place of the more traditional 'primes' and 'composites' as defined in the study 'Integers are only Primals and Compounds,' available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8419643>. This terminology aligns with recent findings on the intrinsic properties of the sieve of primes. For readers who are not familiar with the systematic and periodic positioning of square and oblong numbers on the number line, we recommend consulting 'The SOM Numbers (part I)' available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10208029> for a comprehensive understanding of this concept. Additionally, for any abbreviations or terms used that are not explicitly explained within this text, we recommend consulting 'Symbolic Conventions and Lexicon,' available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10127987>. This resource provides comprehensive definitions and context to ensure a unified understanding of the terminology employed throughout our analysis.

2 Geometric Distribution of Pairs of Complementary Divisors

Let's examine the table below:

Figure 1. C002451 Table of Geometric Distribution of Pairs of Complementary Divisors by Integer Number $x = rs = r(r + b) = s(s - b)$.

https://1drv.ms/i/s!Arslv070x3WjkcZtv8euu_AkKO_gew?e=eRMUjF

2.1 Initial Four Columns Overview:

The first column lists a sequence of integers x , referenced by <https://oeis.org/A256958>.

The second column displays the number of positive divisors for the integer number x , with reference to <https://oeis.org/A000005>.

The third column presents twice the number of pairs of complementary divisors for the integer number $x = rs = r(r + b) = s(s - b)$, as indicated by <https://oeis.org/A161841>.

$$A161841 = 2 \left\lceil \frac{A000005}{2} \right\rceil = 2 * ceiling \left[\frac{A000005}{2} \right]$$

The fourth column details the number of pairs of complementary divisors per integer number $x = rs = r(r + b) = s(s - b)$, cited in <https://oeis.org/A038548>.

$$A038548 = \frac{A161841}{2} = \left\lceil \frac{A000005}{2} \right\rceil = \text{ceiling} \left[\frac{A000005}{2} \right]$$

2.2 Complementary Divisors and the Difference b :

The principal approach is to examine pairs of complementary divisors for a specific integer x , expressed in the forms $x = rs = r(r + b) = s(s - b)$, where b signifies the difference between two complementary divisors of each pair $b = s - r$. Here, $r = d_1$ and $s = d_2$ denote the values of the complementary divisors, and b represents the distance between them, illustrating how the difference between complementary divisors varies with x .

2.3 SqMn and ObMn:

The columns following the initial four are divided into two types:

- **SqMn (Square minus n):** Abbreviation for 'Square minus n', where 'n' represents a specific square number. This notation includes a series of derived sequences where each term results from subtracting a square number from the square sequence. Examples encompass SqM0 (square sequence minus zero), SqM1 (square sequence minus one), SqM4 (square sequence minus four), and so forth.
- **ObMn (Oblong minus n):** Abbreviation for 'Oblong minus n', where 'n' represents a specific oblong number. This notation describes a series of sequences derived by subtracting an oblong number from each term in the oblong sequence. Examples include ObM0 (original oblong sequence without any subtraction), ObM2 (oblong sequence minus two), ObM6 (oblong sequence minus six), etc.

2.4 Patterns of b Values in SqMn and ObMn Columns:

For the SqMn columns, when placed in the form $r(r + b)$ or $s(s - b)$, b assumes even values $2q = (0, 2, 4, 6, \dots)$, reflecting the nature and distribution of numbers in the form of (square sequence minus a square number).

$Y[y] = y*(y \pm 0)$	C000800	Integers in the form of square-0 (SqM0).	http://oeis.org/A000290
$Y[y] = y*(y \pm 2)$	C000801	Integers in the form of square-1 (SqM1).	https://oeis.org/A005563
$Y[y] = y*(y \pm 4)$	C000802	Integers in the form of square-4 (SqM4).	https://oeis.org/A028347
$Y[y] = y*(y \pm 6)$	C000803	Integers in the form of square-9 (SqM9).	https://oeis.org/A028560
$Y[y] = y*(y \pm 8)$	C000804	Integers in the form of square-16 (SqM16).	https://oeis.org/A028566
$Y[y] = y*(y \pm 10)$	C000805	Integers in the form of square-25 (SqM25).	https://oeis.org/A098603
$Y[y] = y*(y \pm 12)$	C000806	Integers in the form of square-36 (SqM36).	http://oeis.org/A098847
$Y[y] = y*(y \pm 14)$	C000807	Integers in the form of square-49 (SqM49).	http://oeis.org/A098848
$Y[y] = y*(y \pm 16)$	C000808	Integers in the form of square-64 (SqM64).	http://oeis.org/A098849
$Y[y] = y*(y \pm 18)$	C000809	Integers in the form of square-81 (SqM81).	http://oeis.org/A098850
$Y[y] = y*(y \pm 20)$	C000810	Integers in the form of square-100 (SqM100).	http://oeis.org/A120071
$Y[y] = y*(y \pm 22)$	C000811	Integers in the form of square-121 (SqM121).	http://oeis.org/A132764
$Y[y] = y*(y \pm 24)$	C000812	Integers in the form of square-144 (SqM144).	http://oeis.org/A132766
$Y[y] = y*(y \pm 26)$	C000813	Integers in the form of square-169 (SqM169).	http://oeis.org/A132768
$Y[y] = y*(y \pm 28)$	C000814	Integers in the form of square-196 (SqM196).	http://oeis.org/A132770
$Y[y] = y*(y \pm 30)$	C000815	Integers in the form of square-225 (SqM225).	http://oeis.org/A132772

Figure 2. [C000776](#) The ([square sequence minus square number](#)) table.

This occurs because:

$$\begin{aligned}
 x &= rs = p^2 - q^2 = (p - q)(p + q) \\
 r &= p - q \\
 s &= p + q \\
 x &= r(p + q) = r(r + 2q) = r(r + \text{even}) \\
 x &= s(p - q) = s(s - 2q) = s(s + \text{even})
 \end{aligned}$$

For the ObMn columns, when represented in the form $r(r + b)$ or $s(s - b)$, b takes on odd values $2q - 1 = (1, 3, 5, 7, \dots)$, showing the characteristic of numbers in the form of (oblong sequence minus an oblong number).

$Y[y] = y^*(y \pm 1)$	C000900	Integers in the form of oblong-0 (ObM0).	http://oeis.org/A002378
$Y[y] = y^*(y \pm 3)$	C000901	Integers in the form of oblong-2 (ObM2).	http://oeis.org/A028552
$Y[y] = y^*(y \pm 5)$	C000902	Integers in the form of oblong-6 (ObM6).	http://oeis.org/A028557
$Y[y] = y^*(y \pm 7)$	C000903	Integers in the form of oblong-12 (ObM12).	http://oeis.org/A028563
$Y[y] = y^*(y \pm 9)$	C000904	Integers in the form of oblong-20 (ObM20).	http://oeis.org/A028569
$Y[y] = y^*(y \pm 11)$	C000905	Integers in the form of oblong-30 (ObM30).	http://oeis.org/A119412
$Y[y] = y^*(y \pm 13)$	C000906	Integers in the form of oblong-42 (ObM42).	http://oeis.org/A132759
$Y[y] = y^*(y \pm 15)$	C000907	Integers in the form of oblong-56 (ObM56).	http://oeis.org/A132760
$Y[y] = y^*(y \pm 17)$	C000908	Integers in the form of oblong-72 (ObM72).	http://oeis.org/A132761
$Y[y] = y^*(y \pm 19)$	C000909	Integers in the form of oblong-90 (ObM90).	http://oeis.org/A132762
$Y[y] = y^*(y \pm 21)$	C000910	Integers in the form of oblong-110 (ObM110).	http://oeis.org/A132763
$Y[y] = y^*(y \pm 23)$	C000911	Integers in the form of oblong-132 (ObM132).	http://oeis.org/A132765
$Y[y] = y^*(y \pm 25)$	C000912	Integers in the form of oblong-156 (ObM156).	http://oeis.org/A132767
$Y[y] = y^*(y \pm 27)$	C000913	Integers in the form of oblong-182 (ObM182).	http://oeis.org/A132769
$Y[y] = y^*(y \pm 29)$	C000914	Integers in the form of oblong-210 (ObM210).	http://oeis.org/A132771
$Y[y] = y^*(y \pm 31)$	C000915	Integers in the form of oblong-240 (ObM240).	http://oeis.org/A132773

Figure 3. [C000777](#) The ([oblong sequence minus the oblong number](#)) table.

This occurs because:

$$\begin{aligned}
 x &= rs = (p^2 - p) - (q^2 - q) = (p - q)(p + q) - (p - q) = (p - q)(p + q - 1) \\
 r &= p - q \\
 s &= p + q - 1 \\
 x &= r(p + q - 1) = r(r + (2q - 1)) = r(r + \text{odd}) \\
 x &= s(p - q) = s(s - (2q - 1)) = s(s - \text{odd})
 \end{aligned}$$

2.5 Column Implications:

In the SqM0 column, zeros appear on the rows of square numbers, indicating that the difference ($b = 0$) between complementary divisors for perfect square numbers is zero.

In the ObM0 column, ones (1) appear on the lines of oblong numbers, signifying that the smallest difference ($b = 1$) between complementary divisors occurs in oblong numbers.

In subsequent columns (SqM1, ObM2, SqM4, ObM6, etc.), the values of b reflect specific differences between complementary divisors for square numbers minus a specific square number and oblong numbers minus a specific oblong number, respectively.

2.6 Example with $x = 4$:

For the number in the row $x = 4$, we observe two distinct values of b in the table, providing different algebraic interpretations for the two pairs of complementary divisors of 4:

In the SqM0 column: The value of b is 0. This indicates that 4 can be expressed as $2(2 \pm 0)$, signifying that 4 is a perfect square $4 = 2^2$, and the two complementary divisors, in this case, are both 2, with a $b = 0$ difference between them, since $2 - 2 = 0$. This example clearly illustrates the relationship between perfect square numbers and the "SqM0" column in the table.

In the ObM2 column: The value of b is 3, demonstrating that 4 has a second pair of complementary divisors (1; 4): as $4 = 1(1 + 3)$ and as $4 = 4(4 - 3)$. These expressions show that, depending on the chosen divisor of the complementary pair (1 or 4 in this case), it must be adjusted (added or subtracted) by 3 to, when multiplied, result in 4.

2.7 Example with $b = 3$:

When we focus on the value of $b = 3$, we find that it appears exclusively in the ObM2 column, covering a sequence of numbers such as 0, 4, 10, 18, 28, etc. This sequence corresponds to the one listed on the OEIS at <https://oeis.org/A028552>. These numbers can all be represented in the form of $r(r + 3)$ or $s(s - 3)$, illustrating a specific algebraic and geometric relationship.

ObM2 Column and $b = 3$: The presence of $b = 3$ in the ObM2 column suggests a unique mathematical pattern. For $b = 3$, the sequence of numbers starting from 0 and moving onwards—4, 10, 18, 28—highlights numbers that are the result of specific algebraic expressions. These expressions consider the adjustment (either addition or subtraction) of 3 to the base number r or s (divisors), when constructing products that fit within the framework of $r(r + 3)$ or $s(s - 3)$.

Algebraic Forms $r(r + 3)$ or $s(s - 3)$: This formula represents a versatile approach to understanding numbers within a structured sequence. Each number in the sequence (0, 4, 10, 18, 28, etc.) exemplifies how an integer can be decomposed or constructed from its divisors, using the value of $b = 3$ to bridge the gap between the multiplier and multiplicand, either by addition to the former or subtraction from the latter.

3 Generating Odd Numbers Through Square Number Differences

Certain positive integers may be written as sum of 2 squares, others not. As elucidated in our study, "Exploring Parabolic Patterns in the Map of Integers and Divisors (MID) Framework," accessible at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10252480>, the generation of odd numbers via square number differences necessitates one square to be even and the other odd. This prerequisite allows

us to establish that an odd number, x , can be expressed as $x = odd = rs = p^2 - q^2 = (p - q)(p + q)$, contingent upon the condition that $p - q$ and $p + q$ are odd.

This insight lays the groundwork for a comprehensive analysis presented in figure below, which catalogs all possible odd bases differences between p and q ranging from 1 to 9, aiming to generate all positive odd numbers. The geometric distribution of these differences is meticulously charted, highlighting a distinct pattern: while each primal number corresponds to a unique square difference, compounds are invariably associated with multiple square differences.

C001668 The Geometry of Odd Number Generation by Square Differences						
n	2n-1	p-q				
		1	3	5	7	9
1	1	1 ² - 0 ² = 1 - 0 = 1				
2	3	2 ² - 1 ² = 4 - 1 = 3				
3	5	3 ² - 2 ² = 9 - 4 = 5				
4	7	4 ² - 3 ² = 16 - 9 = 7				
5	9	5 ² - 4 ² = 25 - 16 = 9	3 ² - 0 ² = 9 - 0 = 9			
6	11	6 ² - 5 ² = 36 - 25 = 11				
7	13	7 ² - 6 ² = 49 - 36 = 13				
8	15	8 ² - 7 ² = 64 - 49 = 15	4 ² - 1 ² = 16 - 1 = 15			
9	17	9 ² - 8 ² = 81 - 64 = 17				
10	19	10 ² - 9 ² = 100 - 81 = 19				
11	21	11 ² - 10 ² = 121 - 100 = 21	5 ² - 2 ² = 25 - 4 = 21			
12	23	12 ² - 11 ² = 144 - 121 = 23				
13	25	13 ² - 12 ² = 169 - 144 = 25		5 ² - 0 ² = 25 - 0 = 25		
14	27	14 ² - 13 ² = 196 - 169 = 27	6 ² - 3 ² = 36 - 9 = 27			
15	29	15 ² - 14 ² = 225 - 196 = 29				
16	31	16 ² - 15 ² = 256 - 225 = 31				
17	33	17 ² - 16 ² = 289 - 256 = 33	7 ² - 4 ² = 49 - 16 = 33			
18	35	18 ² - 17 ² = 324 - 289 = 35		6 ² - 1 ² = 36 - 1 = 35		
19	37	19 ² - 18 ² = 361 - 324 = 37				
20	39	20 ² - 19 ² = 400 - 361 = 39	8 ² - 5 ² = 64 - 25 = 39			
21	41	21 ² - 20 ² = 441 - 400 = 41				
22	43	22 ² - 21 ² = 484 - 441 = 43				
23	45	23 ² - 22 ² = 529 - 484 = 45	9 ² - 6 ² = 81 - 36 = 45	7 ² - 2 ² = 49 - 4 = 45		
24	47	24 ² - 23 ² = 576 - 529 = 47				
25	49	25 ² - 24 ² = 625 - 576 = 49			7 ² - 0 ² = 49 - 0 = 49	
26	51	26 ² - 25 ² = 676 - 625 = 51	10 ² - 7 ² = 100 - 49 = 51			
27	53	27 ² - 26 ² = 729 - 676 = 53				
28	55	28 ² - 27 ² = 784 - 729 = 55		8 ² - 3 ² = 64 - 9 = 55		
29	57	29 ² - 28 ² = 841 - 784 = 57	11 ² - 8 ² = 121 - 64 = 57			
30	59	30 ² - 29 ² = 900 - 841 = 59				
31	61	31 ² - 30 ² = 961 - 900 = 61				
32	63	32 ² - 31 ² = 1024 - 961 = 63	12 ² - 9 ² = 144 - 81 = 63		8 ² - 1 ² = 64 - 1 = 63	
33	65	33 ² - 32 ² = 1089 - 1024 = 65		9 ² - 4 ² = 81 - 16 = 65		
34	67	34 ² - 33 ² = 1156 - 1089 = 67				
35	69	35 ² - 34 ² = 1225 - 1156 = 69	13 ² - 10 ² = 169 - 100 = 69			
36	71	36 ² - 35 ² = 1296 - 1225 = 71				
37	73	37 ² - 36 ² = 1369 - 1296 = 73				
38	75	38 ² - 37 ² = 1444 - 1369 = 75	14 ² - 11 ² = 196 - 121 = 75	10 ² - 5 ² = 100 - 25 = 75		
39	77	39 ² - 38 ² = 1521 - 1444 = 77			9 ² - 2 ² = 81 - 4 = 77	
40	79	40 ² - 39 ² = 1600 - 1521 = 79				
41	81	41 ² - 40 ² = 1681 - 1600 = 81	15 ² - 12 ² = 225 - 144 = 81			9 ² - 0 ² = 81 - 0 = 81
42	83	42 ² - 41 ² = 1764 - 1681 = 83				
43	85	43 ² - 42 ² = 1849 - 1764 = 85		11 ² - 6 ² = 121 - 36 = 85		
44	87	44 ² - 43 ² = 1936 - 1849 = 87	16 ² - 13 ² = 256 - 169 = 87			
45	89	45 ² - 44 ² = 2025 - 1936 = 89				
46	91	46 ² - 45 ² = 2116 - 2025 = 91				
47	93	47 ² - 46 ² = 2209 - 2116 = 93	17 ² - 14 ² = 289 - 196 = 93		10 ² - 3 ² = 100 - 9 = 91	
48	95	48 ² - 47 ² = 2304 - 2209 = 95		12 ² - 7 ² = 144 - 49 = 95		
49	97	49 ² - 48 ² = 2401 - 2304 = 97				
50	99	50 ² - 49 ² = 2500 - 2401 = 99	18 ² - 15 ² = 324 - 225 = 99			10 ² - 1 ² = 100 - 1 = 99
51	101	51 ² - 50 ² = 2601 - 2500 = 101				
52	103	52 ² - 51 ² = 2704 - 2601 = 103				
53	105	53 ² - 52 ² = 2809 - 2704 = 105	19 ² - 16 ² = 361 - 256 = 105	13 ² - 8 ² = 169 - 64 = 105	11 ² - 4 ² = 121 - 16 = 105	
54	107	54 ² - 53 ² = 2916 - 2809 = 107				
55	109	55 ² - 54 ² = 3025 - 2916 = 109				
56	111	56 ² - 55 ² = 3136 - 3025 = 111	20 ² - 17 ² = 400 - 289 = 111			
57	113	57 ² - 56 ² = 3249 - 3136 = 113				
58	115	58 ² - 57 ² = 3364 - 3249 = 115		14 ² - 9 ² = 196 - 81 = 115		
59	117	59 ² - 58 ² = 3481 - 3364 = 117	21 ² - 18 ² = 441 - 324 = 117			11 ² - 2 ² = 121 - 4 = 117
60	119	60 ² - 59 ² = 3600 - 3481 = 119			12 ² - 5 ² = 144 - 25 = 119	

Figure 4. C001668 The Geometry of Odd Number Generation by Square Differences.

<https://1drv.ms/i/s!Arslv070x3WjkccCv1zs6OGCt7OuxA?e=itHBB1>

The figure above showcases the complete collection of square differences that generate all positive odd numbers, emphasizing the geometric distribution of these numerical outcomes. Each column begins with the formula 'Odd Column Number Squared minus Zero', indicating that the difference is generated by the square of each odd column number and 0. These represent the central pair of complementary divisors of the square numbers. Then, row by row, it incrementally

increases the two bases by adding one unit to each base in the difference, thereby constructing the column. This systematic approach ensures that all resulting differences yield odd numbers in every possible manner as differences of squares, where even and odd squares alternately serve as the minuend and subtrahend.

Notably, each odd perfect square aligns with a specific position in a sequence following a quadratic function, defined by 1, 5, 13, 25, 41, 61, ... as catalogued in OEIS <https://oeis.org/A001844> with the formula $a(n) = \left\lceil \frac{(\text{odd})^2}{2} \right\rceil = \left\lceil \frac{(2n-1)^2}{2} \right\rceil$. This sequence arises because each odd square number appears in a row whose index corresponds to these values, illustrating a unique structured pattern in their distribution.

3.1 Review of Difference of Squares to Generate All Odd Numbers

This section details how the difference of two squares can generate all odd integers, supported by specific algebraic cases and general formulas. The general formula for the difference of squares is expressed as:

$$p^2 - q^2 = (p + q)(p - q) = r * s$$

For case C004001, where p is odd and q is even $p = 2k + 1$ and $q = 2j$, the substitution and expansion yields:

$$(2k + 1)^2 - (2j)^2 = 4k^2 + 4k + 1 - 4j^2 = 4(k^2 + k - j^2) + 1$$

resulting in an odd number in the form of $4h + 1 \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$.

For case C004002, where p is even and q is odd $p = 2k$ and $q = 2j + 1$, the formula adjusts to:

$$(2k)^2 - (2j + 1)^2 = 4k^2 - (4j^2 + 4j + 1) = 4(k^2 - j^2 - j) - 1$$

resulting in an odd number in the form of $4h - 1 \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$.

To demonstrate that all odd integers can be represented as the difference of two squares, consider the equation:

$$x = p^2 - q^2 = (p + q)(p - q) = rs$$

Suppose x is odd. Set $p = \frac{x+1}{2}$ and $q = \frac{x-1}{2}$, ensuring p and q differ by 1, hence one is even, the other odd. Then the calculation unfolds as follows:

$$p^2 - q^2 = \left(\frac{x+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{x-1}{2}\right)^2 = x = (p+q)(p-q)$$

This formula confirms that every odd integer x can be expressed in this form. More generally, the equation can be extended to:

$$p^2 - q^2 = \left(\frac{x+b}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{x-b}{2}\right)^2 = bx = (p+q)(p-q)$$

In this more general form, $p = \frac{x+b}{2}$ and $q = \frac{x-b}{2}$. Therefore, $p - q = b$ and $p + q = x$. This relationship shows that the difference $(p - q) = b$, and the sum $(p + q) = x$. These relationships are pivotal for understanding how odd integers can be generated from the differences of squares using various odd values of b and x .

It is important to note that the general formula $p^2 - q^2 = bx$ primarily applies to compound numbers that are multiples of odd numbers. This specificity highlights how differences of squares can encode the structure of compounds within the sequence of odd integers.

For odd values of b and x this results in all multiples of odd numbers being produced in all possible forms, focusing on compound outcomes.

3.2 Square Differences and Sieve of Odd Primals: Unveiling the Patterns of Number Formation

When we consider that every $x = odd = rs = p^2 - q^2 = (p - q) * (p + q)$, it becomes evident that if x is a compound, it must inherently have at least two distinct rs products with different multipliers and multiplicands. This implies that any odd compound must also have at least two distinct differences of $p^2 - q^2$ with different minuends and subtrahends. Crucially, this also necessitates that to produce an odd compound, the distinct bases p and q must have an odd difference (or sum) between them.

Following this rule of formation, the first four positive odd numbers are primals. It is not possible to have two square odd differences or two base odd differences to form 1, 3, 5, or 7. This rule does not allow for distinguishing 1 from 3, 5, or 7 as primal. In all these instances, only an odd base difference of one unit can produce the odd number through the difference of two squares.

Therefore, the first odd compound can only emerge when there is an odd difference of three units between the bases p and q to produce the first positive compound. In this scenario, $p = 3$ and $q = 0$, where $3^2 - 0^2 = 9$.

This insight reveals that beyond the explained indistinction in primality between 1 and other odd primals, and without using factorization to detect primality, it becomes inherently clear that all odd integers greater than 0 are primals, adhering to the "most natural" formation law possible. The non-obvious part is that odd compounds are the "rare" entities. Odd primals are "obvious," while the emergence of odd compounds is not. It is the odd compounds that necessitate justification for their appearance.

It is precisely this line of reasoning that the present study endeavors to elaborate upon. By delving into the inherent patterns of number formation and the distinctive behaviors of odd primal and odd compound numbers, we propose a methodology to "guarantee" an understanding of why, across the entire numerical spectrum, compounds must inevitably manifest.

4 Central Pair of Complementary Divisors (CPCD)

The CPCD concept, when applied to odd numbers seeking operations with the smallest possible figures, necessitates focusing on CPCDs that entail the closest divisors, hence the smallest squares for subtraction.

In the preceding section, "3 Generating Odd Numbers Through Square Number Differences," the study of square numbers provided us with crucial insights into the identification of all Central Pairs of Complementary Divisors (CPCD) across all odd numbers.

It was noted that square numbers configured as CPCD exhibit a parabolic geometry when mapped onto the plane depicted in Figure C001668. This configuration initiates with the odd primal number 1, sequentially followed by the lowest positive odd compound 9 and subsequent odd compound squares such as 25, 49, 81, ... This delineated parabola encloses all the odd compounds in the guise of odd squares, adhering to the equation $y = 4x^2 + 4x + 1$ for $x > 0$. This equation has offset $f = \text{roundz}\left[-\frac{4}{2*4}\right] = \text{roundz}[-0.5] = -1$. Then for $x = k - 1$, $y = 4k^2 - 4k + 1 = (2k - 1)^2 = (2k - 1)(2k - 1) = \text{odd}^2$, now with offset $f = \text{roundz}\left[-\frac{-4}{2*4}\right] = \text{roundz}[0.5] = 0$.

In parallel with this odd square parabola, we encounter the parabola for odd (*even squares - 1*) numbers, beginning with the primal number 3 and progressing through 15, 35, 63, 99, ... The odd compounds manifested in the form of odd (*even squares - 1*) adhere to $y = 4x^2 + 8x + 3$ for $x > 0$. This equation has offset $f = \text{roundz}\left[-\frac{8}{2*4}\right] = \text{roundz}[-1] = -1$. Then for $x = k - 1$, $y = 4k^2 - 1 = (2k)^2 - 1 = (2k - 1)(2k + 1) = \text{even}^2 - 1$, now with offset $f = \text{roundz}\left[-\frac{0}{2*4}\right] = \text{roundz}[0] = 0$.

Subsequently, the parabola representing odd (*odd squares - 4*) numbers commences with the primal number 5, extending to 21, 45, 77, 117, ... Odd compounds within this category, denoted as odd (*odd squares - 4*), are defined by $y = 4x^2 + 12x + 5$ for $x > 0$. This equation has offset $f = \text{roundz}\left[-\frac{12}{2*4}\right] = \text{roundz}[-1.5] = -2$. Then for $x = k - 2$, $y = 4k^2 - 4k - 3 = (2k - 1)^2 - 4 = (2k - 3)(2k + 1) = \text{odd}^2 - 4$, now with offset $f = \text{roundz}\left[-\frac{-4}{2*4}\right] = \text{roundz}[0.5] = 0$.

Following this, we discern the parabola for odd (*even squares - 9*) numbers, initiating with the primal number 7, where odd compounds fitting the description of odd (*even squares - 9*) are expressed by $y = 4x^2 + 16x + 7$ for $x > 0$. This equation has offset $f = \text{roundz}\left[-\frac{16}{2*4}\right] = \text{roundz}[-2] = -2$. Then for $x = k - 2$, $y = 4k^2 - 9 = (2k)^2 - 9 = (2k - 3)(2k + 3) = \text{even}^2 - 9$, now with offset $f = \text{roundz}\left[-\frac{0}{2*4}\right] = \text{roundz}[0] = 0$.

As a final example, the parabola for odd (*odd squares - 16*) numbers starts with 9, identified as the first positive odd compound. The odd compounds conforming to the pattern of odd (*odd squares - 16*) follow the equation $y = 4x^2 + 20x + 9$ for $x > 0$. This equation has offset $f = \text{roundz}\left[-\frac{20}{2*4}\right] = \text{roundz}[-2.5] = -3$. Then for $x = k - 3$, $y = 4k^2 - 4k - 15 = (2k - 1)^2 - 16 = (2k - 5)(2k + 3) = \text{odd}^2 - 16$, now with offset $f = \text{roundz}\left[-\frac{-4}{2*4}\right] = \text{roundz}[0.5] = 0$.

This analytical exploration not only reveals a systematic pattern and mathematical progression in the genesis of odd numbers but also elucidates the transition from primal numbers to the emergence of odd compounds through quadratic differences.

Observe that this algorithm generates all Central Pairs of Complementary Divisors (CPCD) for each positive odd integer. Consequently, all these parabolas, expressed in the form $y = 4x^2 +$

$4mx + (2m - 1)$ for $x > 0$ and $m > 0$, produce a table encompassing all positive odd compounds. Refer to the table C001742 below:

C001742 Table of Distinct Positive Odd Compounds via CPCD Parabolic Algorithm																				
Tally	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20
x_focus	0.063	-0.938	-3.938	-8.938	-15.94	-24.94	-35.94	-48.94	-63.94	-80.94	-99.94	-120.9	-143.9	-168.9	-195.9	-224.9	-255.9	-288.9	-323.9	-360.9
LR	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25
Δ	0	16	64	144	256	400	576	784	1024	1296	1600	1936	2304	2704	3136	3600	4096	4624	5184	5776
√Δ	0	4	8	12	16	20	24	28	32	36	40	44	48	52	56	60	64	68	72	76
C. G.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
R1	-0.5	-0.5	-0.5	-0.5	-0.5	-0.5	-0.5	-0.5	-0.5	-0.5	-0.5	-0.5	-0.5	-0.5	-0.5	-0.5	-0.5	-0.5	-0.5	-0.5
R2	-0.5	-1.5	-2.5	-3.5	-4.5	-5.5	-6.5	-7.5	-8.5	-9.5	-10.5	-11.5	-12.5	-13.5	-14.5	-15.5	-16.5	-17.5	-18.5	-19.5
R2-R1	0	-1	-2	-3	-4	-5	-6	-7	-8	-9	-10	-11	-12	-13	-14	-15	-16	-17	-18	-19
R2+R1	-1	-2	-3	-4	-5	-6	-7	-8	-9	-10	-11	-12	-13	-14	-15	-16	-17	-18	-19	-20
R2*R1	0.25	0.75	1.25	1.75	2.25	2.75	3.25	3.75	4.25	4.75	5.25	5.75	6.25	6.75	7.25	7.75	8.25	8.75	9.25	9.75
x_sp	0	-1	-4	-9	-16	-25	-36	-49	-64	-81	-100	-121	-144	-169	-196	-225	-256	-289	-324	-361
y_sp	-0.5	-1	-1.5	-2	-2.5	-3	-3.5	-4	-4.5	-5	-5.5	-6	-6.5	-7	-7.5	-8	-8.5	-9	-9.5	-10
f	-1	-1	-2	-2	-3	-3	-4	-4	-5	-5	-6	-6	-7	-7	-8	-8	-9	-9	-10	-10
type	DES	SUB	DES	SUB	DES	SUB	DES	SUB	DES	SUB	DES	SUB	DES	SUB	DES	SUB	DES	SUB	DES	SUB
a	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
b	4	8	12	16	20	24	28	32	36	40	44	48	52	56	60	64	68	72	76	80
c	1	3	5	7	9	11	13	15	17	19	21	23	25	27	29	31	33	35	37	39
-20	1521	1443	1365	1287	1209	1131	1053	975	897	819	741	663	585	507	429	351	273	195	117	39
-19	1369	1295	1221	1147	1073	999	925	851	777	703	629	555	481	407	333	259	185	111	37	-37
-18	1225	1155	1085	1015	945	875	805	735	665	595	525	455	385	315	245	175	105	35	-35	-105
-17	1089	1023	957	891	825	759	693	627	561	495	429	363	297	231	165	99	33	-33	-99	-165
-16	961	899	837	775	713	651	589	527	465	403	341	279	217	155	93	31	-31	-93	-155	-217
-15	841	783	725	667	609	551	493	435	377	319	261	203	145	87	29	-29	-87	-145	-203	-261
-14	729	675	621	567	513	459	405	351	297	243	189	135	81	27	-27	-81	-135	-189	-243	-297
-13	625	575	525	475	425	375	325	275	225	175	125	75	25	-25	-75	-125	-175	-225	-275	-325
-12	529	483	437	391	345	299	253	207	161	115	69	23	-23	-69	-115	-161	-207	-253	-299	-345
-11	441	399	357	315	273	231	189	147	105	63	21	-21	-63	-105	-147	-189	-231	-273	-315	-357
-10	361	323	285	247	209	171	133	95	57	19	-19	-57	-95	-133	-171	-209	-247	-285	-323	-361
-9	289	255	221	187	153	119	85	51	17	-17	-51	-85	-119	-153	-187	-221	-255	-289	-323	-357
-8	225	195	165	135	105	75	45	15	-15	-45	-75	-105	-135	-165	-195	-225	-255	-285	-315	-345
-7	169	143	117	91	65	39	13	-13	-39	-65	-91	-117	-143	-169	-195	-221	-247	-273	-299	-325
-6	121	99	77	55	33	11	-11	-33	-55	-77	-99	-121	-143	-165	-187	-209	-231	-253	-275	-297
-5	81	63	45	27	9	-9	-27	-45	-63	-81	-99	-117	-135	-153	-171	-189	-207	-225	-243	-261
-4	49	35	21	7	-7	-21	-35	-49	-63	-77	-91	-105	-119	-133	-147	-161	-175	-189	-203	-217
-3	25	15	5	-5	-15	-25	-35	-45	-55	-65	-75	-85	-95	-105	-115	-125	-135	-145	-155	-165
-2	9	3	-3	-9	-15	-21	-27	-33	-39	-45	-51	-57	-63	-69	-75	-81	-87	-93	-99	-105
-1	1	-1	-3	-5	-7	-9	-11	-13	-15	-17	-19	-21	-23	-25	-27	-29	-31	-33	-35	-37
0	1	3	5	7	9	11	13	15	17	19	21	23	25	27	29	31	33	35	37	39
1	9	15	21	27	33	39	45	51	57	63	69	75	81	87	93	99	105	111	117	123
2	25	35	45	55	65	75	85	95	105	115	125	135	145	155	165	175	185	195	205	215
3	49	63	77	91	105	119	133	147	161	175	189	203	217	231	245	259	273	287	301	315
4	81	99	117	135	153	171	189	207	225	243	261	279	297	315	333	351	369	387	405	423
5	121	143	165	187	209	231	253	275	297	319	341	363	385	407	429	451	473	495	517	539
6	169	195	221	247	273	299	325	351	377	403	429	455	481	507	533	559	585	611	637	663
7	225	255	285	315	345	375	405	435	465	495	525	555	585	615	645	675	705	735	765	795
8	289	323	357	391	425	459	493	527	561	595	629	663	697	731	765	799	833	867	901	935
9	361	399	437	475	513	551	589	627	665	703	741	779	817	855	893	931	969	1007	1045	1083
10	441	483	525	567	609	651	693	735	777	819	861	903	945	987	1029	1071	1113	1155	1197	1239
11	529	575	621	667	713	759	805	851	897	943	989	1035	1081	1127	1173	1219	1265	1311	1357	1403
12	625	675	725	775	825	875	925	975	1025	1075	1125	1175	1225	1275	1325	1375	1425	1475	1525	1575
13	729	783	837	891	945	999	1053	1107	1161	1215	1269	1323	1377	1431	1485	1539	1593	1647	1701	1755
14	841	899	957	1015	1073	1131	1189	1247	1305	1363	1421	1479	1537	1595	1653	1711	1769	1827	1885	1943
15	961	1023	1085	1147	1209	1271	1333	1395	1457	1519	1581	1643	1705	1767	1829	1891	1953	2015	2077	2139
16	1089	1155	1221	1287	1353	1419	1485	1551	1617	1683	1749	1815	1881	1947	2013	2079	2145	2211	2277	2343
17	1225	1295	1365	1435	1505	1575	1645	1715	1785	1855	1925	1995	2065	2135	2205	2275	2345	2415	2485	2555
18	1369	1443	1517	1591	1665	1739	1813	1887	1961	2035	2109	2183	2257	2331	2405	2479	2553	2627	2701	2775
19	1521	1599	1677	1755	1833	1911	1989	2067	2145	2223	2301	2379	2457	2535	2613	2691	2769	2847	2925	3003
20	1681	1763	1845	1927	2009	2091	2173	2255	2337	2419	2501	2583	2665	2747	2829	2911	2993	3075	3157	3239

Figure 5. C001742 Table of Distinct Positive Odd Compounds via CPCD Parabolic Algorithm.

<https://1drv.ms/i/s!Arslv070x3WjkcctDK8Y8SFuCF1QsQ?e=5yR8Gw>

Table C001742 intricately maps the odd numbers generated through the differences of square numbers, where these differences are uniquely defined by odd numbers between the bases of the squares. This structured presentation reveals a systematic pattern in the formation of odd numbers within a mathematical framework governed by square number differences.

In this table:

- At the row corresponding to index $x = 1$, we encounter odd numbers derived from square differences with a base difference of 3 units. $\{3^2 - 0^2, 4^2 - 1^2, 5^2 - 2^2, \dots\}$
- At the row where index $x = 2$, it showcases odd numbers resulting from square differences with a base difference of 5 units. $\{5^2 - 0^2, 6^2 - 1^2, 7^2 - 2^2, \dots\}$
- Similarly, at the row corresponding to index $x = 3$, the focus shifts to odd numbers that emerge from square differences with a base difference of 7 units. $\{7^2 - 0^2, 8^2 - 1^2, 9^2 - 2^2, \dots\}$

This progression continues, illustrating how each horizontal row in Table C001742 correlates to the sequences observed in the columns of Table C001668, albeit without considering the parabolic geometric distribution inherent to Table C001668. Essentially, the rows of Table C001742 serve as a linear counterpart to the parabolic sequences delineated in Table C001668, emphasizing the role of odd base differences in generating distinct odd numbers through square number differences.

In summary: the parabolas in the form of $y = 4x^2 + 4mx + (2m - 1)$ has offset $f = \text{roundz}\left[-\frac{4m}{2*4}\right] = \text{roundz}\left[-\frac{m}{2}\right]$.

For $m = \text{even} = 2h$, then $f = \text{roundz}\left[-\frac{2h}{2}\right] = -h$. Then for $x = k - h$, $y = 4k^2 - (4h^2 - 4h + 1) = (2k)^2 - (2h - 1)^2 = (2k + 2h - 1)(2k - 2h + 1) = 4k^2 - \text{odd}^2$ now with offset $f = \text{roundz}\left[-\frac{0}{2*4}\right] = \text{roundz}[0] = 0$.

For $m = \text{odd} = 2h - 1$, then $f = \text{roundz}\left[-\frac{2h-1}{2}\right] = \text{roundz}[-h + 0.5] = -h$. Then for $x = k - h$, $y = 4k^2 - 4k - (4h^2 - 8h + 3) = 4k^2 - 4k - ((2(h - 1))^2 - 1) = (2k + 2h - 3)(2k - 2h + 1) = 4k^2 - 4k - (\text{even}^2 - 1)$ now with offset $f = \text{roundz}\left[-\frac{-4}{2*4}\right] = \text{roundz}[0.5] = 0$.

This is reflected in the table C001744 below:

C001744 The C001742 Table in Offset f=0																				
Tally	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20
R1°	0.5	0.5	1.5	1.5	2.5	2.5	3.5	3.5	4.5	4.5	5.5	5.5	6.5	6.5	7.5	7.5	8.5	8.5	9.5	9.5
R2°	0.5	-0.5	-0.5	-1.5	-1.5	-2.5	-2.5	-3.5	-3.5	-4.5	-4.5	-5.5	-5.5	-6.5	-6.5	-7.5	-7.5	-8.5	-8.5	-9.5
R2°-R1°	0	-1	-2	-3	-4	-5	-6	-7	-8	-9	-10	-11	-12	-13	-14	-15	-16	-17	-18	-19
R2°+R1°	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0
R2°*R1°	0.25	-0.25	-0.75	-2.25	-3.75	-6.25	-8.75	-12.25	-15.75	-20.25	-24.75	-30.25	-35.75	-42.25	-48.75	-56.25	-63.75	-72.25	-80.75	-90.25
y_sp	0.5	0	0.5	0	0.5	0	0.5	0	0.5	0	0.5	0	0.5	0	0.5	0	0.5	0	0.5	0
f	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
type	DES	SUB	DES	SUB	DES	SUB	DES	SUB	DES	SUB	DES	SUB	DES	SUB	DES	SUB	DES	SUB	DES	SUB
a°	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
b°	-4	0	-4	0	-4	0	-4	0	-4	0	-4	0	-4	0	-4	0	-4	0	-4	0
c°	1	-1	-3	-9	-15	-25	-35	-49	-63	-81	-99	-121	-143	-169	-195	-225	-255	-289	-323	-361
-20	1681	1599	1677	1591	1665	1575	1645	1551	1617	1519	1581	1479	1537	1431	1485	1375	1425	1311	1357	1239
-19	1521	1443	1517	1435	1505	1419	1485	1395	1457	1363	1421	1323	1377	1275	1325	1219	1265	1155	1197	1083
-18	1369	1295	1365	1287	1353	1271	1333	1247	1305	1215	1269	1175	1225	1127	1173	1071	1113	1007	1045	935
-17	1225	1155	1221	1147	1209	1131	1189	1107	1161	1075	1125	1035	1081	987	1029	931	969	867	901	795
-16	1089	1023	1085	1015	1073	999	1053	975	1025	943	989	903	945	855	893	799	833	735	765	663
-15	961	899	957	891	945	875	925	851	897	819	861	779	817	731	765	675	705	611	637	539
-14	841	783	837	775	825	759	805	735	777	703	741	663	697	615	645	559	585	495	517	423
-13	729	675	725	667	713	651	693	627	665	595	629	555	585	507	533	451	473	387	405	315
-12	625	575	621	567	609	551	589	527	561	495	525	455	481	407	429	351	369	287	301	215
-11	529	483	525	475	513	459	493	435	465	403	429	363	385	315	333	259	273	195	205	123
-10	441	399	437	391	425	375	405	351	377	319	341	279	297	231	245	175	185	111	117	39
-9	361	323	357	315	345	299	325	275	297	243	261	203	217	155	165	99	105	35	37	-37
-8	289	255	285	247	273	231	253	207	225	175	189	135	145	87	93	31	33	-33	-35	-105
-7	225	195	221	187	209	171	189	147	161	115	125	75	81	27	29	-29	-31	-93	-99	-165
-6	169	143	165	135	153	119	133	95	105	63	69	23	25	-25	-27	-81	-87	-145	-155	-217
-5	121	99	117	91	105	75	85	51	57	19	21	-21	-23	-69	-75	-125	-135	-189	-203	-261
-4	81	63	77	55	65	39	45	15	17	-17	-19	-57	-63	-105	-115	-161	-175	-225	-243	-297
-3	49	35	45	27	33	11	13	-13	-15	-45	-51	-85	-95	-133	-147	-189	-207	-253	-275	-325
-2	25	15	21	7	9	-9	-11	-33	-39	-65	-75	-105	-119	-153	-171	-209	-231	-273	-299	-345
-1	9	3	5	-7	-9	-21	-27	-45	-55	-77	-91	-117	-135	-165	-187	-221	-247	-285	-315	-357
0	1	-1	-3	-9	-15	-25	-35	-49	-63	-81	-99	-121	-143	-169	-195	-225	-255	-289	-323	-361
1	1	3	-3	-5	-15	-21	-35	-45	-63	-77	-99	-117	-143	-165	-195	-221	-255	-285	-323	-357
2	9	15	5	7	-7	-9	-27	-33	-55	-65	-91	-105	-135	-153	-187	-209	-247	-273	-315	-345
3	25	35	21	27	9	11	-11	-13	-39	-45	-75	-85	-119	-133	-171	-189	-231	-253	-299	-325
4	49	63	45	55	33	39	13	15	-15	-17	-51	-57	-95	-105	-147	-161	-207	-225	-275	-297
5	81	99	77	91	65	75	45	51	17	19	-19	-21	-63	-69	-115	-125	-175	-189	-243	-261
6	121	143	117	135	105	119	85	95	57	63	21	23	-23	-25	-75	-81	-135	-145	-203	-217
7	169	195	165	187	153	171	133	147	105	115	69	75	25	27	-27	-29	-87	-93	-155	-165
8	225	255	221	247	209	231	189	207	161	175	125	135	81	87	29	31	-31	-33	-99	-105
9	289	323	285	315	273	299	253	275	225	243	189	203	145	155	93	99	33	35	-35	-37
10	361	399	357	391	345	375	325	351	297	319	261	279	217	231	165	175	105	111	37	39
11	441	483	437	475	425	459	405	435	377	403	341	363	297	315	245	259	185	195	117	123
12	529	575	525	567	513	551	493	527	465	495	429	455	385	407	333	351	273	287	205	215
13	625	675	621	667	609	651	589	627	561	595	525	555	481	507	429	451	369	387	301	315
14	729	783	725	775	713	759	693	735	665	703	629	663	585	615	533	559	473	495	405	423
15	841	899	837	891	825	875	805	851	777	819	741	779	697	731	645	675	585	611	517	539
16	961	1023	957	1015	945	999	925	975	897	943	861	903	817	855	765	799	705	735	637	663
17	1089	1155	1085	1147	1073	1131	1053	1107	1025	1075	989	1035	945	987	893	931	833	867	765	795
18	1225	1295	1221	1287	1209	1271	1189	1247	1161	1215	1125	1175	1081	1127	1029	1071	969	1007	901	935
19	1369	1443	1365	1435	1353	1419	1333	1395	1305	1363	1269	1323	1225	1275	1173	1219	1113	1155	1045	1083
20	1521	1599	1517	1591	1505	1575	1485	1551	1457	1519	1421	1479	1377	1431	1325	1375	1265	1311	1197	1239

Figure 6. C001744 The C001742 Table in Offset f=0.

In the presentation of Table C001744 at offset $f = 0$, as depicted in figure above, a distinct pattern emerges within the structure of the columns. Each column alternates systematically between two specific forms: $4y^2 - (\text{odd square})$, and $4y^2 - 4y - (\text{even square} - 1)$. This organization highlights a mathematical regularity where each value in the table is defined by subtracting either an odd square or an even square less one from a quadratic function modified by linear terms.

The figure below illustrates the foundational set of parabolas generated by the Central Pairs of Complementary Divisors (CPCD) algorithm from the table above, a pivotal component in our analysis of odd compound numbers. These parabolas, characterized by their mathematical

formulation $y = 4x^2 + 4mx + (2m - 1)$ for $m > 0$ and $x > 0$, delineate the geometric landscape within which the CPCD for positive odd integers are situated.

Central to our exploration are the parabolas' roots and vertexes, particularly highlighted for their significance in understanding the structural dynamics of these mathematical entities. Each parabola's trajectory is defined by its discriminant $\Delta = (4(m - 1))^2$, ensuring real and distinct roots that provide critical insights into the parabolas' intersections and divergences.

The roots, identified as $R1 = -1/2$ and $R2 = 1/2 - m$, manifest the points at which each parabola intersects the x-axis, denoting the transition points of mathematical interest. Notably, the figure also accentuates the vertexes of these parabolas, situated along the equation $y = -4x^2 - 4x - 1 = -(2x + 1)^2 = -4\left(x + \frac{1}{2}\right)^2$ (dashed line), highlighting the apex of each curve and its pivotal role in mapping the parabolas' minimum values.

Furthermore, the figure showcases the parabolas with roots at -0.5 , expressed through the GeoGebra *sequence*($4y^2 + 4ky + 2k - 1, k, 1, 20$), offering a visual representation of these structures as they extend into the domain of $x < 0$. This depiction is crucial for understanding the positions of the parabolas' roots and vertexes, elucidating their geometric and algebraic properties within the negative domain.

By presenting each column as the $m > 0$ value and indexing each row by the $x > 0$ value, the figure methodically maps out the intricacies of these parabolic paths, underscoring their relevance in generating all distinct positive odd compounds. Through this visual analysis, the systematic reduction in the domain of $x < 0$ to reveal the positions of roots and vertexes enhances our comprehension of the mathematical framework governing the distribution of odd compounds.

Figure 7. C001743 The Parabolic Geometry of CPCD Algorithm: Vertex and Root Distributions. -0.5 is the common root.

<https://1drv.ms/i/s!Arslv070x3WjkccuLlZgddbq2mZsvg?e=PkGdkL>

Finally, we present Table C001669 Odd Numbers Derived from CPCD and Minimal Square Differences, where we reveal some new sequences not yet included in the OEIS.

C001669 Odd Numbers Derived from CPCD and Minimal Square Terms Differences												
n	Odd Numbers from CPCD[odds]				Odd Numbers from Differences of Two Squares with Minimally Valued Terms							
	A033676[2n-1]	*	A033677[2n-1]	=	2n-1	C001745 ^2-	A219695 ^2=	C001746 -	C001747 =	2n-1		
	r = d_c1	*	s = d_c2	=	r*s	((s+r)/2)^2-	((s-r)/2)^2=	((s+r)/2)^2-	((s-r)/2)^2=	((s+r)/2)^2-((s-r)/2)^2		
1	1	*	1	=	1	1^2-	0^2=	1	-	0	=	1
2	1	*	3	=	3	2^2-	1^2=	4	-	1	=	3
3	1	*	5	=	5	3^2-	2^2=	9	-	4	=	5
4	1	*	7	=	7	4^2-	3^2=	16	-	9	=	7
5	3	*	3	=	9	3^2-	0^2=	9	-	0	=	9
6	1	*	11	=	11	6^2-	5^2=	36	-	25	=	11
7	1	*	13	=	13	7^2-	6^2=	49	-	36	=	13
8	3	*	5	=	15	4^2-	1^2=	16	-	1	=	15
9	1	*	17	=	17	9^2-	8^2=	81	-	64	=	17
10	1	*	19	=	19	10^2-	9^2=	100	-	81	=	19
11	3	*	7	=	21	5^2-	2^2=	25	-	4	=	21
12	1	*	23	=	23	12^2-	11^2=	144	-	121	=	23
13	5	*	5	=	25	5^2-	0^2=	25	-	0	=	25
14	3	*	9	=	27	6^2-	3^2=	36	-	9	=	27
15	1	*	29	=	29	15^2-	14^2=	225	-	196	=	29
16	1	*	31	=	31	16^2-	15^2=	256	-	225	=	31
17	3	*	11	=	33	7^2-	4^2=	49	-	16	=	33
18	5	*	7	=	35	6^2-	1^2=	36	-	1	=	35
19	1	*	37	=	37	19^2-	18^2=	361	-	324	=	37
20	3	*	13	=	39	8^2-	5^2=	64	-	25	=	39
21	1	*	41	=	41	21^2-	20^2=	441	-	400	=	41
22	1	*	43	=	43	22^2-	21^2=	484	-	441	=	43
23	5	*	9	=	45	7^2-	2^2=	49	-	4	=	45
24	1	*	47	=	47	24^2-	23^2=	576	-	529	=	47
25	7	*	7	=	49	7^2-	0^2=	49	-	0	=	49
26	3	*	17	=	51	10^2-	7^2=	100	-	49	=	51
27	1	*	53	=	53	27^2-	26^2=	729	-	676	=	53
28	5	*	11	=	55	8^2-	3^2=	64	-	9	=	55
29	3	*	19	=	57	11^2-	8^2=	121	-	64	=	57
30	1	*	59	=	59	30^2-	29^2=	900	-	841	=	59
31	1	*	61	=	61	31^2-	30^2=	961	-	900	=	61
32	7	*	9	=	63	8^2-	1^2=	64	-	1	=	63
33	5	*	13	=	65	9^2-	4^2=	81	-	16	=	65
34	1	*	67	=	67	34^2-	33^2=	1156	-	1089	=	67
35	3	*	23	=	69	13^2-	10^2=	169	-	100	=	69
36	1	*	71	=	71	36^2-	35^2=	1296	-	1225	=	71
37	1	*	73	=	73	37^2-	36^2=	1369	-	1296	=	73
38	5	*	15	=	75	10^2-	5^2=	100	-	25	=	75
39	7	*	11	=	77	9^2-	2^2=	81	-	4	=	77
40	1	*	79	=	79	40^2-	39^2=	1600	-	1521	=	79
41	9	*	9	=	81	9^2-	0^2=	81	-	0	=	81
42	1	*	83	=	83	42^2-	41^2=	1764	-	1681	=	83
43	5	*	17	=	85	11^2-	6^2=	121	-	36	=	85
44	3	*	29	=	87	16^2-	13^2=	256	-	169	=	87
45	1	*	89	=	89	45^2-	44^2=	2025	-	1936	=	89
46	7	*	13	=	91	10^2-	3^2=	100	-	9	=	91
47	3	*	31	=	93	17^2-	14^2=	289	-	196	=	93
48	5	*	19	=	95	12^2-	7^2=	144	-	49	=	95
49	1	*	97	=	97	49^2-	48^2=	2401	-	2304	=	97
50	9	*	11	=	99	10^2-	1^2=	100	-	1	=	99
51	1	*	101	=	101	51^2-	50^2=	2601	-	2500	=	101
52	1	*	103	=	103	52^2-	51^2=	2704	-	2601	=	103
53	7	*	15	=	105	11^2-	4^2=	121	-	16	=	105
54	1	*	107	=	107	54^2-	53^2=	2916	-	2809	=	107
55	1	*	109	=	109	55^2-	54^2=	3025	-	2916	=	109
56	3	*	37	=	111	20^2-	17^2=	400	-	289	=	111
57	1	*	113	=	113	57^2-	56^2=	3249	-	3136	=	113
58	5	*	23	=	115	14^2-	9^2=	196	-	81	=	115
59	9	*	13	=	117	11^2-	2^2=	121	-	4	=	117
60	7	*	17	=	119	12^2-	5^2=	144	-	25	=	119

Figure 8. C001669 Odd Numbers Derived from CPCD and Minimal Square Terms Differences.

<https://1drv.ms/i/s!Arslv070x3WjkccDK7Lwyl6RS9Za6g?e=mncQV4>

Figure above illustrates a table delineating square differences employing CPCDs to generate odd numbers from 1 to 119, conforming to the relations:

$$r = d_{c1} = A033676[odd] = A033676[2n - 1] = odd1$$

$$s = d_{c2} = A033677[odd] = A033677[2n - 1] = odd2$$

Consequently, for the central pair of complementary divisors, we ascertain that:

$$rs = odd1 * odd2 = d_{c1} * d_{c2} = A033676[2n - 1] * A033677[2n - 1] = odd$$

$$rs = \left(\frac{s+r}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{s-r}{2}\right)^2 = 2n - 1 = odd$$

$$\frac{s+r}{2} = \frac{A063655[2n-1]}{2} = \frac{A033677[2n-1] + A033676[2n-1]}{2} = C001745$$

$$\frac{s-r}{2} = \frac{A056737[2n-1]}{2} = \frac{A033677[2n-1] - A033676[2n-1]}{2} = A219695$$

$$d_{c1} * d_{c2} = (C001745)^2 - (A219695)^2 = \left(\frac{A063655[2n-1]}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{A056737[2n-1]}{2}\right)^2$$

$$= A033677[2n-1] * A033676[2n-1] = 2n - 1 = odd$$

The first 60 elements of C001745={1, 2, 3, 4, 3, 6, 7, 4, 9, 10, 5, 12, 5, 6, 15, 16, 7, 6, 19, 8, 21, 22, 7, 24, 7, 10, 27, 8, 11, 30, 31, 8, 9, 34, 13, 36, 37, 10, 9, 40, 9, 42, 11, 16, 45, 10, 17, 12, 49, 10, 51, 52, 11, 54, 55, 20, 57, 14, 11, 12, ...}

$$\left(\frac{s+r}{2}\right)^2 = \left(\frac{A063655[2n-1]}{2}\right)^2 = \left(\frac{A033677[2n-1] + A033676[2n-1]}{2}\right)^2$$

$$= (C001745)^2 = C001746$$

The first 60 elements of C001746={1, 4, 9, 16, 9, 36, 49, 16, 81, 100, 25, 144, 25, 36, 225, 256, 49, 36, 361, 64, 441, 484, 49, 576, 49, 100, 729, 64, 121, 900, 961, 64, 81, 1156, 169, 1296, 1369, 100, 81, 1600, 81, 1764, 121, 256, 2025, 100, 289, 144, 2401, 100, 2601, 2704, 121, 2916, 3025, 400, 3249, 196, 121, 144, ...}

$$\left(\frac{s-r}{2}\right)^2 = \left(\frac{A056737[2n-1]}{2}\right)^2 = \left(\frac{A033677[2n-1] - A033676[2n-1]}{2}\right)^2$$

$$= (A219695)^2 = C001747$$

The first 60 elements of C001747={0, 1, 4, 9, 0, 25, 36, 1, 64, 81, 4, 121, 0, 9, 196, 225, 16, 1, 324, 25, 400, 441, 4, 529, 0, 49, 676, 9, 64, 841, 900, 1, 16, 1089, 100, 1225, 1296, 25, 4, 1521, 0, 1681, 36, 169, 1936, 9, 196, 49, 2304, 1, 2500, 2601, 16, 2809, 2916, 289, 3136, 81, 4, 25, ...}

Notably, record occurrences in C001745, C001746, and C001747 are observed when the odd number (2n - 1) in question is primal, as referenced in the sequences:

<https://oeis.org/A219695>

<https://oeis.org/A033676>

<https://oeis.org/A033677>

<https://oeis.org/A063655>

<https://oeis.org/A056737>

This investigation bridges the geometric properties of number sequences with the algebraic structure of odd numbers.

4.1 Conclusion:

These approaches clarify the concept of complementary divisors and demonstrate the practical application of these mathematical principles. They offer examples of how numbers form and fit into distinct categories based on their algebraic characteristics, providing an engaging and accessible entry point into the study of number sequences and their geometric distribution.

This method illuminates remarkable patterns in the distribution of complementary divisors through the manipulation of derived sequences, showcasing a connection between the geometry of numbers and number theory.

5 Redefining the Visualization of Pairs of Complementary Divisors

The C002452 table below is an evolution of the C002451 table, adapted to present data in a way that facilitates the visualization of relationships and patterns among numbers. In this new table, the number line, previously represented as a column, is now laid out horizontally along the X-axis. The original SqMn and ObMn columns are transformed into horizontal rows, reorganizing the data structure for more intuitive reading in the geometric context of the Cartesian XY plane.

C002452 Table of Geometric Distribution of Pairs of Complementary Divisor by Integer																																
Number $x = rs = r(r+b) = s(s-b)$ with number line in horizontal (X-axis)																																
b																																
25																											0					
24																												0	27			
23																												0	26	26		
22																												0	25	25	25	
21																													0	24	24	24
20																													0	23	23	23
19																													0	22	22	22
18																													0	21	21	21
17																													0	20	20	20
16																													0	19	19	19
15																													0	18	18	18
14																													0	17	17	17
13																													0	16	16	16
12																													0	15	15	15
11																													0	14	14	14
10																													0	13	13	13
9																													0	12	12	12
8																													0	11	11	11
7																													0	10	10	10
6																													0	9	9	9
5																													0	8	8	8
4																													0	7	7	7
3																													0	6	6	6
2																													0	5	5	5
1																													0	4	4	4
0																													0	3	3	3
0																													0	2	2	2
0																													0	1	1	1
0																													0	0	0	0

Figure 9. C002452 Table of Geometric Distribution of Pairs of Complementary Divisors by Integer Number $x = rs = r(r + b) = s(s - b)$ with the number line on the horizontal (X-axis). https://1drv.ms/i/s!Arslv070x3WjkcZD_xUHRBYJSTFOZQ?e=Bdt1Ew

5.1 Key Changes in C002452:

Horizontal Number Line (X-axis): The number line is now extended along the X-axis, providing a direct visualization of the integer sequence and its correspondence with the positions of the 'b' values.

Representation of b Values: Previously in the C002451 table, specific b values indicated the locations of complementary divisor pairs for a given integer x . In the C002452 table, these b values are replaced with '0'. This '0' acts as a marker, pinpointing the vertical position (on the y-axis) where a pair of complementary divisors for x is located.

Distance Between Zeros: The table now records the distance between consecutive '0' markers, which represents the interval on the X-axis between one pair of complementary divisors and the next. This distance quantifies the gap between the integer positions of these pairs along the X-axis.

5.2 Understanding the Table:

Visualizing Complementary Divisor Pairs: The presence of a 0 in the C002452 table directly indicates a point where a number x has a pair of complementary divisors, following the relationship $x = r(r + b) = s(s - b)$. The horizontal structure makes it easier to visually identify where these pairs occur along the numeric sequence.

Measuring Distances: Including the distance between the 0's provides an additional layer of information, highlighting the frequency and regularity of the complementary divisor pairs. This metric offers insights into the underlying structure of the number sequence and the distribution patterns of the divisors.

5.3 Didactic Explanation:

Imagine the C002452 table as a map, where each 0 is a landmark, highlighting the location of a pair of complementary divisors in the vast landscape of integers. The space between these landmarks is not empty but filled with information that measures the distance between them, revealing the rhythm and proximity with which these complementary divisor pairs occur. By transforming the SqMn and ObMn columns into horizontal lines and redefining the b values as 0s, the table not only retains its wealth of data but also becomes a more intuitive guide to exploring the geometric harmony of numbers.

This transformation makes the C002452 table not just a continuation of its predecessor but a more accessible and comprehensive tool for delving into the geometric distribution of pairs of complementary divisors across the integer landscape.

6 Harmonizing Geometry and Number Theory: The Primal Sieve Redefined

The geometry of Table C002452 allows us to construct the following map in GeoGebra using the formulas below:

- *AscendentLines*: $Sequency(x = k y + k^2 - k, k, 1, n)$
- *DescendentLines*: $Sequency(x = -(k y) + k^2 + k, k, 1, n)$
- *SQM[s²]*: $Sequency((k^2 + 2 * s * k, 2 * s + 1), k, 1, n)$
- *ObM[r² - r]*: $Sequency((k^2 + (2 * r - 1) * k, 2 * r), k, 1, n)$

Figure 10. C002453 Mapping Primal Occurrences in Geometrically Defined Oblong Zones (step 1). <https://1drv.ms/i/s!Arslv070x3WjkcZnflirhw5mHPSUrA?e=WiAeHa>

In all our analyses, we conceive of the number line as the X-axis.

The 'AscendentLines' and 'DescendentLines', intersecting at the point $(x^2, 1)$, reveal the points of the complementary divisors that generate multiples of x . For instance, the two lines intersecting at the point $(16,1)$ traverse the points of the complementary divisors producing multiples of 4.

It is observed that all 'AscendentLines' and 'DescendentLines' intersect the X-axis solely at oblong values. Every square number has at least one point at $y = 1$, representing the difference $b = 0$ between the pair of equal complementary divisors.

6.1 Mapping Complementary Divisors: The Geometry of Positive Integers on the Y-axis

Each positive integer coordinate of the y-axis produces the line that covers the points that represent complementary divisors with a non-negative b value. See the figure below:

Figure 11. C002453 Mapping Primal Occurrences in Geometrically Defined Oblong Zones (step 2). <https://1drv.ms/i/s!Arslv070x3WjkcZo3jYk7IElvXX4Yg?e=Ft3xdI>

6.2 Parabolic Distribution Geometry of Divisors

By leveraging the concepts derived from the parabolic sieve proposed by Yuri Matiyasevich and Boris Stechkin in 1999, in 'A Visual Sieve for Prime Numbers', available online at <https://logic.pdmi.ras.ru/~yumat/personaljournal/sieve/sieve.html>, we adapt this methodology to explore the parabolic configurations formed geometrically by points representing complementary divisors. This approach leads us to identify two specific sequences of D-parabolas, unveiling the underlying patterns of divisors and their relationships with primal numbers.

- *DsqParabola*: Sequency($x = (-y^2 + 2y + 4k^2 - 1)/4, k, 0, n$) in orange color.
- *DobParabola*: Sequency($x = (-y^2 + 2y + 4(k^2 - k))/4, k, 0, n$) in green color.

Figure 12. C002453 Mapping Primal Occurrences in Geometrically Defined Oblong Zones (step 3). <https://1drv.ms/i/s!Arslv070x3WjkcZp0LrguDW7R3Wlxw?e=1EYPJd>

6.3 Unified Geometry of Divisors: Parabolic and Linear Perspectives

In the comprehensive synthesis provided, we get:

Figure 13. C002453 Mapping Primal Occurrences in Geometrically Defined Oblong Zones (step 4). https://1drv.ms/i/s!Arslv070x3WjkcZqKHSE_nFe_gdxtQ?e=z4uHxJ

This map elucidates how all integer coordinate points result from intersections among ascending diagonal lines, descending lines, and parabolas. The y coordinate of these points signifies the difference between the divisor values in each complementary pair. Notably, only compound numbers on the X-axis have verticals that intersect the parabolas at more than one point with integer coordinates.

6.4 Investigating Number Theory: Oblong Numbers as a Path to Primality

Due to the similarity between triangles, all integers distributed along the X-axis can be sifted in relation to oblong numbers smaller than them. For instance, consider the number 21. The oblong numbers smaller than 21 are 0, 2, 6, 12, and 20. Analyzing these through subtraction and ratio analysis yields insights into the divisibility and primality of 21, demonstrating it is not primal. Similar examinations of numbers 22, 23, 24, and 25 reveal their divisibility properties, using oblong numbers as a reference. This method provides a novel lens through which the primality of numbers can be investigated, illustrated through specific examples and their outcomes:

For 21:

- $21 - 20 = 1$, inconclusive.
- $21 - 12 = 9$; $12/9$ is reducible as both numerator and denominator share the divisor 3, indicating 21 is not primal. Continuing, $12/9 = 4/3$ and $4 + 3 = 7$, which is a divisor of 21.
- $21 - 6 = 15$; $6/15$ is also reducible, sharing the divisor 3. $6/15 = 2/5$ and $2 + 5 = 7$, another divisor of 21.
- $21 - 2 = 19$; $2/19$ is irreducible as 2 is primal. $2 + 19 = 21$, a divisor of 21.

- $21 - 0 = 21$; $0/21$ is reducible as both share the divisor 21. $0/21 = 0/1$ and $0 + 1 = 1$, a divisor of 21.

For 22 through 25, a similar process unfolds, where the relationship between the number in question and smaller oblong numbers is examined. Each step elucidates whether the number can be classified as primal, or compound based on the reducibility of ratios formed between the difference of the number and its preceding oblong numbers.

Incorporating the unique perspective on the primality of the number 1, as well as redefining the conventional understanding of prime numbers, this approach to exploring primality, alongside those presented in various studies, does not exclude the number 1 from being considered a prime. Contrary to traditional mathematical definitions that categorize 1 neither as prime nor composite, our exploration reveals that the properties of primality for 1 align with those of prime numbers such as 2, 3, 5, 7, 11, etc. This observation leads us to treat the primality of 1 on par with other prime numbers throughout this study.

To adhere to and not contravene standard mathematical principles, we adopt the terms 'primals' and 'compounds' to describe numbers, drawing upon the concepts as defined and discussed in the publication "Integers are only Primals and Compounds" (https://www.researchgate.net/publication/379381586_Integers_are_only_Primals_and_Compounds). This nomenclature allows us to inclusively examine the number 1 within the broader context of primality without stepping outside established mathematical frameworks. By considering 'primals' to encompass what are traditionally known as prime numbers, including 1, and 'compounds' to represent composite numbers including 0, we open a novel avenue for analyzing the fundamental nature of numbers and their intrinsic properties. This methodology not only enriches our understanding of number theory but also ensures a cohesive and inclusive approach to defining and investigating the primality and divisibility of integers within the mathematical landscape.

7 Squares and Oblongs: Defining the Integer Number Distribution

7.1 Investigating the Presence of Primal Numbers within Oblong and Square Intervals

One of the intriguing questions in number theory concerns the guaranteed presence of at least one primal number between an oblong number and the succeeding square (termed the OS sector <https://oeis.org/A334163>) and vice versa (the SO sector <https://oeis.org/A307508>). This phenomenon prompts a geometric examination of how oblong numbers partition the numerical line in the XY plane, particularly focusing on the alignment of all pairs of complementary divisors.

7.2 Geometric Distribution and Oblong Divisor Inclinations

As depicted in figure below, "C002453 Mapping Primal Occurrences in Geometrically Defined Oblong Zones (step 5)," our investigation reveals that vertical semi rays originate from oblong numbers positioned along the horizontal X-axis.

Figure 14. C002453 Mapping Primal Occurrences in Geometrically Defined Oblong Zones (step 5). <https://1drv.ms/i/s!Arslv070x3WjkcZr0oBRbq9JmlsrPg?e=Tjbzer>

At these oblong points, inclined lines encompass all points representing the complementary divisors of integers on the X-axis, establishing a clear geometric relationship. For instance, at the oblong number $0 * 1 = 0$, the slope is $1:1$; for $1 * 2 = 2$, the slope becomes $1:2$; this pattern continues, with the slope at oblong $(n - 1)n$ being $1:n$, or at oblong $n(n + 1)$, $1:(n + 1)$.

7.3 Focusing on Odd Numbers and Prime (Primal) Distribution

A pivotal aspect of our geometric framework is the emphasis on analyzing the distribution of primal numbers predominantly among odd integers. This focus is underpinned by recognizing the singular primal status of the number 2—the only oblong primal number—and similarly unique characteristics of the square primal number 1, alongside 3, the sole primal in the form of (square minus 1). Given these premises, the exploration of primal distribution narrows to exclude even numbers beyond the primal oblong number 2, as their compound nature offers no additional insight into primal phenomena.

7.4 Categorization of Oblong Zones

Our examination introduces a refined classification of oblong numbers, segregating them into two distinct categories based on the parity of the numbers that generate them:

- **0620-Oblong** (Illustrated in OEIS as <https://oeis.org/A002943>, with visual representation in "Twin Diamond Stars" at <https://oeis.org/A002943/a002943.jpg>): This category encompasses oblong numbers generated by an even number n (represented as $2k$), yielding formations such as $(2k - 2)(2k - 1)$ or $(2k)(2k + 1)$.

The sequence—0, 6, 20, 42, 72, etc.—is notably produced by consecutive even numbers multiplied by their successors, aligning with a visually compelling geometric representation.

- **0212-Oblong** (Referenced in OEIS as <https://oeis.org/A002939> with visual representation below): These oblong numbers are defined by the product of an odd number n (expressed as $2k - 1$) with its successor, thus adopting forms such as $(2k - 1)(2k)$ or $(2k + 1)(2k + 2)$. Notably, the sequence—0, 2, 12, 30, 56, 90, etc.—is characterized by its derivation from consecutive odd numbers multiplied by their successors, offering a distinctive geometric and numerical pattern for further exploration.

Figure 15. Visual Representation for 0212-Oblong Numbers at <https://oeis.org/A002939>.

The deliberate demarcation into '0212-Oblong' and '0620-Oblong' zones, based on the generating numbers' parity, is a strategy to deepen our understanding of primal numbers' distribution. By applying a similar principle of selective examination to square numbers as is done with even numbers beyond the primal oblong number 2, we refine our investigative focus to zones where the potential for uncovering novel primal characteristics is highest.

7.5 Square Zones and Primal Distribution

Parallel to the exploration of vertical and inclined lines originating from oblong numbers, an analogous methodology can be applied to square numbers. This approach involves tracing both vertical and inclined lines that begin at square numbers, completing our geometric analysis of the number line. In adherence to the principle of focusing exclusively on odd numbers for the study of primal distribution, it necessitates a division of the numeric line into zones demarcated by consecutive even-squares and consecutive odd-squares. This division is guided by the parity of the squares, a strategy that mirrors our approach with oblong numbers, albeit adapted for squares.

Figure 16. C002453 Mapping Primal Occurrences in Geometrically Defined Oblong Zones (step 6). <https://1drv.ms/i/s!Arslv070x3WjkcZsD9G-TrRktZS1LA?e=ZSwlDn>

7.6 Incorporating Square Numbers into Geometric Analysis

By drawing vertical and inclined lines from square numbers, we extend our geometric framework to encompass another fundamental set of numbers within the numerical landscape.

The distinction between even-squares and odd-squares is pivotal. Even-squares are those square numbers where the square root is an even number, whereas odd-squares are derived from the squaring of odd numbers. This categorization introduces a systematic way to analyze the numerical line, segmenting it into zones that are bordered by sequences of square numbers with matching parity.

8 Mapping the Number of Odd Primals and Odd Compounds Between Zones Delimited by Squares and Oblongs

In the forthcoming chapter, we embark on a detailed exposition of our findings derived from mapping the number of odd primal numbers situated between zones generated by distinct numerical sequences. These zones encompass odd integers within 0212-Oblong Zones, odd integers within 0620-Oblong Zones, odd integers within Odd Square Zones, and odd integers within Even Square Zones.

8.1 Table C001751: Mapping the Number of Odd Primals and Odd Compounds Between 0212-Oblongs

The table below provides an exploration of the relationship between the count of primal numbers and odd compound numbers within intervals delineated by “0212-Oblong” numbers that are derived from consecutive odd numbers.

C001751 Mapping the Number of Odd Primals and Odd Compounds Between Zones Delimited by 0212-Oblong Numbers										
A	B	C	D	E	F = E - D	G = F/2	H = E/2	I	J = dif (H)	K = G - J
Integer	Odd Numbers	Odd Numbers + 2	Start Point: 0212-Oblongs (Odd(Odd+1))	End Point: Next 0212-Oblongs ((Odd+2)(Odd+3))	Difference to Next 0212-Oblong	Number of Odd Numbers Betw een 0212-Oblong Zones	Number of Odd Numbers Up to Next 0212-Oblong	Number of Odd Primals Up to 0212-Oblong"	Number of Odd Primals Betw een Consecutive 0212-Oblongs	Number of Odd Compounds Betw een Consecutive 0212-Oblongs
n	2n - 1	2n + 1	4n ² -2n	4n ² +6n+2	8*n + 2	4*n + 1	2n ² +3n+1	primepi(E)	dif primepi(E)	# Odds - # Odd Primals
0	-1	1	0	2	2	1	1	1	1	0
1	1	3	2	12	10	5	6	5	4	1
2	3	5	12	30	18	9	15	10	5	4
3	5	7	30	56	26	13	28	16	6	7
4	7	9	56	90	34	17	45	24	8	9
5	9	11	90	132	42	21	66	32	8	13
6	11	13	132	182	50	25	91	42	10	15
7	13	15	182	240	58	29	120	52	10	19
8	15	17	240	306	66	33	153	62	10	23
9	17	19	306	380	74	37	190	75	13	24
10	19	21	380	462	82	41	231	89	14	27
11	21	23	462	552	90	45	276	101	12	33
12	23	25	552	650	98	49	325	118	17	32
13	25	27	650	756	106	53	378	133	15	38
14	27	29	756	870	114	57	435	150	17	40
15	29	31	870	992	122	61	496	167	17	44
16	31	33	992	1122	130	65	561	187	20	45
17	33	35	1122	1260	138	69	630	205	18	51
18	35	37	1260	1406	146	73	703	222	17	56
19	37	39	1406	1560	154	77	780	246	24	53
20	39	41	1560	1722	162	81	861	268	22	59
21	41	43	1722	1892	170	85	946	290	22	63
22	43	45	1892	2070	178	89	1035	312	22	67
23	45	47	2070	2256	186	93	1128	335	23	70
24	47	49	2256	2450	194	97	1225	363	28	69
25	49	51	2450	2652	202	101	1326	383	20	81

Figure 17. C001751 Mapping the Number of Odd Primals and Odd Compounds Between Zones Delimited by 0212-Oblong Numbers. https://1drv.ms/i/s!Arslv070x3WjkcZxqOnK8J-MPy_8tA?e=DOYcDY

8.2 Table C001752: Mapping the Number of Odd Primals and Odd Compounds Between 0620-Oblongs

C001752 Mapping the Number of Odd Primals and Odd Compounds Between Zones Delimited by 0620-Oblong Numbers										
A	B	C	D	E	F = E - D	G = F/2	H = E/2	I	J = dif (H)	K = G - J
Integer	Even Numbers	Even Numbers + 2	Start Point: 0620-Oblongs (Even(Even+1))	End Point: Next 0620-Oblongs ((Even+2)(Even+3))	Difference to Next 0620-Oblong	Number of Odd Numbers Between 0620-Oblong Zones	Number of Odd Numbers Up to Next 0620-Oblong	Number of Odd Primals Up to 0620-Oblong"	Number of Odd Primals Between Consecutive 0620-Oblongs	Number of Odd Compounds Between Consecutive 0620-Oblongs
n	2n	2n + 2	4n ² +2n	4n ² +10n+6	8*n + 6	4*n + 3	2n ² +5n+3	primepi(E)	dif primepi(E)	# Odds - # Odd Primals
0	0	2	0	6	6	3	3	3	3	0
1	2	4	6	20	14	7	10	8	5	2
2	4	6	20	42	22	11	21	13	5	6
3	6	8	42	72	30	15	36	20	7	8
4	8	10	72	110	38	19	55	29	9	10
5	10	12	110	156	46	23	78	36	7	16
6	12	14	156	210	54	27	105	46	10	17
7	14	16	210	272	62	31	136	58	12	19
8	16	18	272	342	70	35	171	68	10	25
9	18	20	342	420	78	39	210	81	13	26
10	20	22	420	506	86	43	253	96	15	28
11	22	24	506	600	94	47	300	109	13	34
12	24	26	600	702	102	51	351	126	17	34
13	26	28	702	812	110	55	406	141	15	40
14	28	30	812	930	118	59	465	158	17	42
15	30	32	930	1056	126	63	528	177	19	44
16	32	34	1056	1190	134	67	595	195	18	49
17	34	36	1190	1332	142	71	666	217	22	49
18	36	38	1332	1482	150	75	741	234	17	58
19	38	40	1482	1640	158	79	820	259	25	54
20	40	42	1640	1806	166	83	903	279	20	63
21	42	44	1806	1980	174	87	990	299	20	67
22	44	46	1980	2162	182	91	1081	326	27	64
23	46	48	2162	2352	190	95	1176	349	23	72
24	48	50	2352	2550	198	99	1275	373	24	75
25	50	52	2550	2756	206	103	1378	402	29	74

Figure 18. C001752 Mapping the Number of Odd Primals and Odd Compounds Between Zones Delimited by 0620-Oblong Numbers. <https://1drv.ms/i/s!Arslv070x3WjkcZygphgerQnC-VUyw?e=PdpDUX>

8.3 Table C001753: Mapping the Number of Odd Primals and Odd Compounds Between Odd Squares

C001753 Mapping the Number of Odd Primals and Odd Compounds Between Zones Delimited by Odd Square Numbers										
A	B	C	D	E	F = E - D	G = F/2	H = E/2	I	J = dif (H)	K = G - J
Integer	Odd Numbers	Odd Numbers + 2	Start Point: Odd Squares (Odd ²)	End Point: Next Odd Square ((Odd+2) ²)	Difference to Next Odd Square	Number of Odd Numbers Between Odd Square Zones	Number of Odd Numbers Up to Next Odd Square	Number of Odd Primals Up to Odd Square	Number of Odd Primals Between Consecutive Odd Squares	Number of Odd Compounds Between Consecutive Odd Squares
n	2n - 1	2n + 1	4n ² -4n+1	4n ² +4n+1	8*n	4*n	2n ² +2n	primepi(E)	dif primepi(E)	# Odds - # Odd Primals
0	-1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
1	1	3	1	9	8	4	4	4	4	0
2	3	5	9	25	16	8	12	9	5	3
3	5	7	25	49	24	12	24	15	6	6
4	7	9	49	81	32	16	40	22	7	9
5	9	11	81	121	40	20	60	30	8	12
6	11	13	121	169	48	24	84	39	9	15
7	13	15	169	225	56	28	112	48	9	19
8	15	17	225	289	64	32	144	61	13	19
9	17	19	289	361	72	36	180	72	11	25
10	19	21	361	441	80	40	220	85	13	27
11	21	23	441	529	88	44	264	99	14	30
12	23	25	529	625	96	48	312	114	15	33
13	25	27	625	729	104	52	364	129	15	37
14	27	29	729	841	112	56	420	146	17	39
15	29	31	841	961	120	60	480	162	16	44
16	31	33	961	1089	128	64	544	181	19	45
17	33	35	1089	1225	136	68	612	200	19	49
18	35	37	1225	1369	144	72	684	219	19	53
19	37	39	1369	1521	152	76	760	240	21	55
20	39	41	1521	1681	160	80	840	263	23	57
21	41	43	1681	1849	168	84	924	283	20	64
22	43	45	1849	2025	176	88	1012	306	23	65
23	45	47	2025	2209	184	92	1104	329	23	69
24	47	49	2209	2401	192	96	1200	357	28	68
25	49	51	2401	2601	200	100	1300	378	21	79

Figure 19. C001753 Mapping the Number of Odd Primals and Odd Compounds Between Zones Delimited by Odd Square Numbers. https://1drv.ms/i/s!Arslv070x3WjkcZznw-qtrqX_GxeWA?e=mDWIhf

8.4 Table C001754: Mapping the Number of Odd Primals and Odd Compounds Between Even Squares

C001754 Mapping the Number of Odd Primals and Odd Compounds Between Zones Delimited by Even Square Numbers										
A	B	C	D	E	F = E - D	G = F/2	H = E/2	I	J = dif (H)	K = G - J
Integer	Even Numbers	Even Numbers + 2	Start Point: Even Squares (Even ²)	End Point: Next Even Squares ((Even+2) ²)	Difference to Next Even Square	Number of Odd Numbers Between Even Square Zones	Number of Odd Numbers Up to Next Even Square	Number of Odd Primals Up to Even Square	Number of Odd Primals Between Consecutive Odd Squares	Number of Odd Compounds Between Consecutive Odd Squares
n	2n	2n + 2	4n ²	4n ² +8n+4	8*n + 4	4*n + 2	2n ² +4n+3	primepi(E)	dif primepi(E)	# Odds - # Odd Primals
0	0	2	0	4	4	2	3	2	2	0
1	2	4	4	16	12	6	9	6	4	2
2	4	6	16	36	20	10	19	11	5	5
3	6	8	36	64	28	14	33	18	7	7
4	8	10	64	100	36	18	51	25	7	11
5	10	12	100	144	44	22	73	34	9	13
6	12	14	144	196	52	26	99	44	10	16
7	14	16	196	256	60	30	129	54	10	20
8	16	18	256	324	68	34	163	66	12	22
9	18	20	324	400	76	38	201	78	12	26
10	20	22	400	484	84	42	243	92	14	28
11	22	24	484	576	92	46	289	105	13	33
12	24	26	576	676	100	50	339	122	17	33
13	26	28	676	784	108	54	393	137	15	39
14	28	30	784	900	116	58	451	154	17	41
15	30	32	900	1024	124	62	513	172	18	44
16	32	34	1024	1156	132	66	579	191	19	47
17	34	36	1156	1296	140	70	649	210	19	51
18	36	38	1296	1444	148	74	723	228	18	56
19	38	40	1444	1600	156	78	801	251	23	55
20	40	42	1600	1764	164	82	883	274	23	59
21	42	44	1764	1936	172	86	969	295	21	65
22	44	46	1936	2116	180	90	1059	319	24	66
23	46	48	2116	2304	188	94	1153	342	23	71
24	48	50	2304	2500	196	98	1251	367	25	73
25	50	52	2500	2704	204	102	1353	393	26	76

Figure 20. C001754 Mapping the Number of Odd Primals and Odd Compounds Between Zones Delimited by Even Square Numbers. <https://1drv.ms/i/s!Arslv070x3WjkcZ0uydXX-DgBbFUfA?e=FyEWtB>

8.5 Explanations

For a more coherent understanding across the four tables—C001751, C001752, C001753, and C001754—each focusing on different numerical zones, we'll explain the unique formulaic distinctions of each table column that highlights the varied approaches to examining the

distribution of odd primal and odd compound numbers. This unified text emphasizes the differences in formulas tailored to the specific numerical constructs of 0212-Oblong Zones, 0620-Oblong Zones, Odd Square Zones, and Even Square Zones.

Integer (Column A)

Across all tables, this column serves as the foundational sequence of integers (n), which underpins the calculations in subsequent columns.

Even or Odd Numbers (Columns B and C)

For C001751 (0212-Oblong) and C001753 (Odd Square Zones): These columns generate sequences of odd numbers using the formula $2n - 1$ for Column B and their successors $2n + 1$ for Column C, underscoring the emphasis on odd numerical constructs within these zones.

For C001752 (0620-Oblong) and C001754 (Even Square Zones): In contrast, these tables produce sequences of even numbers with $2n$ for Column B and their successors $2n + 2$ for Column C.

Start and End Points (Columns D and E)

These columns define the intervals for analysis, with their formulas varying across tables due to the distinct numerical constructs they each focus on:

- 0212-Oblong Zones (C001751): Start points are given by $(4n^2 - 2n)$, and end points by $(4n^2 + 6n + 2)$, focusing on intervals between numbers formed by the product of consecutive odd and even numbers.
- 0620-Oblong Zones (C001752): Utilizes $(4n^2 + 2n)$ for start points and $(4n^2 + 10n + 6)$ for end points, reflecting intervals between numbers formed by the product of consecutive even and the next odd numbers.
- Odd Square Zones (C001753): Applies $(4n^2 - 4n + 1)$ for start and $(4n^2 + 4n + 1)$ for end points, concentrating on intervals between squares of consecutive odd numbers.
- Even Square Zones (C001754): Employs $(4n^2)$ for start points and $(4n^2 + 8n + 4)$ for end points, covering intervals between squares of consecutive even numbers.

Difference to Next Zone (Column F)

The formulas here reflect how numerical intervals expand or contract based on the zone's nature:

- 0212 and 0620-Oblong Zones: Both adjust their formulas to account for the oblong nature, with 0212-Oblong using $(8n + 2)$ and 0620-Oblong $(8n + 6)$, indicating varying gap sizes between zones.

- Odd and Even Square Zones: Odd Squares use $(8n)$, highlighting consistent gaps between odd squares, while Even Squares adjust with $(8n + 4)$, reflecting the structured progression of even squares.

Number of Odd Numbers (Columns G and H)

Columns G and H are dedicated to the calculation of the number of odd numbers within the delineated zones and their cumulative count up to the boundary of the next zone.

- For 0212-Oblong Zones: The formulas $4n + 1$ for Column G and $2n^2 + 3n + 1$ for Column H are utilized, corresponding to the progression pattern of 0212-oblong numbers.
- For 0620-Oblong Zones: Formulas $4n + 3$ and $2n^2 + 5n + 3$ are applied to match the interval progression of 0620-oblong numbers, providing the count of odd numbers within and up to these oblong zones.
- For Odd Square Zones: The sequence of odd squares is addressed with simpler formulas: $4n$ for Column G, indicating the number of odd numbers between odd square zones, and $2n^2 + 2n$ for Column H, offering the cumulative odd number count up to the next odd square.
- For Even Square Zones: The calculations adjust to $4n + 2$ for Column G, reflecting the total odd numbers between even square zones, and $2n^2 + 4n + 3$ for Column H, tallying the cumulative odd numbers up to the next even square.

Odd Primals (Columns I to K)

The calculation of odd primals up to each zone, their change between consecutive zones, and the resulting count of odd compounds, while following a general approach using the `primepi` function, subtly adjusts to the specifics of each zone type:

- The inclusion of 1 as an odd primal adjusts the application of `primepi`, ensuring accurate counts that align with the study's unique focus across different numerical constructs.
- The differences in the count of odd primal numbers between zones (Column J) and the determination of odd compounds (Column K) are nuanced to reflect the nature of each zone, providing insights into the distribution within these specifically delineated intervals.

In our study, which examines the distribution of odd primal numbers within Squares and Oblong Zones, the “primepi” function is applied with a specific interpretation. While `primepi` typically counts primes up to a certain number, including the even prime 2, our framework uniquely categorizes the number 1 as an "odd primal," diverging from its standard exclusion in prime number theory. Thus, “primepi” effectively counts 1 in place of 2 for our purposes, aligning with our focus on odd primals. This adaptation ensures our analysis remains consistent with our definitions while accurately investigating odd primal number distribution.

9 Mapping the Odd Primals and Odd Compounds Between Zones Delimited by Squares and Oblongs

We now explore the distribution of odd integers as categorized by the zones delineated in Tables C001751, C001752, C001753, and C001754, focusing specifically on their placement along the odd number continuum. This examination has led to the creation of four new tables, each dedicated to a distinct type of zone:

9.1 C001755: Distribution of Odd Integers Within 0212-Oblong Zones

This table outlines how odd integers are situated within zones framed by 0212-oblong numbers.

C001755 Odd Integers Within 0212-Oblong Zones										
Start Point: 0212-Oblongs (Odd(Odd+1))	End Point: Next 0212-Oblongs ((Odd+2)(Odd+3))	Number of Odd Numbers Between 0212-Oblong Zones	Tally From Start Points	Negative Tally From Start Points	Odd Integer	3 ≤ Positive Odd Divisors ≤ sqrt(Odd Integer)				
						3	5	7	9	11
0	2	1	1	0	1					
2	12	5	1	-4	3					
			2	-3	5					
			3	-2	7					
			4	-1	9	3				
			5	0	11					
12	30	9	1	-8	13					
			2	-7	15	3				
			3	-6	17					
			4	-5	19					
			5	-4	21	3				
			6	-3	23					
			7	-2	25		5			
			8	-1	27	3				
			9	0	29					
30	56	13	1	-12	31					
			2	-11	33	3				
			3	-10	35		5			
			4	-9	37					
			5	-8	39	3				
			6	-7	41					
			7	-6	43					
			8	-5	45	3	5			
			9	-4	47					
			10	-3	49			7		
			11	-2	51	3				
			12	-1	53					
			13	0	55		5			
56	90	17	1	-16	57	3				
			2	-15	59					
			3	-14	61					
			4	-13	63	3		7		
			5	-12	65		5			
			6	-11	67					
			7	-10	69	3				
			8	-9	71					
			9	-8	73					
			10	-7	75	3	5			
			11	-6	77			7		
			12	-5	79					
			13	-4	81	3			9	
			14	-3	83					
			15	-2	85		5			
			16	-1	87	3				
			17	0	89					
90	132	21	1	-20	91			7		
			2	-19	93	3				
			3	-18	95		5			
			4	-17	97					
			5	-16	99	3			9	
			6	-15	101					
			7	-14	103					
			8	-13	105	3	5	7		
			9	-12	107					
			10	-11	109					
			11	-10	111	3				
			12	-9	113					
			13	-8	115		5			
			14	-7	117	3			9	
			15	-6	119			7		
			16	-5	121				11	
			17	-4	123	3				
			18	-3	125		5			
			19	-2	127					
			20	-1	129	3				
			21	0	131					

Figure 21. C001755 Mapping the Distribution of Odd Integers Within 0212-Oblong Zones.

<https://1drv.ms/i/s!Arslv070x3WjkcZ12td5x-nZkne7Eg?e=f8RtFp>

9.2 C001756: Distribution of Odd Integers Within 0620-Oblong Zones

Here, the focus shifts to the arrangement of odd integers within the intervals marked by 0620-oblong numbers.

C001756 Odd Integers Within 0620-Oblong Zones										
Start Point: 0620-Oblongs (Even(Even+1))	End Point: Next 0620-Oblongs ((Even+2)(Even+3))	Number of Odd Numbers Between 0620-Oblong Zones	Tally From Start Points	Negative Tally From Start Points	Odd Integer	$3 \leq \text{Positive Odd Divisors} \leq \text{sqrt}(\text{Odd Integer})$				
						3	5	7	9	11
0	6	3	1	-2	1					
			2	-1	3					
			3	0	5					
6	20	7	1	-6	7					
			2	-5	9	3				
			3	-4	11					
			4	-3	13					
			5	-2	15	3				
			6	-1	17					
			7	0	19					
20	42	11	1	-10	21	3				
			2	-9	23					
			3	-8	25			5		
			4	-7	27	3				
			5	-6	29					
			6	-5	31					
			7	-4	33	3				
			8	-3	35			5		
			9	-2	37					
			10	-1	39	3				
			11	0	41					
42	72	15	1	-14	43					
			2	-13	45	3		5		
			3	-12	47					
			4	-11	49				7	
			5	-10	51	3				
			6	-9	53					
			7	-8	55			5		
			8	-7	57	3				
			9	-6	59					
			10	-5	61					
			11	-4	63	3			7	
			12	-3	65			5		
			13	-2	67					
			14	-1	69	3				
			15	0	71					
72	110	19	1	-18	73					
			2	-17	75	3		5		
			3	-16	77				7	
			4	-15	79					
			5	-14	81	3				9
			6	-13	83					
			7	-12	85			5		
			8	-11	87	3				
			9	-10	89					
			10	-9	91				7	
			11	-8	93	3				
			12	-7	95			5		
			13	-6	97					
			14	-5	99	3				9
			15	-4	101					
			16	-3	103					
			17	-2	105	3		5		7
			18	-1	107					
			19	0	109					
110	156	23	1	-22	111	3				
			2	-21	113					
			3	-20	115			5		
			4	-19	117	3				9
			5	-18	119				7	
			6	-17	121					11
			7	-16	123	3				
			8	-15	125			5		
			9	-14	127					
			10	-13	129	3				
			11	-12	131					
			12	-11	133				7	
			13	-10	135	3		5		9
			14	-9	137					
			15	-8	139					
			16	-7	141	3				
			17	-6	143					11
			18	-5	145			5		
			19	-4	147	3			7	
			20	-3	149					
			21	-2	151					
			22	-1	153	3				9
			23	0	155				5	

Figure 22. C001756 Mapping the Distribution of Odd Integers Within 0620-Oblong Zones.

<https://1drv.ms/i/s!Arslv070x3WjkcZ2SHazK9HRqTP9lw?e=Qe7LRL>

9.3 C001757: Distribution of Odd Integers Within Odd Square Zones

This table examines the placement of odd integers within zones bounded by odd square numbers.

C001757 Odd Integers Within Odd Square Zones										
Start Point: Odd Squares (Odd ²)	End Point: Next Odd Square ((Odd+2) ²)	Number of Odd Numbers Between Odd Square Zones	Tally From Start Points	Negative Tally From Start Points	Odd Integer	3 ≤ Positive Odd Divisors ≤ sqrt(Odd Integer)				
						3	5	7	9	11
1	9	4	1	-3	1					
			2	-2	3					
			3	-1	5					
			4	0	7					
9	25	8	1	-7	9	3				
			2	-6	11					
			3	-5	13					
			4	-4	15	3				
			5	-3	17					
			6	-2	19					
			7	-1	21	3				
			8	0	23					
25	49	12	1	-11	25			5		
			2	-10	27	3				
			3	-9	29					
			4	-8	31					
			5	-7	33	3				
			6	-6	35			5		
			7	-5	37					
			8	-4	39	3				
			9	-3	41					
			10	-2	43					
			11	-1	45	3		5		
			12	0	47					
49	81	16	1	-15	49				7	
			2	-14	51	3				
			3	-13	53					
			4	-12	55			5		
			5	-11	57	3				
			6	-10	59					
			7	-9	61					
			8	-8	63	3			7	
			9	-7	65			5		
			10	-6	67					
			11	-5	69	3				
			12	-4	71					
			13	-3	73					
			14	-2	75	3		5		
			15	-1	77					7
			16	0	79					
81	121	20	1	-19	81	3			9	
			2	-18	83					
			3	-17	85			5		
			4	-16	87	3				
			5	-15	89					
			6	-14	91				7	
			7	-13	93	3				
			8	-12	95			5		
			9	-11	97					
			10	-10	99	3				9
			11	-9	101					
			12	-8	103					
			13	-7	105	3		5		7
			14	-6	107					
			15	-5	109					
			16	-4	111	3				
			17	-3	113					
			18	-2	115			5		
			19	-1	117	3				9
			20	0	119					7
121	169	24	1	-23	121					11
			2	-22	123	3				
			3	-21	125			5		
			4	-20	127					
			5	-19	129	3				
			6	-18	131					
			7	-17	133				7	
			8	-16	135	3		5		9
			9	-15	137					
			10	-14	139					
			11	-13	141	3				
			12	-12	143					11
			13	-11	145			5		
			14	-10	147	3			7	
			15	-9	149					
			16	-8	151					
			17	-7	153	3				9
			18	-6	155			5		
			19	-5	157					
			20	-4	159	3				
			21	-3	161				7	
			22	-2	163					
			23	-1	165	3		5		11
			24	0	167					

Figure 23. C001757 Mapping the Distribution of Odd Integers Within Odd Square Zones.

<https://1drv.ms/i/s!Arslv070x3WjkcZ3S6uqhBGBQqBLcA?e=ztrWKf>

9.4 C001758: Distribution of Odd Integers Within Even Square Zones

Lastly, the distribution of odd integers within zones delineated by even square numbers is detailed.

C001758 Odd Integers Within Even Square Zones						$3 \leq \text{Positive Odd Divisors} \leq \sqrt{\text{Odd Integer}}$				
Start Point: Odd Squares (Odd ²)	End Point: Next Even Squares ((Even+2) ²)	Number of Odd Numbers Between Even Square Zones	Tally From Start Points	Negative Tally From Start Points	Odd Integer	3	5	7	9	11
0	4	2	1	-1	1					
			2	0	3					
4	16	6	1	-5	5					
			2	-4	7					
			3	-3	9	3				
			4	-2	11					
			5	-1	13					
			6	0	15	3				
16	36	10	1	-9	17					
			2	-8	19					
			3	-7	21	3				
			4	-6	23					
			5	-5	25		5			
			6	-4	27	3				
			7	-3	29					
			8	-2	31					
			9	-1	33	3				
			10	0	35		5			
36	64	14	1	-13	37					
			2	-12	39	3				
			3	-11	41					
			4	-10	43					
			5	-9	45	3	5			
			6	-8	47					
			7	-7	49			7		
			8	-6	51	3				
			9	-5	53					
			10	-4	55		5			
			11	-3	57	3				
			12	-2	59					
			13	-1	61					
			14	0	63	3		7		
64	100	18	1	-17	65		5			
			2	-16	67					
			3	-15	69	3				
			4	-14	71					
			5	-13	73					
			6	-12	75	3	5			
			7	-11	77			7		
			8	-10	79					
			9	-9	81	3			9	
			10	-8	83					
			11	-7	85		5			
			12	-6	87	3				
			13	-5	89					
			14	-4	91			7		
			15	-3	93	3				
			16	-2	95		5			
			17	-1	97					
			18	0	99	3			9	
100	144	22	1	-21	101					
			2	-20	103					
			3	-19	105	3	5	7		
			4	-18	107					
			5	-17	109					
			6	-16	111	3				
			7	-15	113					
			8	-14	115		5			
			9	-13	117	3			9	
			10	-12	119			7		
			11	-11	121					
			12	-10	123	3				
			13	-9	125		5			
			14	-8	127					
			15	-7	129	3				
			16	-6	131					
			17	-5	133			7		
			18	-4	135	3	5		9	
			19	-3	137					
			20	-2	139					
			21	-1	141	3				
			22	0	143				11	

Figure 24. C001758 Mapping the Distribution of Odd Integers Within Even Square Zones.

<https://1drv.ms/i/s!Arslv070x3WjkcZ4HVndkqyNOQvS2Q?e=pzswYy>

These tables provide a structured insight into the organization of odd primals and compounds across the different mathematical landscapes defined by squares and oblongs.

9.5 Tables C001755, C001756, C001757, and C001758: A Comparative Overview

These tables collectively map the distribution of odd primal numbers and compounds within zones delineated by mathematical constructs—0212-Oblongs, 0620-Oblongs, Odd Squares, and Even Squares. While each table shares a common goal, they each offer a unique perspective based on the specific delimiting figures.

Start and End Points (Columns A and B):

0212-Oblongs: The start point is defined by 0212-oblong numbers of the form $odd(odd + 1)$, and the end point by the subsequent 0212-oblong number, $(odd + 2)(odd + 3)$.

0620-Oblongs: The zones begin with 0620-oblong numbers calculated by $even(even + 1)$, extending to the next 0620-oblong, $(even + 2)(even + 3)$.

Odd Squares: For odd squares, the sequence starts with odd^2 and stretches to the next odd square, $(odd + 2)^2$.

Even Squares: The table begins with $even^2$ and proceeds to the next even square, $(even + 2)^2$.

Number of Odd Numbers (Column C):

This column uniformly counts the odd numbers between the start and end points, reflecting the odd integer population within each specific zone. The calculation adapts to the zone's nature, ensuring accurate representation of odd integers in the delimited intervals.

Tally Columns (Columns D and E):

The "Tally from Start Points" column provides a sequential count from the beginning of each zone, highlighting the relative position of each odd integer within its zone. This helps us visualize and understand the placement of numbers in the sequence.

The "Negative Tally from Start Points" column, on the other hand, counts in reverse. It includes the analysis of the negative of the difference of two squares in the distribution analysis within the zones, ensuring that all integers are accounted for, back to the origin point.

For each specific zone, whether it is a 0212-Oblong, 0620-Oblong, Odd Square, or Even Square, the tally count begins at the zone's start point. The negative tally, which operates in reverse, is designed to encompass every integer down to position 0, thereby providing a full count that includes the entire range of integers up to the start point.

The tally columns play a crucial role in organizing these tables, as they pinpoint the location of each odd number according to the squares and oblongs that demarcate zones on the number line. It's akin to drawing a detailed map where each odd number is marked in relation to the geometric boundaries established by these squares and oblongs, akin to city blocks. This not only

helps outline where each "resident" (the odd number) lives within its designated "block" (zone), but it also clarifies the organization of these numbers in a highly structured and methodical manner.

Odd Integer Column (Column F):

This column lists odd integers, serving as a reference point for the analysis of primal occurrences and compound formations within each zone.

Divisors Columns (Columns G and onward):

These columns enumerate the positive odd divisors greater than 1 for each odd integer, provided that the divisor is less than or equal to the square root of the odd integer. This restriction ensures a focus on relevant divisors, enhancing the clarity and utility of the divisor-related insights derived from the tables.

10 Parabolic Patterns in Primal and Compound Divisors: Insights from MID Framework Analysis

In the study titled 'Exploring Parabolic Patterns in the Map of Integers and Divisors (MID) Framework,' available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10252480>, we address the interconnectedness of all pairs of complementary divisors of integers through quadratic equations. This relationship encompasses both primal and compound numbers, without exception, highlighting that the structure of divisors is invariably associated with parabolas in the form of squares, with the distances between divisors following the method of differences.

In this same study, as we have just demonstrated above in section '6.2 Parabolic Distribution Geometry of Divisors,' all pairs of complementary divisors are also distributed in a parabolic configuration.

Also, based on '2 Geometric Distribution of Pairs of Complementary Divisors', a crucial aspect of our analysis reveals that covering the divisors of odd numbers is only possible through the difference between squares of even and odd numbers $(odd)^2 - (even)^2$ or $(even)^2 - (odd)^2$, with no alternative to represent the entirety of odd integers through the difference of two squares that does not adhere to this specificity.

Furthermore, we highlight a distinctive feature related to primal numbers: each primal number, whether positive or negative, and when considering only the absolute values of the divisors, is characterized by a single pair of complementary divisors. This contrasts with compounds, which, also when considering only the absolute values of the divisors, exhibit multiple pairs of complementary divisors. Like the Triangular Multiplication Table (TMT), this uniqueness of primal numbers is evidenced in the table C004001 Vertical Odd Squares Minus Horizontal Even Squares: Comprehensive Mapping, in which primal numbers appear only once, whereas compounds are listed at least twice.

C004001 Vertical Odd Squares Minus Horizontal Even Squares: Comprehensive Mapping																																
(ODD Sq.)- (EVEN Sq.)	k	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	
n	2n-1	square	0	4	16	36	64	100	144	196	256	324	400	484	576	676	784	900	1024	1156	1296	1444	1600	1764	1936	2116	2304	2500	2704	2916	3136	3364
1	1	1	-3	-15	-35	-63	-99	-143	-195	-255	-323	-399	-483	-575	-675	-783	-899	-1023	-1155	-1295	-1443	-1599	-1763	-1935	-2115	-2303	-2499	-2703	-2915	-3135	-3363	
2	3	9	5	-7	-27	-55	-91	-135	-187	-247	-315	-391	-475	-567	-667	-775	-891	-1015	-1147	-1287	-1435	-1591	-1755	-1927	-2107	-2295	-2491	-2695	-2907	-3127	-3355	
3	5	25	21	9	-11	-39	-75	-119	-171	-231	-299	-375	-459	-551	-651	-759	-875	-999	-1131	-1271	-1419	-1575	-1739	-1911	-2091	-2279	-2475	-2679	-2891	-3111	-3339	
4	7	49	49	45	33	19	-15	-51	-95	-147	-207	-275	-351	-435	-527	-627	-735	-851	-975	-1107	-1247	-1395	-1551	-1715	-1887	-2067	-2255	-2451	-2655	-2867	-3087	-3315
5	9	81	81	77	65	45	17	-19	-63	-115	-175	-243	-319	-403	-495	-595	-703	-819	-943	-1075	-1215	-1363	-1519	-1683	-1855	-2035	-2223	-2419	-2623	-2835	-3055	-3283
6	11	121	121	117	105	85	57	21	-23	-75	-135	-203	-279	-363	-455	-555	-663	-779	-903	-1035	-1175	-1323	-1479	-1643	-1815	-1995	-2183	-2379	-2583	-2795	-3015	-3243
7	13	169	169	165	153	133	105	69	25	-27	-87	-155	-231	-315	-407	-507	-615	-731	-855	-987	-1127	-1275	-1431	-1595	-1767	-1947	-2135	-2331	-2535	-2747	-2967	-3195
8	15	225	225	221	209	189	161	125	81	29	-31	-99	-175	-259	-351	-451	-559	-675	-799	-931	-1071	-1219	-1375	-1539	-1711	-1891	-2079	-2275	-2479	-2691	-2911	-3139
9	17	289	289	285	273	253	225	189	145	93	33	-35	-111	-195	-287	-387	-495	-611	-735	-867	-1007	-1155	-1311	-1475	-1647	-1827	-2015	-2211	-2415	-2627	-2847	-3075
10	19	361	361	357	345	325	297	261	217	165	105	-87	-139	-215	-315	-423	-539	-663	-795	-935	-1083	-1239	-1403	-1575	-1755	-1943	-2139	-2343	-2555	-2775	-3003	
11	21	441	441	437	425	405	377	341	297	245	185	117	41	-43	-135	-235	-343	-459	-583	-715	-855	-1003	-1159	-1323	-1495	-1675	-1863	-2059	-2263	-2475	-2695	-2923
12	23	529	529	525	513	493	465	429	385	333	275	205	129	45	-47	-147	-255	-371	-495	-627	-767	-915	-1071	-1235	-1407	-1587	-1775	-1971	-2175	-2387	-2607	-2835
13	25	625	625	621	609	589	561	525	481	429	369	301	225	141	43	-51	-159	-275	-399	-531	-671	-819	-975	-1139	-1311	-1491	-1679	-1875	-2079	-2291	-2511	-2739
14	27	729	729	725	713	693	665	629	585	533	473	405	329	245	153	53	-55	-171	-295	-427	-567	-715	-871	-1035	-1207	-1387	-1575	-1771	-1975	-2187	-2407	-2635
15	29	841	841	837	825	805	777	741	697	645	585	517	441	357	265	165	57	-59	-183	-315	-455	-603	-759	-923	-1095	-1275	-1463	-1659	-1863	-2075	-2295	-2523
16	31	961	961	957	945	925	897	861	817	765	705	637	561	477	385	285	177	61	-63	-195	-335	-483	-639	-803	-975	-1155	-1343	-1539	-1743	-1955	-2175	-2403
17	33	1089	1089	1085	1073	1053	1025	989	945	893	833	765	689	605	513	413	305	189	65	-67	-207	-355	-511	-675	-847	-1027	-1215	-1411	-1615	-1827	-2047	-2275
18	35	1225	1225	1221	1209	1189	1161	1125	1081	1029	969	901	825	741	649	549	441	325	201	69	-71	-219	-375	-539	-711	-891	-1079	-1275	-1479	-1691	-1911	-2139
19	37	1369	1369	1365	1353	1333	1305	1269	1225	1173	1113	1045	969	885	793	693	585	469	345	213	-75	-231	-395	-567	-747	-935	-1131	-1335	-1547	-1767	-1995	
20	39	1521	1521	1517	1505	1485	1457	1421	1377	1325	1265	1197	1121	1037	945	845	737	621	497	365	225	77	-79	-243	-415	-595	-783	-979	-1183	-1395	-1615	-1843
21	41	1681	1681	1677	1665	1645	1617	1581	1537	1485	1425	1357	1281	1197	1105	1005	897	781	657	525	385	237	81	-83	-255	-435	-623	-819	-1023	-1235	-1455	-1683
22	43	1849	1849	1845	1833	1813	1785	1749	1705	1653	1593	1525	1449	1365	1273	1173	1065	949	825	693	553	405	249	85	-87	-267	-455	-651	-855	-1067	-1287	-1515
23	45	2025	2025	2021	2009	1989	1961	1925	1881	1829	1769	1701	1625	1541	1449	1349	1241	1125	1001	869	729	581	425	261	89	-91	-279	-475	-679	-891	-1111	-1339
24	47	2209	2209	2205	2193	2173	2145	2109	2065	2013	1953	1885	1809	1725	1633	1533	1425	1309	1185	1053	913	765	609	445	273	93	-95	-291	-495	-707	-927	-1155
25	49	2401	2401	2397	2385	2365	2337	2301	2257	2205	2145	2077	2001	1917	1825	1725	1617	1501	1377	1245	1105	957	801	637	465	285	97	-99	-303	-515	-735	-963
26	51	2601	2601	2597	2585	2565	2537	2501	2457	2405	2345	2277	2201	2117	2025	1925	1817	1701	1577	1445	1305	1157	1001	837	665	485	297	101	-103	-315	-535	-763
27	53	2809	2809	2805	2793	2773	2745	2709	2665	2613	2553	2485	2409	2325	2233	2133	2025	1909	1785	1653	1513	1365	1209	1045	873	693	505	309	105	-107	-327	-555
28	55	3025	3025	3021	3009	2989	2961	2925	2881	2829	2769	2701	2625	2541	2449	2349	2241	2125	2001	1869	1729	1581	1425	1261	1089	909	721	525	321	-109	-111	-339
29	57	3249	3249	3245	3233	3213	3185	3149	3105	3053	2993	2925	2849	2765	2673	2573	2465	2349	2225	2093	1953	1805	1649	1485	1313	1133	945	749	545	333	-113	-115
30	59	3481	3481	3477	3465	3445	3417	3381	3337	3285	3225	3157	3081	2997	2905	2805	2697	2581	2457	2325	2185	2037	1881	1717	1545	1365	1177	981	777	565	345	-117

Figure 25. C004001 Vertical Odd Squares Minus Horizontal Even Squares: Comprehensive Mapping. <https://1drv.ms/i/s!Arslv070x3WjkcgOegAfn9BNHy3Q9w?e=Y2u0mm>

For $n \geq 1$ and $k \geq 0$:

$$C004001 \text{ Horizontals} = -(2k)^2 + (2n - 1)^2 = -(even\ square) + odd\ square$$

$$C004001 \text{ Verticals} = 4(n^2 - n) - ((2k)^2 - 1) = 4(oblong) - odd\ square\ minus\ 1$$

For example, for $n = 6$ and $k = 3$, the compound is 85. Similarly, in the table C004002 Vertical Even Squares Minus Horizontal Odd Squares: Comprehensive Mapping.

C004002 Vertical Even Squares Minus Horizontal Odd Squares: Comprehensive Mapping																																
(EVEN Sq.) -(ODD Sq.)	n	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	
k	2k	square	1	3	5	7	9	11	13	15	17	19	21	23	25	27	29	31	33	35	37	39	41	43	45	47	49	51	53	55	57	59
0	0	0	-1	-9	-25	-49	-81	-121	-169	-225	-289	-361	-441	-529	-625	-729	-841	-961	-1089	-1225	-1369	-1521	-1681	-1849	-2025	-2209	-2401	-2601	-2809	-3025	-3249	-3481
1	2	4	3	-5	-21	-45	-77	-117	-165	-221	-285	-357	-437	-525	-621	-725	-837	-957	-1085	-1221	-1365	-1517	-1677	-1845	-2021	-2205	-2397	-2597	-2805	-3021	-3245	-3477
2	4	16	15	7	-9	-33	-65	-105	-153	-209	-273	-345	-425	-513	-609	-713	-825	-945	-1073	-1209	-1353	-1505	-1665	-1833	-2009	-2193	-2385	-2585	-2793	-3009	-3233	-3465
3	6	36	35	27	11	-13	-45	-85	-133	-189	-253	-325	-405	-493	-589	-693	-805	-925	-1053	-1189	-1333	-1485	-1645	-1813	-1989	-2173	-2365	-2565	-2773	-2989	-3213	-3445
4	8	64	63	55	39	15	-17	-57	-105	-161	-225	-297	-377	-465	-561	-665	-777	-897	-1025	-1161	-1305	-1457	-1617	-1785	-1961	-2145	-2337	-2537	-2745	-2961	-3185	-3415
5	10	100	99	91	75	51	19	-21	-69	-125	-189	-261	-341	-429	-525	-629	-741	-861	-989	-1125	-1269	-1421	-1581	-1749	-1925	-2109	-2301	-2501	-2709	-2925	-3149	-3381
6	12	144	143	135	119	95	63	23	-25	-81	-145	-217	-297	-385	-481	-585	-697	-817	-945	-1081	-1225	-1377	-1537	-1705	-1881	-2065	-2257	-2457	-2665	-2881	-3105	-3337
7	14	196	195	187	171	147	115	75	27	-29	-93	-165	-245	-333	-429	-533	-645	-765	-893	-1029	-1173	-1325	-1485	-1653	-1829	-2013	-2205	-2405	-2613	-2829	-3053	-3285
8	16	256	255	247	231	207	175	135	87	31	-33	-105	-185	-273	-369	-473	-585	-705	-833	-969	-1113	-1265	-1425	-1593	-1769	-1953	-2145	-2345	-2553	-2769	-2993	-3225
9	18																															

Figure 26. C004002 Vertical Even Squares Minus Horizontal Odd Squares: Comprehensive Mapping. <https://1drv.ms/i/s!Arslv070x3WjkcgNBNV5xgF-Jfgxsg?e=Kbm1OG>

For $n \geq 1$ and $k \geq 0$:

$$C004002 \text{ Horizontals} = -4(n^2 - n) + ((2k)^2 - 1) = -4(\text{oblong}) + \text{odd square minus 1}$$

$$C004002 \text{ Verticals} = (2k)^2 - (2n - 1)^2 = \text{even square} - \text{odd square}$$

For example, for $n = 3$ and $k = 6$, the compound is 119.

10.1 Analysis of Odd Number Generation through Differences of Squares

In our examination of the generation of odd integers through the differences between squares, the tables C004001 and C004002 reveal distinct patterns in their numerical outputs:

Table C004001 is structured to analyze the differences between odd squares and even squares. For $n > k$, it generates positive odd integers in the form of $1 \pmod{4}$, which are represented by the sequence <https://oeis.org/A016813>. These integers are derived from the difference where the odd square is greater than the even square. The corresponding sequence of positive primal numbers, known as Pythagorean primes, is catalogued at <https://oeis.org/A002144>. Conversely, for $n \leq k$, the table generates negative odd integers in the form of $-1 \pmod{4}$, listed under <https://oeis.org/A004767>. These are formed when the odd square is less than the even square, with the associated sequence of negative primal numbers available at <https://oeis.org/A002145>.

Table C004002 focuses on the differences between even squares and odd squares. For $k \geq n$, it produces positive odd integers in the form of $-1 \pmod{4}$, documented by <https://oeis.org/A004767>. These integers arise when the even square exceeds the odd square. The sequence for positive primal numbers in this configuration is found at <https://oeis.org/A002145>. For $k < n$, the table results in negative odd integers in the form of $1 \pmod{4}$, corresponding to the sequence <https://oeis.org/A016813>. These integers are generated when the even square is less than the odd square, and the relevant sequence of negative Pythagorean primals is catalogued at <https://oeis.org/A002144>.

These tables not only systematically generate all positive odd numbers but also illustrate a coherent mathematical structure when examining the negative values they produce. The sequences inversely correspond between the two tables, highlighting a consistent and symmetrical structure across our data sets.

It is important to note that both tables consist of a 30x30 element matrix. For the analysis of odd primal numbers, we can explore the behavior of these numbers within the range of -113 to +113. However, for the odd compound numbers that lie outside the diagonals reserved for primal numbers, the range of analysis is extended to between -339 and +339.

10.2 Mapping Twin Primes and the Differences of Odd and Even Squares

In the analysis of the distribution of twin primes within matrices C004001 and C004002, a notable characteristic regarding their arrangement is observed. These prime numbers, defined as

pairs of primes that differ by two units, manifest adjacently, both vertically and horizontally, within these structured matrices.

In the C004001 matrix, when observed horizontally, or in the C004002 matrix, when viewed vertically, twin primes emerge from subtracting the same odd square number by two consecutive even square numbers. This phenomenon is echoed in the sequence identified by <https://oeis.org/A122565>, which consists of prime numbers derived from the difference between a single odd square number and two consecutive even square numbers. This sequence highlights a unique property where the calculation of prime numbers is based on a specific interaction between odd and even square numbers within a defined mathematical operation.

Conversely, in the C004002 matrix, when examined horizontally, or in the C004001 matrix, from a vertical perspective, it is identified that twin primes result from the difference between two consecutive odd square numbers and a single even square number. Complementarily, the sequence represented by <https://oeis.org/A122564> comprises prime numbers generated through the subtraction of a single even square number from two consecutive odd square numbers. This sequence elucidates a distinct mathematical phenomenon where prime numbers emerge from the differential of sequential odd square numbers and a singular even square number.

It's imperative to clarify that the value of the differences must always be considered in absolute terms because one difference will invariably be positive and the other negative. Given that prime numbers are not currently regarded as negative, this distinction is crucial. Therefore, in our analytical approach and particularly when discussing the interactions between odd and even square numbers leading to the identification of prime numbers, the absolute value of the differences plays a pivotal role. This consideration ensures that our analysis remains aligned with the conventional understanding and classification of prime numbers as positive integers.

In addition to the insightful exploration of twin primes within the context of the C004001 and C004002 matrices, it's pertinent to acknowledge the existence of other prime configurations, such as cousin primes, sexy primes, and those that form the basis of the Goldbach Conjecture. These configurations, characterized by their unique differences and relational properties among prime numbers, offer further avenues for mathematical investigation. It is worth noting that these prime groupings, each with their distinct separations and patterns, will be the subject of a forthcoming study.

10.3 Conjecture on Prime Number Classification through Continued Fraction Expansions

Within the framework of this study, we have explored how differences between squares contribute to the formation of distinct sequences of odd integers. These sequences further segregate into odd primes fitting the forms of $4n + 1$ and $4n - 1$. Building on the effectiveness of Continued Fraction Expansions in identifying prime sequences between square and subsequent oblong numbers, as evidenced by our previous collaborations (see <https://oeis.org/A307508> and <https://oeis.org/A334163>), I propose the following conjecture:

“I conjecture that Continued Fraction Expansions can distinctly identify and separate odd primes between the two forms $4n+1$ and $4n-1$. This conjecture is based on the hypothesis that the mathematical properties inherent in Continued Fraction Expansions could reveal structural

distinctions between these two prime classifications, thereby offering a novel methodological approach to understanding their distribution within the number system.”

This conjecture is particularly inspired by observations from earlier research where geometric and algebraic methods provided insights into the classification of primes between squares and oblongs. In this study, we aim to extend these insights to systematically categorize primes of $4n + 1$ and $4n - 1$ forms, enhancing our understanding of their inherent properties and distributions.

11 Mapping the Coverage: Square Differences Within the Zones

In our quest to map numerical patterns, we have unearthed a phenomenon through Tables C004001 and C004002. These tables reveal sequences where the differences between initial squares progressively decrease as we move across each row from left to right. This systematic reduction uncovers a characteristic fundamental to further analytical exploration.

To delve deeper into this characteristic and its implications within the established zones, we propose the creation of eight additional sets of tables. Each set will be developed by calculating the differences between the elements from C004001 and C004002 and specific starting points: 0212-Oblongs, 0620-Oblongs, and the squares of both odd and even integers.

This methodical approach to table construction ensures that each horizontal sequence invariably starts with positive integers, with values transitioning to negative as one advances horizontally across the table. This reflects a systematic decrease, moving incrementally away from the zone's starting point.

For each distinct zone category—including 0212-Oblongs, 0620-Oblongs, and squares from both odd and even integers—we will undertake a horizontal assessment of positive terms. This procedure is designed to uncover the minimum quantity of compound numbers that are consistently generated by a square within its designated zone. Simultaneously, a vertical analysis of negative terms will delineate the quadratic curve. This curve outlines the minimum volume of compound elements produced within each zone.

This chapter warrants further in-depth study as it focuses on and demonstrates the quadratic distribution of integers. The motivation for advancing this data is the surprising appearance of the recent sequence <https://oeis.org/A371355> in Table C001767 upon inspection. Other sequences emerge as expected, but to avoid overburdening the presentation with figures, we have chosen to merely provide the links to them.

11.1 C001759 C001760 Mapping the Coverage: (Odd Sq. – Even Sq.) and (Even Sq. – Odd Sq.) Differences Relative to Start Point in 0212-Oblong Zones

https://1drv.ms/i/s!Arslv070x3WjkccEY_NlnvesXDnTXg?e=Vze06N

C001767 0212-Oblong Zone Analysis: Maximum Number of Primals:

<https://1drv.ms/i/s!Arslv070x3WjkccFk1FoWX-qJoGF8Q?e=MfUxDh>

11.2 C001761 C001762 Mapping the Coverage: (Odd Sq. – Even Sq.) (Even Sq. – Odd Sq.) Differences Relative to Start Point in 0620-Oblong Zones

<https://1drv.ms/i/s!Arslv070x3WjkccGcxNL5WNyhK9qqw?e=8tWQ2v>

C001768 0620-Oblong Zone Analysis: Maximum Number of Primals:

<https://1drv.ms/i/s!Arslv070x3WjkccHOxgKgFCDRIdyiA?e=wPc3dm>

11.3 C001763 C001764 Mapping the Coverage: (Odd Sq. – Even Sq.) (Even Sq. – Odd Sq.) Differences Relative to Start Point in Odd Square Zones

<https://1drv.ms/i/s!Arslv070x3WjkccIahUPdMT6rSRQUA?e=eaWdhZ>

C001769 Odd Square Zone Analysis: Maximum Number of Primals:

https://1drv.ms/i/s!Arslv070x3WjkccJKkHbbjP8qQn_ZA?e=ol1Fqw

11.4 C001765 C001766 Mapping the Coverage: (Odd Sq. – Even Sq.) (Even Sq. – Odd Sq.) Differences Relative to Start Point in Even Square Zones

<https://1drv.ms/i/s!Arslv070x3WjkccKziUSeOF8y5pYyg?e=Lb60xm>

C001770 Even Square Zone Analysis: Maximum Number of Primals:

<https://1drv.ms/i/s!Arslv070x3WjkccL6B0I1AI847gR6A?e=8V6NdM>

12 The Polynomial Distribution of Odd Compound Numbers Relative to Start Point in all Zones

To achieve our goal of polynomially mapping 100% of odd compound numbers, we will consider only those compounds that yield positive differences in each of the tables, C004001 Vertical Odd Squares Minus Horizontal Even Squares and C004002 Vertical Even Squares Minus Horizontal Odd Squares. Furthermore, we will disregard the central descending 45-degree diagonal that contains positive primal numbers highlighted with bold black borders.

Specifically, for Table C004001, we only consider the first $(n - 1)$ terms for each horizontal row $n \geq 1$. Similarly, in Table C004002, the selection is limited to the first $(k - 1)$ terms for each horizontal row $k \geq 0$.

By excluding this central diagonal to avoid using primal numbers, we consequently ignore all compounds along the diagonal as well. However, this exclusion does not affect our reasoning because every odd compound possesses at least two pairs of complementary divisors. As observed in the TMT (Triangular Multiplication Table), there is always another pair of complementary divisors denoting the compound number. In our tables, C004001 and C004002, these pairs of complementary divisors now appear as differences of squares. In other words, every compound has at least two square differences that result in the compound, with only one

appearing on the central diagonal. All repeated positive compounds are located below this central diagonal. Effectively, ignoring the central diagonals in tables C004001 and C004002, which contain both positive and negative primal numbers, is analogous to disregarding the line of multiples of 1 in the FMT (Full Multiplication Table).

With the two tables, C004001 and C004002, we have defined all positive odd compounds expressed as all the possible differences between two squares.

12.1 C004011 Table of Count of Odd Numbers Between Odd Compounds from C004001 Relative to Start Point in 0212-Oblong Zones

We now focus on how each $C004001 = (odd)^2 - (even)^2$ approaches or distances itself from the start point of the 0212-Oblong zone it belongs to. For example, $(odd)^2 - (0)^2$ occupies the positions $3n - 2$ starting from the initial 0212-Oblong points. We apply the same reasoning to $(odd)^2 - (1)^2$ and finally to $(odd)^2 - (2)^2$. This approach allows us to generate the three minimum elements necessary to create each horizontal quadratic sequence for all infinite horizontal lines. This procedure results in a notable table, the C004011 Table of Count of Odd Numbers Between Odd Compounds from C004001 Relative to Start Point in 0212-Oblong Zones, which excludes multiples of 3.

Odd Numbers	Start Point: 0212-Oblong gs (Odd)	End Point: Next 0212-Oblong gs	Number of Odd Numbers Between	C004011 Table of Count of Odd Numbers Between Odd Compounds from C004001 Relative to Start Point in 0212-Oblong Zones																																	
				(ODD Sq.) - (EVEN Sq.)	k	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29		
1	5	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1		
1	12	12	5	2	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4		
5	30	56	13	4	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	
7	56	90	17	5	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	
9	90	132	21	6	16	16	16	16	16	16	16	16	16	16	16	16	16	16	16	16	16	16	16	16	16	16	16	16	16	16	16	16	16	16	16	16	
11	132	182	25	7	19	19	19	19	19	19	19	19	19	19	19	19	19	19	19	19	19	19	19	19	19	19	19	19	19	19	19	19	19	19	19	19	
13	182	240	29	8	22	22	22	22	22	22	22	22	22	22	22	22	22	22	22	22	22	22	22	22	22	22	22	22	22	22	22	22	22	22	22	22	
15	240	306	33	9	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	
17	306	380	37	10	28	28	28	28	28	28	28	28	28	28	28	28	28	28	28	28	28	28	28	28	28	28	28	28	28	28	28	28	28	28	28	28	
19	380	462	41	11	31	31	31	31	31	31	31	31	31	31	31	31	31	31	31	31	31	31	31	31	31	31	31	31	31	31	31	31	31	31	31	31	
21	462	552	45	12	34	34	34	34	34	34	34	34	34	34	34	34	34	34	34	34	34	34	34	34	34	34	34	34	34	34	34	34	34	34	34	34	
23	552	650	49	13	37	37	37	37	37	37	37	37	37	37	37	37	37	37	37	37	37	37	37	37	37	37	37	37	37	37	37	37	37	37	37	37	
25	650	756	53	14	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	
27	756	870	57	15	43	43	43	43	43	43	43	43	43	43	43	43	43	43	43	43	43	43	43	43	43	43	43	43	43	43	43	43	43	43	43	43	43
29	870	992	61	16	46	46	46	46	46	46	46	46	46	46	46	46	46	46	46	46	46	46	46	46	46	46	46	46	46	46	46	46	46	46	46	46	
31	992	1122	65	17	49	49	49	49	49	49	49	49	49	49	49	49	49	49	49	49	49	49	49	49	49	49	49	49	49	49	49	49	49	49	49	49	
33	1122	1260	69	18	52	52	52	52	52	52	52	52	52	52	52	52	52	52	52	52	52	52	52	52	52	52	52	52	52	52	52	52	52	52	52	52	
35	1260	1406	73	19	55	55	55	55	55	55	55	55	55	55	55	55	55	55	55	55	55	55	55	55	55	55	55	55	55	55	55	55	55	55	55	55	
37	1406	1560	77	20	58	58	58	58	58	58	58	58	58	58	58	58	58	58	58	58	58	58	58	58	58	58	58	58	58	58	58	58	58	58	58	58	
39	1560	1722	81	21	61	61	61	61	61	61	61	61	61	61	61	61	61	61	61	61	61	61	61	61	61	61	61	61	61	61	61	61	61	61	61	61	
41	1722	1892	85	22	64	64	64	64	64	64	64	64	64	64	64	64	64	64	64	64	64	64	64	64	64	64	64	64	64	64	64	64	64	64	64	64	
43	1892	2070	89	23	67	67	67	67	67	67	67	67	67	67	67	67	67	67	67	67	67	67	67	67	67	67	67	67	67	67	67	67	67	67	67	67	
45	2070	2256	93	24	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	
47	2256	2450	97	25	73	73	73	73	73	73	73	73	73	73	73	73	73	73	73	73	73	73	73	73	73	73	73	73	73	73	73	73	73	73	73	73	
49	2450	2652	101	26	76	76	76	76	76	76	76	76	76	76	76	76	76	76	76	76	76	76	76	76	76	76	76	76	76	76	76	76	76	76	76	76	
51	2652	2862	105	27	79	79	79	79	79	79	79	79	79	79	79	79	79	79	79	79	79	79	79	79	79	79	79	79	79	79	79	79	79	79	79	79	
53	2862	3080	109	28	82	82	82	82	82	82	82	82	82	82	82	82	82	82	82	82	82	82	82	82	82	82	82	82	82	82	82	82	82	82	82	82	
55	3080	3306	113	29	85	85	85	85	85	85	85	85	85	85	85	85	85	85	85	85	85	85	85	85	85	85	85	85	85	85	85	85	85	85	85	85	
57	3306	3540	117	30	88	88	88	88	88	88	88	88	88	88	88	88	88	88	88	88	88	88	88	88	88	88	88	88	88	88	88	88	88	88	88	88	

Figure 27. C004011 Table of Count of Odd Numbers Between Odd Compounds from C004001 Relative to Start Point in 0212-Oblong Zones. <https://1drv.ms/i/s!Arslv070x3WjkcgQ-xtGvBrLLfinA?e=H30jI0>

For $n \geq 1$ and $k \geq 0$:

$$C004011horizontals = (3n - 2) - 2k^2 = (X \text{ mod } 3 = 1) - (2 * \text{square})$$

$$C004011verticals = (3n) - 2(k^2 - 1) = (X \text{ mod } 3 = 0) - (2 * (\text{square} - 1))$$

The sequences of primal numbers $x = 2y^2 - 199$ and $x = 2y^2 - 181$ both with 55 consecutive primals, $x = 2y^2 - 61$ with 31 primals, $x = 2y^2 - 11$ with 21 primals, and $x = 2y^2 - 29$ with 57 primals stand out.

12.2 C004012 Table of Count of Odd Numbers Between Odd Compounds From C004002 Relative to Start Point in 0212-Oblong Zones

The same procedure is applied in $C004002 = (even)^2 - (odd)^2$ to obtain:

Odd Numbers	Start Point (0212-Oblong gs)	End Point (Next 0212-Oblong gs)	Number of Odd Numbers Between	C004012 Table of Count of Odd Numbers Between Odd Compounds from C004002 Relative to Start Point in 0212-Oblong Zones																																
				(EVEN Sq.)	(ODD Sq.)	n	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30
				n ² -n	0	2	6	12	20	30	42	56	72	90	110	132	156	182	210	240	272	306	342	380	420	462	506	552	600	650	702	756	812	870		
-1	0	2	1	0	0	0	-4	-12	-24	-40	-60	-84	-112	-144	-180	-220	-264	-312	-364	-420	-480	-544	-612	-684	-760	-840	-924	-1012	-1104	-1200	-1300	-1404	-1512	-1624	-1740	
1	2	12	5	1	1	1	-3	-11	-23	-39	-59	-83	-111	-143	-179	-219	-263	-311	-363	-419	-479	-543	-611	-683	-759	-839	-923	-1011	-1103	-1199	-1299	-1403	-1511	-1623	-1739	
3	12	30	9	2	2	2	-2	-10	-22	-38	-58	-82	-110	-142	-178	-218	-262	-310	-362	-418	-478	-542	-610	-682	-758	-838	-922	-1010	-1102	-1198	-1298	-1402	-1510	-1622	-1738	
5	30	56	13	3	3	3	-1	-9	-21	-37	-57	-81	-109	-141	-177	-217	-261	-309	-361	-417	-477	-541	-609	-681	-757	-837	-921	-1009	-1101	-1197	-1297	-1401	-1509	-1621	-1737	
7	56	90	17	4	4	4	0	-6	-18	-34	-54	-80	-110	-140	-176	-216	-260	-308	-360	-416	-476	-540	-608	-680	-756	-836	-920	-1008	-1100	-1196	-1296	-1400	-1508	-1620	-1736	
9	90	132	21	5	5	5	1	-7	-19	-35	-55	-81	-111	-143	-179	-219	-263	-311	-363	-419	-479	-543	-611	-683	-759	-839	-923	-1011	-1103	-1199	-1299	-1403	-1511	-1623	-1739	
11	132	182	25	6	6	6	2	-8	-20	-36	-56	-82	-112	-144	-180	-220	-264	-312	-364	-420	-480	-544	-612	-684	-760	-840	-924	-1012	-1104	-1200	-1300	-1404	-1512	-1624	-1740	
13	182	240	29	7	7	7	3	-5	-17	-33	-53	-77	-105	-137	-173	-213	-257	-305	-357	-413	-473	-537	-605	-677	-753	-833	-917	-1005	-1097	-1193	-1293	-1397	-1505	-1617	-1733	
15	240	306	33	8	8	8	4	-4	-16	-32	-52	-76	-104	-136	-172	-212	-256	-304	-356	-412	-472	-536	-604	-676	-752	-832	-916	-1004	-1096	-1192	-1292	-1396	-1504	-1616	-1732	
17	306	380	37	9	9	9	5	-3	-15	-31	-51	-75	-103	-135	-171	-211	-255	-303	-355	-411	-471	-535	-603	-675	-751	-831	-915	-1003	-1095	-1191	-1291	-1395	-1503	-1615	-1731	
19	380	462	41	10	10	10	6	-2	-14	-30	-50	-74	-102	-134	-170	-210	-254	-302	-354	-410	-470	-534	-602	-674	-750	-830	-914	-1002	-1094	-1190	-1290	-1394	-1502	-1614	-1730	
21	462	552	45	11	11	11	7	-1	-13	-29	-49	-73	-101	-133	-169	-209	-253	-301	-353	-409	-469	-533	-601	-673	-749	-829	-913	-1001	-1093	-1189	-1289	-1393	-1501	-1613	-1729	
23	552	650	49	12	12	12	8	0	-12	-28	-48	-72	-100	-132	-168	-208	-252	-300	-352	-408	-468	-532	-600	-672	-748	-828	-912	-1000	-1092	-1188	-1288	-1392	-1500	-1612	-1728	
25	650	756	53	13	13	13	9	1	-11	-27	-47	-71	-99	-131	-167	-207	-251	-299	-351	-407	-467	-531	-600	-671	-747	-827	-911	-999	-1091	-1187	-1287	-1391	-1499	-1611	-1727	
27	756	870	57	14	14	14	10	2	-10	-26	-46	-70	-98	-130	-166	-206	-250	-298	-350	-406	-466	-530	-598	-670	-746	-826	-910	-998	-1090	-1186	-1286	-1390	-1498	-1610	-1726	
29	870	992	61	15	15	15	11	3	-9	-25	-45	-69	-97	-129	-165	-205	-249	-297	-349	-405	-465	-529	-597	-669	-745	-825	-909	-997	-1089	-1185	-1285	-1389	-1497	-1609	-1725	
31	992	1122	65	16	16	16	12	4	-8	-24	-44	-68	-96	-128	-164	-204	-248	-296	-348	-404	-464	-528	-596	-668	-744	-824	-908	-996	-1088	-1184	-1284	-1388	-1496	-1608	-1724	
33	1122	1260	69	17	17	17	13	5	-7	-23	-43	-67	-95	-127	-163	-203	-247	-295	-347	-403	-463	-527	-595	-667	-743	-823	-907	-995	-1087	-1183	-1283	-1387	-1495	-1607	-1723	
35	1260	1406	73	18	18	18	14	6	-6	-22	-42	-66	-94	-126	-162	-202	-246	-294	-346	-402	-462	-526	-594	-666	-742	-822	-906	-994	-1086	-1182	-1282	-1386	-1494	-1606	-1722	
37	1406	1560	77	19	19	19	15	7	-5	-21	-41	-65	-93	-125	-161	-201	-245	-293	-345	-401	-461	-525	-593	-665	-741	-821	-905	-993	-1085	-1181	-1281	-1385	-1493	-1605	-1721	
39	1560	1722	81	20	20	20	16	8	-4	-20	-40	-64	-92	-124	-160	-200	-244	-292	-344	-400	-460	-524	-592	-664	-740	-820	-904	-992	-1084	-1180	-1280	-1384	-1492	-1604	-1720	
41	1722	1892	85	21	21	21	17	9	-3	-19	-39	-63	-91	-123	-159	-199	-243	-291	-343	-399	-459	-523	-591	-663	-739	-819	-903	-991	-1083	-1179	-1279	-1383	-1491	-1603	-1719	
43	1892	2070	89	22	22	22	18	10	-2	-18	-38	-62	-90	-122	-158	-198	-242	-290	-342	-398	-458	-522	-590	-662	-738	-818	-902	-990	-1082	-1178	-1278	-1382	-1490	-1602	-1718	
45	2070	2256	93	23	23	23	19	11	-1	-17	-37	-61	-89	-121	-157	-197	-241	-289	-341	-397	-457	-521	-589	-661	-737	-817	-901	-989	-1081	-1177	-1277	-1381	-1489	-1601	-1717	
47	2256	2450	97	24	24	24	20	12	0	-16	-36	-60	-88	-120	-156	-196	-240	-288	-340	-396	-456	-520	-588	-660	-736	-816	-900	-988	-1080	-1176	-1276	-1380	-1488	-1600	-1716	
49	2450	2652	101	25	25	25	21	13	1	-15	-35	-59	-87	-119	-155	-195	-239	-287	-339	-395	-455	-519	-587	-659	-735	-815	-900	-987	-1079	-1175	-1275	-1379	-1487	-1599	-1715	
51	2652	2862	105	26	26	26	22	14	2	-14	-34	-58	-86	-118	-154	-194	-238	-286	-338	-394	-454	-518	-586	-658	-734	-814	-900	-986	-1078	-1174	-1274	-1378	-1486	-1598	-1714	
53	2862	3080	109	27	27	27	23	15	3	-13	-33	-57	-85	-117	-153	-193	-237	-285	-337	-393	-453	-517	-585	-657	-733	-813	-897	-985	-1077	-1173	-1273	-1377	-1485	-1597	-1713	
55	3080	3306	113	28	28	28	24	16	4	-12	-32	-56	-84	-116	-152	-192	-236	-284	-336	-392	-452	-516	-584	-656	-732	-812	-896	-984	-1076	-1172	-1272	-1376	-1484	-1596	-1712	
57	3306	3540	117	29	29	29	25	17	5	-11	-31	-55	-83	-115	-151	-191	-235	-283	-335	-391	-451	-515	-583	-655	-731	-811	-895	-983	-1075	-1171	-1271	-1375	-1483	-1595	-1711	

Figure 28. C004012 Table of Count of Odd Numbers Between Odd Compounds From C004002 Relative to Start Point in 0212-Oblong Zones.

<https://1drv.ms/i/s!Arslv070x3Wjkcgr9CGbIzfQkynlVg?e=6yawkJ>

For $n \geq 1$ and $k \geq 0$:

$$C004012horizontal = k - 2(n^2 - n) = (integer) - 2 * (oblong)$$

$$C004012vertical = -2(n^2 - n) + k = -2 * (oblong) + (integer)$$

The sequences of primal numbers $x = 2y^2 - 2y + 19$ with 36 consecutive primals, $x = 2y^2 - 2y - 41$ with 26 consecutive primals, $x = 2y^2 - 2y - 71$ with 32 primals, $x = 2y^2 - 2y - 83$ with 34 primals, and $x = 2y^2 - 2y - 113$ with 44 primals stand out.

12.3 C004013 Table of Count of Odd Numbers Between Odd Compounds From C004001 Relative to Start Point in 0620-Oblong Zones

Using 0620-Oblong Zone start points for C004001 table elements:

even	Start Point even + (even + 1)	End Point (even + 2) + (even + 3)	# odds between oblongs	C004014 Table of Count of Odd Numbers Between Odd Compounds from C004002 Relative to Start Point in 0620-Oblong Zones																															
				(EVEN Sq.) - (ODD Sq.)	n	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30
-2	2	0	3	0	-1	-1	-5	-13	-25	-41	-61	-85	-113	-145	-181	-221	-265	-313	-365	-421	-481	-545	-613	-685	-761	-841	-925	-1013	-1105	-1201	-1301	-1405	-1513	-1625	-1741
0	0	6	7	1	2	2	-2	-10	-22	-38	-58	-82	-110	-142	-178	-218	-262	-310	-362	-418	-478	-542	-610	-682	-758	-838	-922	-1010	-1102	-1198	-1298	-1402	-1510	-1622	-1738
2	6	20	11	2	5	5	-1	-7	-19	-35	-55	-79	-107	-139	-175	-215	-259	-307	-359	-415	-475	-539	-607	-679	-755	-835	-919	-1007	-1099	-1195	-1295	-1399	-1507	-1619	-1735
4	20	42	15	3	8	8	4	-4	-16	-32	-52	-76	-104	-136	-172	-212	-256	-304	-356	-412	-472	-536	-604	-676	-752	-832	-916	-1004	-1096	-1192	-1292	-1396	-1504	-1616	-1732
6	42	72	19	4	11	11	7	-1	-13	-29	-49	-73	-101	-133	-169	-209	-253	-301	-353	-409	-469	-533	-601	-673	-749	-829	-913	-1001	-1093	-1189	-1289	-1393	-1501	-1613	-1729
8	72	110	23	5	14	14	10	2	-10	-26	-46	-70	-98	-130	-166	-206	-250	-298	-350	-406	-466	-530	-598	-670	-746	-826	-910	-998	-1090	-1186	-1286	-1390	-1498	-1610	-1726
10	110	166	27	6	17	17	13	5	-7	-23	-43	-67	-95	-127	-163	-203	-247	-295	-347	-403	-463	-527	-595	-667	-743	-823	-907	-995	-1087	-1183	-1283	-1387	-1495	-1607	-1723
12	156	210	31	7	20	20	16	8	-4	-20	-40	-64	-92	-124	-160	-200	-244	-292	-344	-400	-460	-524	-592	-664	-740	-820	-904	-992	-1084	-1180	-1280	-1384	-1492	-1604	-1720
14	210	272	35	8	23	23	19	11	3	-17	-37	-61	-89	-121	-157	-197	-241	-289	-341	-397	-457	-521	-589	-661	-737	-817	-901	-989	-1081	-1177	-1277	-1381	-1489	-1601	-1717
16	272	342	39	9	26	26	22	14	2	-14	-34	-58	-86	-118	-154	-194	-238	-286	-338	-394	-454	-518	-586	-658	-734	-814	-898	-986	-1078	-1174	-1274	-1378	-1486	-1598	-1714
18	342	420	43	10	29	29	25	17	5	-11	-31	-55	-83	-115	-151	-191	-235	-283	-335	-391	-451	-515	-583	-655	-731	-811	-895	-983	-1075	-1171	-1271	-1375	-1483	-1595	-1711
20	420	506	47	11	32	32	28	20	8	-6	-28	-52	-80	-112	-148	-188	-232	-280	-332	-388	-448	-512	-580	-652	-728	-808	-892	-980	-1072	-1168	-1268	-1372	-1480	-1592	-1708
22	506	600	51	12	35	35	31	23	11	-5	-25	-49	-77	-109	-145	-185	-229	-277	-329	-385	-445	-509	-577	-649	-725	-805	-889	-977	-1069	-1165	-1265	-1369	-1477	-1589	-1705
24	600	702	55	13	38	38	34	26	14	-2	-22	-46	-74	-106	-142	-182	-226	-274	-326	-382	-442	-506	-574	-646	-722	-802	-886	-974	-1066	-1162	-1262	-1366	-1474	-1586	-1702
26	702	812	59	14	41	41	37	29	17	-4	-19	-43	-71	-103	-139	-179	-223	-271	-323	-379	-439	-503	-571	-643	-719	-799	-883	-971	-1063	-1159	-1259	-1363	-1471	-1583	-1699
28	812	930	63	15	44	44	40	32	20	4	-16	-40	-68	-100	-136	-176	-220	-268	-320	-376	-436	-500	-568	-640	-716	-796	-880	-968	-1060	-1156	-1256	-1360	-1468	-1580	-1696
30	930	1056	67	16	47	47	43	35	23	7	-13	-37	-65	-97	-133	-173	-217	-265	-317	-373	-433	-497	-565	-637	-713	-793	-877	-965	-1057	-1153	-1253	-1357	-1465	-1577	-1693
32	1056	1190	71	17	50	50	46	38	26	10	-10	-34	-62	-94	-130	-170	-214	-262	-314	-370	-430	-494	-562	-634	-710	-790	-874	-962	-1054	-1150	-1250	-1354	-1462	-1574	-1690
34	1190	1332	75	18	53	53	49	41	29	13	-7	-31	-59	-91	-127	-167	-211	-259	-311	-367	-427	-491	-559	-631	-707	-787	-871	-959	-1051	-1147	-1247	-1351	-1459	-1571	-1687
36	1332	1482	79	19	56	56	52	44	32	16	-4	-28	-56	-88	-124	-164	-208	-256	-308	-364	-424	-488	-556	-628	-704	-784	-868	-956	-1048	-1144	-1244	-1348	-1456	-1568	-1684
38	1482	1640	83	20	59	59	55	47	35	19	-1	-25	-53	-85	-121	-161	-205	-253	-305	-361	-421	-485	-553	-625	-701	-781	-865	-953	-1045	-1141	-1241	-1345	-1453	-1565	-1681
40	1640	1806	87	21	62	62	58	50	38	22	2	-22	-50	-82	-118	-158	-202	-250	-302	-358	-418	-482	-550	-622	-698	-778	-862	-950	-1042	-1138	-1238	-1342	-1450	-1562	-1678
42	1806	1980	91	22	65	65	61	53	41	25	6	-19	-47	-79	-115	-155	-199	-247	-299	-355	-415	-479	-547	-619	-695	-775	-859	-947	-1039	-1135	-1235	-1339	-1447	-1559	-1675
44	1980	2162	95	23	68	68	64	56	44	28	8	-16	-44	-76	-112	-152	-196	-244	-296	-352	-412	-476	-544	-616	-692	-772	-856	-944	-1036	-1132	-1232	-1336	-1444	-1556	-1672
46	2162	2352	99	24	71	71	67	59	47	31	11	-13	-41	-73	-109	-149	-193	-241	-293	-349	-409	-473	-541	-613	-689	-769	-853	-941	-1033	-1129	-1229	-1333	-1441	-1553	-1669
48	2352	2550	103	25	74	74	70	62	50	34	14	-10	-38	-70	-106	-146	-190	-238	-290	-346	-406	-470	-538	-610	-686	-766	-850	-938	-1030	-1126	-1226	-1330	-1438	-1550	-1666
50	2550	2756	107	26	77	77	73	65	53	37	17	-7	-35	-67	-103	-143	-187	-235	-287	-343	-403	-467	-535	-607	-683	-763	-847	-935	-1027	-1123	-1223	-1327	-1435	-1547	-1663
52	2756	2970	111	27	80	80	76	68	56	40	20	-4	-32	-64	-100	-140	-184	-232	-284	-340	-400	-464	-532	-604	-680	-760	-844	-932	-1024	-1120	-1220	-1324	-1432	-1544	-1660
54	2970	3192	115	28	83	83	79	71	59	43	23	-1	-29	-61	-97	-137	-181	-229	-281	-337	-397	-461	-529	-601	-677	-757	-841	-929	-1021	-1117	-1217	-1321	-1429	-1541	-1657
56	3192	3422	119	29	86	86	82	74	62	46	26	2	-26	-58	-94	-134	-178	-226	-278	-334	-394	-458	-526	-598	-674	-754	-838	-926	-1018	-1114	-1214	-1318	-1426	-1538	-1654

Figure 30. C004014 Table of Count of Odd Numbers Between Odd Compounds from C004002 Relative to Start Point in 0620-Oblong Zones.

https://1drv.ms/i/s!Arslv070x3WjkcgTMpk22N0X_pyl_g?e=S0iTvD

For $n \geq 1$ and $k \geq 0$:

$$C004014_{horizontal} = -2(n^2 - n) + (3k - 1) = -(2 * oblong) + (X \text{ mod } 3 = 2)$$

$$C004014_{vertical} = (3k) - (2(n^2 - n) + 1) = (X \text{ mod } 3 = 2) - (2 * oblong)$$

The positive numbers are not divisible by 3.

The sequences of primal numbers $x = 2y^2 - 2y - 41$ with 26 consecutive primals, $x = 2y^2 - 2y - 71$ with 32 primals, $x = 2y^2 - 2y - 83$ with 34 primals, and $x = 2y^2 - 2y - 113$ with 44 primals stand out.

12.5 C004015 Table of Count of Odd Numbers Between Odd Compounds from C004001 Relative to Start Point in Odd Square Zones

Using Odd Square Zone start points for C004001 table elements:

Odd	Start Point odd ²	End Point (odd+2) ²	# odds betw even odds square	C004015 Table of Count of Odd Numbers Between Odd Compounds from C004001 Relative to Start Point in Odd Square Zones																															
				(ODD Sq.) - (EVEN Sq.)	k	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29
1	1	9	4	1	0	0	-2	-8	-18	-32	-50	-72	-98	-128	-162	-200	-242	-288	-338	-392	-450	-512	-578	-648	-722	-800	-882	-968	-1058	-1152	-1250	-1352	-1458	-1568	-1682
3	9	25	8	2	0	0	-2	-8	-18	-32	-50	-72	-98	-128	-162	-200	-242	-288	-338	-392	-450	-512	-578	-648	-722	-800	-882	-968	-1058	-1152	-1250	-1352	-1458	-1568	-1682
5	25	49	12	3	0	0	-2	-8	-18	-32	-50	-72	-98	-128	-162	-200	-242	-288	-338	-392	-450	-512	-578	-648	-722	-800	-882	-968	-1058	-1152	-1250	-1352	-1458	-1568	-1682
7	49	81	16	4	0	0	-2	-8	-18	-32	-50	-72	-98	-128	-162	-200	-242	-288	-338	-392	-450	-512	-578	-648	-722	-800	-882	-968	-1058	-1152	-1250	-1352	-1458	-1568	-1682
9	81	121	20	5	0	0	-2	-8	-18	-32	-50	-72	-98	-128	-162	-200	-242	-288	-338	-392	-450	-512	-578	-648	-722	-800	-882	-968	-1058	-1152	-1250	-1352	-1458	-1568	-1682
11	121	169	24	6	0	0	-2	-8	-18	-32	-50	-72	-98	-128	-162	-200	-242	-288	-338	-392	-450	-512	-578	-648	-722	-800	-882	-968	-1058	-1152	-1250	-1352	-1458	-1568	-1682
13	169	225	28	7	0	0	-2	-8	-18	-32	-50	-72	-98	-128	-162	-200	-242	-288	-338	-392	-450	-512	-578	-648	-722	-800	-882	-968	-1058	-1152	-1250	-1352	-1458	-1568	-1682
15	225	289	32	8	0	0	-2	-8	-18	-32	-50	-72	-98	-128	-162	-200	-242	-288	-338	-392	-450	-512	-578	-648	-722	-800	-882	-968	-1058	-1152	-1250	-1352	-1458	-1568	-1682
17	289	361	36	9	0	0	-2	-8	-18	-32	-50	-72	-98	-128	-162	-200	-242	-288	-338	-392	-450	-512	-578	-648	-722	-800	-882	-968	-1058	-1152	-1250	-1352	-1458	-1568	-1682
19	361	441	40	10	0	0	-2	-8	-18	-32	-50	-72	-98	-128	-162	-200	-242	-288	-338	-392	-450	-512	-578	-648	-722	-800	-882	-968	-1058	-1152	-1250	-1352	-1458	-1568	-1682
21	441	529	44	11	0	0	-2	-8	-18	-32	-50	-72	-98	-128	-162	-200	-242	-288	-338	-392	-450	-512	-578	-648	-722	-800	-882	-968	-1058	-1152	-1250	-1352	-1458	-1568	-1682
23	529	625	48	12	0	0	-2	-8	-18	-32	-50	-72	-98	-128	-162	-200	-242	-288	-338	-392	-450	-512	-578	-648	-722	-800	-882	-968	-1058	-1152	-1250	-1352	-1458	-1568	-1682
25	625	729	52	13	0	0	-2	-8	-18	-32	-50	-72	-98	-128	-162	-200	-242	-288	-338	-392	-450	-512	-578	-648	-722	-800	-882	-968	-1058	-1152	-1250	-1352	-1458	-1568	-1682
27	729	841	56	14	0	0	-2	-8	-18	-32	-50	-72	-98	-128	-162	-200	-242	-288	-338	-392	-450	-512	-578	-648	-722	-800	-882	-968	-1058	-1152	-1250	-1352	-1458	-1568	-1682
29	841	961	60	15	0	0	-2	-8	-18	-32	-50	-72	-98	-128	-162	-200	-242	-288	-338	-392	-450	-512	-578	-648	-722	-800	-882	-968	-1058	-1152	-1250	-1352	-1458	-1568	-1682
31	961	1089	64	16	0	0	-2	-8	-18	-32	-50	-72	-98	-128	-162	-200	-242	-288	-338	-392	-450	-512	-578	-648	-722	-800	-882	-968	-1058	-1152	-1250	-1352	-1458	-1568	-1682
33	1089	1225	68	17	0	0	-2	-8	-18	-32	-50	-72	-98	-128	-162	-200	-242	-288	-338	-392	-450	-512	-578	-648	-722	-800	-882	-968	-1058	-1152	-1250	-1352	-1458	-1568	-1682
35	1225	1369	72	18	0	0	-2	-8	-18	-32	-50	-72	-98	-128	-162	-200	-242	-288	-338	-392	-450	-512	-578	-648	-722	-800	-882	-968	-1058	-1152	-1250	-1352	-1458	-1568	-1682
37	1369	1521	76	19	0	0	-2	-8	-18	-32	-50	-72	-98	-128	-162	-200	-242	-288	-338	-392	-450	-512	-578	-648	-722	-800	-882	-968	-1058	-1152	-1250	-1352	-1458	-1568	-1682
39	1521	1681	80	20	0	0	-2	-8	-18	-32	-50	-72	-98	-128	-162	-200	-242	-288	-338	-392	-450	-512	-578	-648	-722	-800	-882	-968	-1058	-1152	-1250	-1352	-1458	-1568	-1682
41	1681	1849	84	21	0	0	-2	-8	-18	-32	-50	-72	-98	-128	-162	-200	-242	-288	-338	-392	-450	-512	-578	-648	-722	-800	-882	-968	-1058	-1152	-1250	-1352	-1458	-1568	-1682
43	1849	2025	88	22	0	0	-2	-8	-18	-32	-50	-72	-98	-128	-162	-200	-242	-288	-338	-392	-450	-512	-578	-648	-722	-800	-882	-968	-1058	-1152	-1250	-1352	-1458	-1568	-1682
45	2025	2209	92	23	0	0	-2	-8	-18	-32	-50	-72	-98	-128	-162	-200	-242	-288	-338	-392	-450	-512	-578	-648	-722	-800	-882	-968	-1058	-1152	-1250	-1352	-1458	-1568	-1682
47	2209	2401	96	24	0	0	-2	-8	-18	-32	-50	-72	-98	-128	-162	-200	-242	-288	-338	-392	-450	-512	-578	-648	-722	-800	-882	-968	-1058	-1152	-1250	-1352	-1458	-1568	-1682
49	2401	2601	100	25	0	0	-2	-8	-18	-32	-50	-72	-98	-128	-162	-200	-242	-288	-338	-392	-450	-512	-578	-648	-722	-800	-882	-968	-1058	-1152	-1250	-1352	-1458	-1568	-1682
51	2601	2809	104	26	0	0	-2	-8	-18	-32	-50	-72	-98	-128	-162	-200	-242	-288	-338	-392	-450	-512	-578	-648	-722	-800	-882	-968	-1058	-1152	-1250	-1352	-1458	-1568	-1682
53	2809	3025	108	27	0	0	-2	-8	-18	-32	-50	-72	-98	-128	-162	-200	-242	-288	-338	-392	-450	-512	-578	-648	-722	-800	-882	-968	-1058	-1152	-1250	-1352	-1458	-1568	-1682
55	3025	3249	112	28	0	0	-2	-8	-18	-32	-50	-72	-98	-128	-162	-200	-242	-288	-338	-392	-450	-512	-578	-648	-722	-800	-882	-968	-1058	-1152	-1250	-1352	-1458	-1568	-1682
57	3249	3481	116	29	0	0	-2	-8	-18	-32	-50	-72	-98	-128	-162	-200	-242	-288	-338	-392	-450	-512	-578	-648	-722	-800	-882	-968	-1058	-1152	-1250	-1352	-1458	-1568	-1682
59	3481	3721	120	30	0	0	-2	-8	-18	-32	-50	-72	-98	-128	-162	-200	-242	-288	-338	-392	-450	-512	-578	-648	-722	-800	-882	-968	-1058	-1152	-1250	-1352	-1458	-1568	-1682

Figure 31. C004015 Table of Count of Odd Numbers Between Odd Compounds from C004001 Relative to Start Point in Odd Square Zones.

<https://1drv.ms/i/s!Arslv070x3WjkcgUSpcNyOdI9zqtg?e=dtX7DI>

For $n \geq 1$ and $k \geq 0$:

$$C004015_{horizontal} = -2k^2 = -2 * square$$

The verticals are constant.

All numbers are non-positive and even in the form of two times a square number.

12.6 C004016 Table of Count of Odd Numbers Between Odd Compounds from C004002 Relative to Start Point in Odd Square Zones

Using Odd Square Zone start points for C004002 table elements:

Odd	Start Point odd ²	End Point odd ²	# odds betw even odds	C004016 Table of Count of Odd Numbers Between Odd Compounds from C004002 Relative to Start Point in Odd Square Zones																															
				(EVEN Sq.) = n	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	
3	1	9	0	0	1	-1	-5	-13	-25	-41	-61	-85	-113	-145	-181	-221	-265	-313	-365	-421	-481	-545	-613	-685	-761	-841	-925	-1013	-1105	-1201	-1301	-1405	-1513	-1625	-1741
5	9	25	4	1	3	1	-3	-11	-23	-39	-59	-83	-111	-143	-179	-219	-263	-311	-363	-419	-479	-543	-611	-683	-759	-839	-923	-1011	-1103	-1199	-1299	-1403	-1511	-1623	-1739
7	25	49	12	3	7	5	1	-7	-19	-35	-55	-79	-107	-139	-175	-215	-259	-307	-359	-415	-475	-539	-607	-679	-755	-835	-919	-1007	-1099	-1195	-1295	-1399	-1507	-1618	-1735
9	49	81	20	5	11	7	3	-5	-17	-33	-53	-77	-105	-137	-173	-213	-257	-305	-357	-413	-473	-537	-605	-677	-753	-833	-917	-1005	-1097	-1193	-1293	-1397	-1505	-1617	-1735
11	81	121	28	7	15	9	5	-3	-15	-31	-51	-75	-103	-135	-171	-211	-255	-303	-355	-411	-471	-535	-603	-675	-751	-831	-915	-1003	-1095	-1191	-1291	-1395	-1503	-1615	-1731
13	121	169	36	9	21	11	7	-1	-13	-29	-49	-73	-101	-133	-169	-209	-253	-301	-353	-409	-469	-533	-601	-673	-749	-829	-913	-1001	-1093	-1189	-1289	-1393	-1501	-1613	-1729
15	169	225	44	11	27	13	9	1	-11	-27	-47	-71	-99	-131	-167	-207	-251	-299	-351	-407	-467	-531	-599	-671	-747	-827	-911	-999	-1091	-1187	-1287	-1391	-1499	-1611	-1727
17	225	289	52	13	35	15	11	3	-9	-25	-45	-69	-97	-129	-165	-205	-249	-297	-349	-405	-465	-529	-597	-669	-745	-825	-909	-997	-1089	-1185	-1285	-1389	-1497	-1609	-1725
19	289	361	60	15	41	17	13	5	-7	-23	-43	-67	-95	-127	-163	-203	-247	-295	-347	-403	-463	-527	-595	-667	-743	-823	-907	-995	-1087	-1183	-1283	-1387	-1495	-1607	-1723
21	361	441	68	17	49	19	15	7	-5	-21	-41	-65	-93	-125	-161	-201	-245	-293	-345	-401	-461	-525	-593	-665	-741	-821	-905	-993	-1085	-1181	-1281	-1385	-1493	-1605	-1721
23	441	529	76	19	57	21	17	9	-3	-19	-39	-63	-91	-123	-159	-199	-243	-291	-343	-399	-459	-523	-591	-663	-739	-819	-903	-991	-1083	-1179	-1279	-1383	-1491	-1603	-1719
25	529	625	84	21	65	23	19	11	-1	-17	-37	-61	-89	-121	-157	-197	-241	-289	-341	-397	-457	-521	-589	-661	-737	-817	-901	-989	-1081	-1177	-1277	-1381	-1489	-1601	-1717
27	625	729	92	23	73	25	21	13	1	-15	-35	-59	-87	-119	-155	-195	-239	-287	-339	-395	-455	-519	-587	-659	-735	-815	-903	-991	-1083	-1179	-1275	-1379	-1487	-1599	-1715
29	729	841	100	25	81	27	23	15	3	-13	-33	-57	-85	-117	-153	-193	-237	-285	-337	-393	-453	-517	-585	-657	-733	-813	-901	-989	-1081	-1177	-1273	-1377	-1485	-1597	-1713
31	841	961	108	27	89	29	25	17	5	-11	-31	-55	-83	-115	-151	-191	-235	-283	-335	-391	-451	-515	-583	-655	-731	-811	-895	-983	-1075	-1171	-1271	-1375	-1483	-1595	-1711
33	961	1089	116	29	97	31	27	19	7	-9	-29	-53	-81	-113	-149	-189	-233	-281	-333	-389	-449	-513	-581	-653	-729	-809	-893	-981	-1073	-1169	-1269	-1373	-1481	-1593	-1709
35	1089	1225	124	31	105	33	29	21	9	-7	-27	-51	-79	-111	-147	-187	-231	-279	-331	-387	-447	-511	-579	-651	-727	-807	-891	-979	-1071	-1167	-1267	-1371	-1479	-1591	-1707
37	1225	1369	132	33	113	35	31	23	11	-5	-25	-49	-77	-109	-145	-185	-229	-277	-329	-385	-445	-509	-577	-649	-725	-805	-889	-977	-1069	-1165	-1265	-1369	-1477	-1589	-1705
39	1369	1521	140	35	121	37	33	25	13	-3	-23	-47	-75	-107	-143	-183	-227	-275	-327	-383	-443	-507	-575	-647	-723	-803	-887	-975	-1067	-1163	-1263	-1367	-1475	-1587	-1703
41	1521	1681	148	37	129	39	35	27	15	-1	-21	-45	-73	-105	-141	-181	-225	-273	-325	-381	-441	-505	-573	-645	-721	-801	-885	-973	-1065	-1161	-1261	-1365	-1473	-1585	-1701
43	1681	1849	156	39	137	41	37	29	17	1	-19	-43	-71	-103	-139	-179	-223	-271	-323	-379	-439	-503	-571	-643	-719	-799	-883	-971	-1063	-1159	-1259	-1363	-1471	-1583	-1699
45	1849	2025	164	41	145	43	39	31	19	3	-17	-41	-69	-101	-137	-177	-221	-269	-321	-377	-437	-501	-569	-641	-717	-797	-881	-969	-1061	-1157	-1257	-1361	-1469	-1581	-1697
47	2025	2209	172	43	153	45	41	33	21	5	-15	-39	-67	-99	-135	-175	-219	-267	-319	-375	-435	-499	-567	-639	-715	-795	-879	-967	-1059	-1155	-1255	-1359	-1467	-1578	-1695
49	2209	2401	180	45	161	47	43	35	23	7	-13	-37	-65	-97	-133	-173	-217	-265	-317	-373	-433	-497	-565	-637	-713	-793	-877	-965	-1057	-1153	-1253	-1357	-1465	-1577	-1693
51	2401	2601	188	47	169	49	45	37	25	9	-11	-35	-63	-95	-131	-171	-215	-263	-315	-371	-431	-495	-563	-635	-711	-791	-875	-963	-1055	-1151	-1251	-1355	-1463	-1575	-1691
53	2601	2809	196	49	177	51	47	39	27	11	-9	-33	-61	-93	-129	-169	-213	-261	-313	-369	-429	-493	-561	-633	-709	-789	-873	-961	-1053	-1149	-1249	-1353	-1461	-1573	-1689
55	2809	3025	204	51	185	53	49	41	29	13	-7	-31	-59	-91	-127	-167	-211	-259	-311	-367	-427	-491	-559	-631	-707	-787	-871	-959	-1051	-1147	-1247	-1351	-1459	-1571	-1687
57	3025	3249	212	53	193	55	51	43	31	15	-5	-29	-57	-89	-125	-165	-209	-257	-309	-365	-425	-489	-557	-629	-705	-785	-869	-957	-1049	-1145	-1245	-1349	-1457	-1569	-1685
59	3249	3481	220	55	201	57	53	45	33	17	-3	-27	-55	-87	-123	-163	-207	-255	-307	-363	-423	-487	-555	-627	-703	-783	-867	-955	-1047	-1143	-1243	-1347	-1455	-1567	-1683

Figure 32. C004016 Table of Count of Odd Numbers Between Odd Compounds from C004002 Relative to Start Point in Odd Square Zones. https://1drv.ms/i/s!Arslv070x3WjkcgVO-lo_rvdd0oZw?e=ez8KQq

For $n \geq 1$ and $k \geq 0$:

$$C004016_{horizontal} = -2(n^2 - n) + (2k + 1) = -(2 * oblong) + (odd)$$

$$C004016_{vertical} = 2k - (2(n^2 - n) - 1) = (even) - (2 * oblong - 1)$$

All elements of C004016 are odd.

12.7 C004017 Table of Count of Odd Numbers Between Odd Compounds from C004001 Relative to Start Point in Even Square Zones

Using Even Square Zone start points for C004001 table elements:

Even	Start Point even ²	End Point (even +2) ²	# odds between even squares	C004017 Table of Count of Odd Numbers Between Odd Compounds from C004001 Relative to Start Point in Even Square Zones																															
				(ODD Sq.) - (EVEN Sq.)	k	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29
0	0	4	2	1	1	0	2	8	18	32	50	72	98	128	162	200	242	288	338	392	450	512	578	648	722	800	882	968	1058	1152	1250	1352	1458	1568	1682
2	4	16	6	2	3	3	1	-5	-15	-29	-47	-69	-95	-125	-159	-197	-239	-285	-335	-389	-447	-509	-575	-645	-719	-797	-879	-965	-1055	-1149	-1247	-1349	-1455	-1565	-1679
4	16	36	10	3	5	5	3	-3	-13	-27	-45	-67	-93	-123	-157	-195	-237	-283	-333	-387	-445	-507	-573	-643	-717	-795	-877	-963	-1053	-1147	-1245	-1347	-1453	-1563	-1677
6	36	64	14	4	7	7	5	-1	-11	-25	-43	-65	-91	-121	-155	-193	-235	-281	-331	-385	-443	-505	-571	-641	-715	-793	-875	-961	-1051	-1145	-1243	-1345	-1451	-1561	-1675
8	64	100	18	5	9	9	7	1	-9	-23	-41	-63	-89	-119	-153	-191	-233	-279	-329	-383	-441	-503	-569	-639	-713	-791	-873	-959	-1049	-1143	-1241	-1343	-1449	-1559	-1673
10	100	144	22	6	11	11	9	3	-7	-21	-39	-61	-87	-117	-151	-189	-231	-277	-327	-381	-439	-501	-567	-637	-711	-789	-871	-957	-1047	-1141	-1239	-1341	-1447	-1557	-1671
12	144	196	26	7	13	13	11	5	-5	-19	-37	-59	-85	-115	-149	-187	-229	-275	-325	-379	-437	-499	-565	-635	-709	-787	-869	-955	-1045	-1139	-1237	-1339	-1445	-1555	-1669
14	196	256	30	8	15	15	13	7	-3	-17	-35	-57	-83	-113	-147	-185	-227	-273	-323	-377	-435	-497	-563	-633	-707	-785	-867	-953	-1043	-1137	-1235	-1337	-1443	-1553	-1667
16	256	324	34	9	17	17	15	9	3	-15	-33	-55	-81	-111	-145	-183	-225	-271	-321	-375	-433	-495	-561	-631	-705	-783	-865	-951	-1041	-1135	-1233	-1335	-1441	-1551	-1665
18	324	400	38	10	19	19	17	11	1	-13	-31	-53	-79	-109	-143	-181	-223	-269	-319	-373	-431	-493	-559	-629	-703	-781	-863	-949	-1039	-1133	-1231	-1333	-1439	-1549	-1663
20	400	484	42	11	21	21	19	13	3	-11	-29	-51	-77	-107	-141	-179	-221	-267	-317	-371	-429	-491	-557	-627	-701	-779	-861	-947	-1037	-1131	-1229	-1331	-1437	-1547	-1661
22	484	576	46	12	23	23	21	15	5	-9	-27	-49	-75	-105	-139	-177	-219	-265	-315	-369	-427	-489	-555	-625	-699	-777	-859	-945	-1035	-1129	-1227	-1329	-1435	-1545	-1659
24	576	676	50	13	25	25	23	17	7	-7	-25	-47	-73	-103	-137	-175	-217	-263	-313	-367	-425	-487	-553	-623	-697	-775	-857	-943	-1033	-1127	-1225	-1327	-1433	-1543	-1657
26	676	784	54	14	27	27	25	19	9	-5	-23	-45	-71	-101	-135	-173	-215	-261	-311	-365	-423	-485	-551	-621	-695	-773	-855	-941	-1031	-1125	-1223	-1325	-1431	-1541	-1655
28	784	900	58	15	29	29	27	21	11	-3	-21	-43	-69	-99	-133	-171	-213	-259	-309	-363	-421	-483	-549	-619	-693	-771	-853	-939	-1029	-1123	-1221	-1323	-1429	-1539	-1653
30	900	1024	62	16	31	31	29	23	13	-1	-19	-41	-67	-97	-131	-169	-211	-257	-307	-361	-419	-481	-547	-617	-691	-769	-851	-937	-1027	-1121	-1219	-1321	-1427	-1537	-1651
32	1024	1156	66	17	33	33	31	25	15	1	-17	-39	-65	-95	-129	-167	-209	-255	-305	-359	-417	-479	-545	-615	-689	-767	-849	-935	-1025	-1119	-1217	-1319	-1425	-1535	-1649
34	1156	1296	70	18	35	35	33	27	17	3	-15	-37	-63	-93	-127	-165	-207	-253	-303	-357	-415	-477	-543	-613	-687	-765	-847	-933	-1023	-1117	-1215	-1317	-1423	-1533	-1647
36	1296	1444	74	19	37	37	35	29	19	5	-13	-35	-61	-91	-125	-163	-205	-251	-301	-355	-413	-475	-541	-611	-685	-763	-845	-931	-1021	-1115	-1213	-1315	-1421	-1531	-1645
38	1444	1600	78	20	39	39	37	31	21	7	-11	-33	-59	-89	-123	-161	-203	-249	-299	-353	-411	-473	-539	-609	-683	-761	-843	-929	-1019	-1113	-1211	-1313	-1419	-1529	-1643
40	1600	1764	82	21	41	41	39	33	23	9	-9	-31	-57	-87	-121	-159	-201	-247	-297	-351	-409	-471	-537	-607	-681	-759	-841	-927	-1017	-1111	-1209	-1311	-1417	-1527	-1641
42	1764	1936	86	22	43	43	41	35	25	11	-7	-29	-55	-85	-119	-157	-199	-245	-295	-349	-407	-469	-535	-605	-679	-757	-839	-925	-1015	-1109	-1207	-1309	-1415	-1525	-1639
44	1936	2116	90	23	45	45	43	37	27	13	-5	-27	-53	-83	-117	-155	-197	-243	-293	-347	-405	-467	-533	-603	-677	-755	-837	-923	-1013	-1107	-1205	-1307	-1413	-1523	-1637
46	2116	2304	94	24	47	47	45	39	29	15	-3	-25	-51	-81	-115	-153	-195	-241	-291	-345	-403	-465	-531	-601	-675	-753	-835	-921	-1011	-1105	-1203	-1305	-1411	-1521	-1635
48	2304	2500	98	25	49	49	47	41	31	17	-1	-23	-49	-79	-113	-151	-193	-239	-289	-343	-401	-463	-529	-599	-673	-751	-833	-919	-1009	-1103	-1201	-1303	-1409	-1519	-1633
50	2500	2704	102	26	51	51	49	43	33	19	1	-21	-47	-77	-111	-149	-191	-237	-287	-341	-399	-461	-527	-597	-671	-749	-831	-917	-1007	-1101	-1199	-1301	-1407	-1517	-1631
52	2704	2916	106	27	53	53	51	45	35	21	3	-19	-45	-75	-109	-147	-189	-235	-285	-339	-397	-459	-525	-595	-669	-747	-829	-915	-1005	-1099	-1197	-1299	-1405	-1515	-1629
54	2916	3136	110	28	55	55	53	47	37	23	5	-17	-43	-73	-107	-145	-187	-233	-283	-337	-395	-457	-523	-593	-667	-745	-827	-913	-1003	-1097	-1195	-1297	-1403	-1513	-1627
56	3136	3364	114	29	57	57	55	49	39	25	7	-15	-41	-71	-105	-143	-185	-231	-281	-335	-393	-455	-521	-591	-665	-743	-825	-911	-1001	-1095	-1193	-1295	-1401	-1511	-1625
58	3364	3600	118	30	59	59	57	51	41	27	9	-13	-39	-69	-103	-141	-183	-229	-279	-333	-391	-453	-519	-589	-663	-741	-823	-909	-999	-1093	-1191	-1293	-1399	-1509	-1623

Figure 33. C004017 Table of Count of Odd Numbers Between Odd Compounds from C004001 Relative to Start Point in Even Square Zones.

<https://1drv.ms/i/s!Arslv070x3WjkcqWNt9jLQwe3fyxIQ?e=YtNW36>

For $n \geq 1$ and $k \geq 0$:

$$C004017_{horizontal} = -2k^2 + (2n - 1) = -(2 * square) + (odd)$$

$$C004017_{vertical} = 2n - (2k^2 + 1) = (even) - (2 * square + 1)$$

All elements of C004017 are odd.

12.8 C004018 Table of Count of Odd Numbers Between Odd Compounds from C004002 Relative to Start Point in Even Square Zones

Using Even Square Zone start points for C004002 table elements:

		C004018 Table of Count of Odd Numbers Between Odd Compounds from C004002 Relative to Start Point in Even Square Zones																																		
Even	Start Point even ²	End Point (even +2) ²	# odds between even squares	(EVEN Sq.) - (ODD Sq.)	n	n ² -n																														
						1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	
				k	4k-2	2k	0	4	12	24	40	60	84	112	144	180	220	264	312	364	420	480	544	612	684	760	840	924	1012	1104	1200	1300	1404	1512	1624	1740
-2	4	0	-2	0	-2	-2	-6	-14	-26	-42	-62	-86	-114	-146	-182	-222	-266	-314	-366	-422	-482	-546	-614	-686	-762	-842	-926	-1014	-1106	-1202	-1302	-1406	-1514	-1626	-1742	
6	0	4	2	1	2	2	-2	-10	-22	-38	-58	-82	-110	-142	-178	-218	-262	-310	-362	-418	-478	-542	-610	-682	-758	-838	-922	-1010	-1102	-1198	-1298	-1402	-1510	-1622	-1738	
2	4	16	6	2	6	6	2	-6	-18	-34	-54	-78	-106	-138	-174	-214	-258	-306	-358	-414	-474	-538	-606	-678	-754	-834	-918	-1006	-1098	-1194	-1294	-1398	-1506	-1618	-1734	
4	16	36	10	3	10	10	6	-2	-14	-30	-50	-74	-102	-134	-170	-210	-254	-302	-354	-410	-470	-534	-602	-674	-750	-830	-914	-1002	-1094	-1190	-1290	-1394	-1502	-1614	-1730	
6	36	64	14	4	14	14	10	2	-10	-26	-46	-70	-98	-130	-166	-206	-250	-298	-350	-406	-466	-530	-598	-670	-746	-826	-910	-998	-1090	-1186	-1286	-1390	-1498	-1610	-1726	
8	64	100	18	5	18	18	14	6	-6	-22	-42	-66	-94	-126	-162	-202	-246	-294	-346	-402	-462	-526	-594	-666	-742	-822	-906	-994	-1086	-1182	-1282	-1386	-1494	-1606	-1722	
10	100	144	22	6	22	22	18	10	-2	-18	-38	-62	-90	-122	-158	-198	-242	-290	-342	-398	-458	-522	-590	-662	-738	-818	-902	-990	-1082	-1178	-1278	-1382	-1490	-1602	-1718	
12	144	196	26	7	26	26	22	14	2	-14	-34	-58	-86	-118	-154	-194	-238	-286	-338	-394	-454	-518	-586	-658	-734	-814	-898	-986	-1078	-1174	-1274	-1378	-1486	-1598	-1714	
14	196	256	30	8	30	30	26	18	8	-10	-30	-54	-82	-114	-150	-190	-234	-282	-334	-390	-450	-514	-582	-654	-730	-810	-894	-982	-1074	-1170	-1270	-1374	-1482	-1594	-1710	
16	256	324	34	9	34	34	30	22	10	-6	-26	-50	-78	-110	-146	-186	-230	-278	-330	-386	-446	-510	-578	-650	-726	-806	-890	-978	-1070	-1166	-1266	-1370	-1478	-1590	-1706	
18	324	400	38	10	38	38	34	26	14	-2	-22	-46	-74	-106	-142	-182	-226	-274	-326	-382	-442	-506	-574	-646	-722	-802	-886	-974	-1066	-1162	-1262	-1366	-1474	-1586	-1702	
20	400	484	42	11	42	42	38	30	18	2	-18	-42	-70	-102	-138	-178	-222	-270	-322	-378	-438	-502	-570	-642	-718	-798	-882	-970	-1062	-1158	-1258	-1362	-1470	-1582	-1698	
22	484	576	46	12	46	46	42	34	22	6	-14	-38	-66	-98	-134	-174	-218	-266	-318	-374	-434	-498	-566	-638	-714	-794	-878	-966	-1058	-1154	-1254	-1358	-1466	-1578	-1694	
24	576	676	50	13	50	50	46	38	26	10	-10	-34	-62	-94	-130	-170	-214	-262	-314	-370	-430	-494	-562	-634	-710	-790	-874	-962	-1054	-1150	-1250	-1354	-1462	-1574	-1690	
26	676	784	54	14	54	54	50	42	30	14	-6	-30	-58	-90	-126	-166	-210	-258	-310	-366	-426	-490	-558	-630	-706	-786	-870	-958	-1050	-1146	-1246	-1350	-1458	-1570	-1686	
28	784	900	58	15	58	58	54	46	34	18	-2	-26	-54	-86	-122	-162	-206	-254	-306	-362	-422	-486	-554	-626	-702	-782	-866	-954	-1046	-1142	-1242	-1346	-1454	-1566	-1682	
30	900	1024	62	16	62	62	58	50	38	22	2	-22	-50	-82	-118	-158	-202	-250	-302	-358	-418	-482	-550	-622	-698	-778	-862	-950	-1042	-1138	-1238	-1342	-1450	-1562	-1678	
32	1024	1156	66	17	66	66	62	54	42	26	6	-18	-46	-78	-114	-154	-198	-246	-298	-354	-414	-478	-546	-618	-694	-774	-858	-946	-1038	-1134	-1234	-1338	-1446	-1558	-1674	
34	1156	1296	70	18	70	70	66	58	46	30	10	-14	-42	-74	-110	-150	-194	-242	-294	-350	-410	-474	-542	-614	-690	-770	-854	-942	-1034	-1130	-1230	-1334	-1442	-1554	-1670	
36	1296	1444	74	19	74	74	70	62	50	34	14	-10	-38	-70	-106	-146	-190	-238	-290	-346	-406	-470	-538	-610	-686	-766	-850	-938	-1030	-1126	-1226	-1330	-1438	-1550	-1666	
38	1444	1600	78	20	78	78	74	66	54	38	18	-6	-34	-66	-102	-142	-186	-234	-286	-342	-402	-466	-534	-606	-682	-762	-846	-934	-1026	-1122	-1222	-1326	-1434	-1546	-1662	
40	1600	1764	82	21	82	82	78	70	58	42	22	-2	-30	-62	-98	-138	-182	-230	-282	-338	-398	-462	-530	-602	-678	-758	-842	-930	-1022	-1118	-1218	-1322	-1430	-1542	-1658	
42	1764	1936	86	22	86	86	82	74	62	46	26	2	-26	-58	-94	-134	-178	-226	-278	-334	-394	-458	-526	-598	-674	-754	-838	-926	-1018	-1114	-1214	-1318	-1426	-1538	-1654	
44	1936	2116	90	23	90	90	86	78	66	50	30	6	-22	-54	-90	-130	-174	-222	-274	-330	-390	-454	-522	-594	-670	-750	-834	-922	-1014	-1110	-1210	-1314	-1422	-1534	-1650	
46	2116	2304	94	24	94	94	90	82	70	54	34	10	-18	-50	-86	-126	-170	-218	-270	-326	-386	-450	-518	-590	-666	-746	-830	-918	-1010	-1106	-1206	-1310	-1418	-1530	-1646	
48	2304	2500	98	25	98	98	94	86	74	58	38	14	-14	-46	-82	-122	-166	-214	-266	-322	-382	-446	-514	-586	-662	-742	-826	-914	-1006	-1102	-1202	-1306	-1414	-1526	-1642	
50	2500	2704	102	26	102	102	98	90	78	62	42	18	-10	-42	-78	-118	-162	-210	-262	-318	-378	-442	-510	-582	-658	-738	-822	-910	-1002	-1098	-1198	-1302	-1410	-1522	-1638	
52	2704	2916	106	27	106	106	102	94	82	66	46	22	-6	-38	-74	-114	-158	-206	-258	-314	-374	-438	-506	-578	-654	-734	-818	-906	-998	-1094	-1194	-1298	-1406	-1518	-1634	
54	2916	3136	110	28	110	110	106	98	86	70	50	26	-2	-34	-70	-110	-154	-202	-254	-310	-370	-434	-502	-574	-650	-730	-814	-902	-994	-1090	-1190	-1294	-1402	-1514	-1630	
56	3136	3364	114	29	114	114	110	102	90	74	54	30	2	-30	-66	-106	-150	-198	-250	-306	-366	-430	-498	-570	-646	-726	-810	-898	-990	-1086	-1186	-1290	-1398	-1510	-1626	

Figure 34. C004018 Table of Count of Odd Numbers Between Odd Compounds from C004002 Relative to Start Point in Even Square Zones.

<https://1drv.ms/i/s!ArsIv070x3WjkcgXSYn4zNxN8EpAFw?e=UiskHz>

For $n \geq 1$ and $k \geq 0$:

$$C004018_{horizontal} = -2((n^2 - n) + (2k - 1)) = -2((oblong) + (odd))$$

$$C004018_{vertical} = 2(2k - (k^2 - k + 1)) = 2((even) - (central polygonal))$$

All elements of C004018 are even.

13 The Polynomial Distribution of Odd Compound Numbers Relative to End Point in all Zones

13.1 C004021 Table of Count of Odd Numbers Between Odd Compounds from C004001 Relative to End Point in 0212-Oblong Zones

Odd Numbers	Start Point: 0212-Oblongs	End Point: Next 0212-Oblongs	Number of Odd Numbers Between	C004021 Table of Count of Odd Numbers Between Odd Compounds from C004001 Relative to End Point in 0212-Oblong Zones																															
				(ODD Sq.) - (EVEN Sq.)	k	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29
				n	n-1	2n^2	0	2	8	18	32	50	72	98	128	162	200	242	288	338	392	450	512	578	648	722	800	882	968	1058	1152	1250	1352	1458	1568
-1	0	2	1	0	0	-2	-6	-18	-32	-50	-72	-98	-128	-162	-200	-242	-288	-338	-392	-450	-512	-578	-648	-722	-800	-882	-968	-1058	-1152	-1250	-1352	-1458	-1568	-1682	
1	2	12	5	2	1	-1	-5	-19	-33	-51	-73	-99	-129	-163	-201	-243	-289	-339	-393	-451	-513	-579	-649	-723	-801	-883	-969	-1059	-1153	-1251	-1353	-1459	-1569	-1683	
3	12	30	9	3	2	-2	-4	-10	-20	-34	-52	-74	-100	-130	-164	-202	-244	-290	-340	-394	-452	-514	-580	-650	-724	-802	-884	-970	-1060	-1154	-1252	-1354	-1460	-1570	-1684
5	30	56	13	4	3	-3	-5	-11	-21	-35	-53	-75	-101	-131	-165	-203	-245	-291	-341	-395	-453	-515	-581	-651	-725	-803	-885	-971	-1061	-1155	-1253	-1355	-1461	-1571	-1685
7	56	90	17	5	4	-4	-6	-12	-22	-36	-54	-76	-102	-132	-166	-204	-246	-292	-342	-396	-454	-516	-582	-652	-726	-804	-886	-972	-1062	-1156	-1254	-1356	-1462	-1572	-1686
9	90	132	21	6	5	-5	-7	-13	-23	-37	-55	-77	-103	-133	-167	-205	-247	-293	-343	-397	-455	-517	-583	-653	-727	-805	-887	-973	-1063	-1157	-1255	-1357	-1463	-1573	-1687
11	132	182	25	7	6	-6	-8	-14	-24	-38	-56	-78	-104	-134	-168	-206	-248	-294	-344	-398	-456	-518	-584	-654	-728	-806	-888	-974	-1064	-1158	-1256	-1358	-1464	-1574	-1688
13	182	240	29	8	7	-7	-9	-15	-25	-39	-57	-79	-105	-135	-169	-207	-249	-295	-345	-399	-457	-519	-585	-655	-729	-807	-889	-975	-1065	-1159	-1257	-1359	-1465	-1575	-1689
15	240	306	33	9	8	-8	-10	-16	-26	-40	-58	-80	-106	-136	-170	-208	-250	-296	-346	-400	-458	-520	-586	-656	-730	-808	-890	-976	-1066	-1160	-1258	-1360	-1466	-1576	-1690
17	306	380	37	10	9	-9	-11	-17	-27	-41	-59	-81	-107	-137	-171	-209	-251	-297	-347	-401	-459	-521	-587	-657	-731	-809	-891	-977	-1067	-1161	-1259	-1361	-1467	-1577	-1691
19	380	462	41	11	10	-10	-12	-18	-28	-42	-60	-82	-108	-138	-172	-210	-252	-298	-348	-402	-460	-522	-588	-658	-732	-810	-892	-978	-1068	-1162	-1260	-1362	-1468	-1578	-1692
21	462	552	45	12	11	-11	-13	-19	-29	-43	-61	-83	-109	-139	-173	-211	-253	-299	-349	-403	-461	-523	-589	-659	-733	-811	-893	-979	-1069	-1163	-1261	-1363	-1469	-1579	-1693
23	552	650	49	13	12	-12	-14	-20	-30	-44	-62	-84	-110	-140	-174	-212	-254	-300	-350	-404	-462	-524	-590	-660	-734	-812	-894	-980	-1070	-1164	-1262	-1364	-1470	-1580	-1694
25	650	756	53	14	13	-13	-15	-21	-31	-45	-63	-85	-111	-141	-175	-213	-255	-301	-351	-405	-463	-525	-591	-661	-735	-813	-895	-981	-1071	-1165	-1263	-1365	-1471	-1581	-1695
27	756	870	57	15	14	-14	-16	-22	-32	-46	-64	-86	-112	-142	-176	-214	-256	-302	-352	-406	-464	-526	-592	-662	-736	-814	-896	-982	-1072	-1166	-1264	-1366	-1472	-1582	-1696
29	870	992	61	16	15	-15	-17	-23	-33	-47	-65	-87	-113	-143	-177	-215	-257	-303	-353	-407	-465	-527	-593	-663	-737	-815	-897	-983	-1073	-1167	-1265	-1367	-1473	-1583	-1697
31	992	1122	65	17	16	-16	-18	-24	-34	-48	-66	-88	-114	-144	-178	-216	-258	-304	-354	-408	-466	-528	-594	-664	-738	-816	-898	-984	-1074	-1168	-1266	-1368	-1474	-1584	-1698
33	1122	1260	69	18	17	-17	-19	-25	-35	-49	-67	-89	-115	-145	-179	-217	-259	-305	-355	-409	-467	-529	-595	-665	-739	-817	-899	-985	-1075	-1169	-1267	-1369	-1475	-1585	-1699
35	1260	1406	73	19	18	-18	-20	-26	-36	-50	-68	-90	-116	-146	-180	-218	-260	-306	-356	-410	-468	-530	-596	-666	-740	-818	-900	-986	-1076	-1170	-1268	-1370	-1476	-1586	-1700
37	1406	1560	77	20	19	-19	-21	-27	-37	-51	-69	-91	-117	-147	-181	-219	-261	-307	-357	-411	-469	-531	-597	-667	-741	-819	-901	-987	-1077	-1171	-1269	-1371	-1477	-1587	-1701
39	1560	1722	81	21	20	-20	-22	-28	-38	-52	-70	-92	-118	-148	-182	-220	-262	-308	-358	-412	-470	-532	-598	-668	-742	-820	-902	-988	-1078	-1172	-1270	-1372	-1478	-1588	-1702
41	1722	1892	85	22	21	-21	-23	-29	-39	-53	-71	-93	-119	-149	-183	-221	-263	-309	-359	-413	-471	-533	-599	-669	-743	-821	-903	-989	-1079	-1173	-1271	-1373	-1479	-1589	-1703
43	1892	2070	89	23	22	-22	-24	-30	-40	-54	-72	-94	-120	-150	-184	-222	-264	-310	-360	-414	-472	-534	-600	-670	-744	-822	-904	-990	-1080	-1174	-1272	-1374	-1480	-1590	-1704
45	2070	2256	93	24	23	-23	-25	-31	-41	-55	-73	-95	-121	-151	-185	-223	-265	-311	-361	-415	-473	-535	-601	-671	-745	-823	-905	-991	-1081	-1175	-1273	-1375	-1481	-1591	-1705
47	2256	2450	97	25	24	-24	-26	-32	-42	-56	-74	-96	-122	-152	-186	-224	-266	-312	-362	-416	-474	-536	-602	-672	-746	-824	-906	-992	-1082	-1176	-1274	-1376	-1482	-1592	-1706
49	2450	2652	101	26	25	-25	-27	-33	-43	-57	-75	-97	-123	-153	-187	-225	-267	-313	-363	-417	-475	-537	-603	-673	-747	-825	-907	-993	-1083	-1177	-1275	-1377	-1483	-1593	-1707
51	2652	2862	105	27	26	-26	-28	-34	-44	-58	-76	-98	-124	-154	-188	-226	-268	-314	-364	-418	-476	-538	-604	-674	-748	-826	-908	-994	-1084	-1178	-1276	-1378	-1484	-1594	-1708
53	2862	3080	109	28	27	-27	-29	-35	-45	-59	-77	-99	-125	-155	-189	-227	-269	-315	-365	-419	-477	-539	-605	-675	-749	-827	-909	-995	-1085	-1179	-1277	-1379	-1485	-1595	-1709
55	3080	3306	113	29	28	-28	-30	-36	-46	-60	-78	-100	-126	-156	-190	-228	-270	-316	-366	-420	-478	-540	-606	-676	-750	-828	-910	-996	-1086	-1180	-1278	-1380	-1486	-1596	-1710
57	3306	3540	117	30	29	-29	-31	-37	-47	-61	-79	-101	-127	-157	-191	-229	-271	-317	-367	-421	-479	-541	-607	-677	-751	-829	-911	-997	-1087	-1181	-1279	-1381	-1487	-1597	-1711

Figure 35. C004021 Table of Count of Odd Numbers Between Odd Compounds from C004001 Relative to End Point in 0212-Oblong Zones.

<https://1drv.ms/i/s!Arslv070x3Wjkgc6EsYGvAuLT0nmLQ?e=5ffFTY>

For $n \geq 1$ and $k \geq 0$:

$$C004021_{horizontal} = -2k^2 - (n - 1) = -(2 * square) - integer$$

$$C004021_{vertical} = -n - 2(k^2 - 1) = (integer) - (2 * (square - 1))$$

The sequences of primal numbers $x = 2y^2 - 199$ and $x = 2y^2 - 181$ both with 55 consecutive primals, $x = 2y^2 - 61$ with 31 primals, $x = 2y^2 - 11$ with 21 primals, and $x = 2y^2 - 29$ with 57 primals stand out.

13.2 C004022 Table of Count of Odd Numbers Between Odd Compounds from C004002 Relative to End Point in 0212-Oblong Zones

The same procedure is applied in $C004002 = (even)^2 - (odd)^2$ to obtain:

Odd Numbers	Start Point Next Oblong (Odd)	End Point Oblong (Odd)	Number of Odd Numbers Between	C004022 Table of Count of Odd Numbers Between Odd Compounds from C004002 Relative to End Point in 0212-Oblong Zones																																			
				(EVEN Sq.)	(ODD Sq.)	n	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30			
				k	3k+1	2*Ob	0	4	12	24	40	60	84	112	144	180	220	264	312	364	420	480	544	612	684	760	840	924	1012	1104	1200	1300	1404	1512	1624	1740			
-1	0	2	-3	0	1																																		
1	2	12	1	4																																			
3	12	30	5	2	7																																		
5	30	58	9	3	10																																		
7	58	90	13	4	13																																		
9	90	132	17	5	16																																		
11	132	182	21	6	19																																		
13	182	240	25	7	22																																		
15	240	306	29	8	25																																		
17	306	380	33	9	28																																		
19	380	462	37	10	31																																		
21	462	552	41	11	34																																		
23	552	650	45	12	37																																		
25	650	758	49	13	40																																		
27	758	870	53	14	43																																		
29	870	992	57	15	46																																		
31	992	1122	61	16	49																																		
33	1122	1260	65	17	52																																		
35	1260	1408	69	18	55																																		
37	1408	1560	73	19	58																																		
39	1560	1722	77	20	61																																		
41	1722	1892	81	21	64																																		
43	1892	2070	85	22	67																																		
45	2070	2268	89	23	70																																		
47	2268	2490	93	24	73																																		
49	2490	2852	97	25	76																																		
51	2852	3262	101	26	79																																		
53	3262	3800	105	27	82																																		
55	3800	4306	109	28	85																																		
57	4306	4840	113	29	88																																		

Figure 36. C004022 Table of Count of Odd Numbers Between Odd Compounds from C004002 Relative to End Point in 0212-Oblong Zones.

https://1drv.ms/i/s!ArsIv070x3Wjkgc7pUkFOZPhdtx_gQ?e=KRb0YH

For $n \geq 1$ and $k \geq 0$:

$$C004022_{horizontal} = -2(n^2 - n) - (3k + 1) = -2 * (oblong) - (X \text{ mod } 3 = 1)$$

$$C004022_{vertical} = -3k - (2(n^2 - n) + 1) = (X \text{ mod } 3 = 0) - (2 * oblong + 1)$$

The sequences of primal numbers $x = 2y^2 - 2y + 19$ with 36 consecutive primals, $x = 2y^2 - 2y - 41$ with 26 consecutive primals, $x = 2y^2 - 2y - 71$ with 32 primals, $x = 2y^2 - 2y - 83$ with 34 primals, and $x = 2y^2 - 2y - 113$ with 44 primals stand out.

13.3 C004023 Table of Count of Odd Numbers Between Odd Compounds from C004001 Relative to End Point in 0620-Oblong Zones

Using 0620-Oblong Zone start points for C004001 table elements:

even	Start Point even + (even + 1)	End Point (even + 2) + (even + 3)	# odds betw en oblon gs	C004023 Table of Count of Odd Numbers Between Odd Compounds from C004001 Relative to End Point in 0620-Oblong Zones																															
				(ODD Sq.) - (EVEN Sq.)	k	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29
0	0	6	3	1	2	-2	-4	-10	-20	-34	-52	-74	-100	-130	-164	-202	-244	-290	-340	-394	-452	-514	-580	-650	-724	-802	-884	-970	-1060	-1154	-1252	-1354	-1460	-1570	-1684
2	6	20	7	2	5	-5	-7	-13	-23	-37	-55	-77	-103	-133	-167	-205	-247	-293	-343	-397	-455	-517	-583	-653	-727	-805	-887	-973	-1063	-1157	-1255	-1357	-1463	-1573	-1687
4	20	42	11	3	8	-9	-10	-18	-28	-40	-58	-80	-106	-136	-170	-208	-250	-296	-346	-400	-458	-520	-586	-656	-730	-808	-890	-976	-1066	-1160	-1258	-1360	-1466	-1576	-1690
6	42	72	15	4	11	-11	-13	-19	-29	-43	-61	-83	-109	-139	-173	-211	-253	-299	-349	-403	-461	-523	-589	-659	-733	-811	-893	-979	-1069	-1163	-1261	-1363	-1469	-1579	-1693
8	72	110	19	5	14	-14	-16	-22	-32	-46	-64	-86	-112	-142	-176	-214	-256	-302	-352	-406	-464	-526	-592	-662	-736	-814	-896	-982	-1072	-1166	-1264	-1366	-1472	-1582	-1696
10	110	156	23	6	17	-17	-19	-25	-35	-49	-67	-89	-115	-145	-179	-217	-259	-305	-355	-409	-467	-529	-595	-665	-739	-817	-899	-985	-1075	-1169	-1267	-1369	-1475	-1585	-1699
12	156	210	27	7	20	-20	-22	-28	-38	-52	-70	-92	-118	-148	-182	-220	-262	-308	-358	-412	-470	-532	-598	-668	-742	-820	-902	-988	-1078	-1172	-1270	-1372	-1478	-1588	-1702
14	210	272	31	8	23	-23	-25	-31	-41	-55	-73	-95	-121	-151	-185	-223	-265	-311	-361	-415	-473	-535	-601	-671	-745	-823	-905	-991	-1081	-1175	-1273	-1375	-1481	-1591	-1705
16	272	342	35	9	26	-26	-28	-34	-44	-58	-76	-98	-124	-154	-188	-226	-268	-314	-364	-418	-476	-538	-604	-674	-748	-826	-908	-994	-1084	-1178	-1276	-1378	-1484	-1594	-1708
18	342	420	39	10	29	-29	-31	-37	-47	-61	-79	-101	-127	-157	-191	-229	-271	-317	-367	-421	-479	-541	-607	-677	-751	-829	-911	-997	-1087	-1181	-1279	-1381	-1487	-1597	-1711
20	420	506	43	11	32	-32	-34	-40	-50	-64	-82	-104	-130	-160	-194	-232	-274	-320	-370	-424	-482	-544	-610	-680	-754	-832	-914	-1000	-1090	-1184	-1282	-1384	-1490	-1600	-1714
22	506	600	47	12	35	-35	-37	-43	-53	-67	-85	-107	-133	-163	-197	-235	-277	-323	-373	-427	-485	-547	-613	-683	-757	-835	-917	-1003	-1093	-1187	-1285	-1387	-1493	-1603	-1717
24	600	702	51	13	38	-38	-40	-46	-56	-70	-88	-110	-136	-166	-200	-238	-280	-326	-376	-430	-488	-550	-616	-686	-760	-838	-920	-1006	-1096	-1190	-1288	-1390	-1496	-1606	-1720
26	702	812	55	14	41	-41	-43	-49	-59	-73	-91	-113	-139	-169	-203	-241	-283	-329	-379	-433	-491	-553	-619	-689	-763	-841	-923	-1009	-1099	-1193	-1291	-1393	-1499	-1609	-1723
28	812	930	59	15	44	-44	-46	-52	-62	-76	-94	-116	-142	-172	-206	-244	-286	-332	-382	-436	-494	-556	-622	-692	-766	-844	-926	-1012	-1102	-1196	-1294	-1396	-1502	-1612	-1726
30	930	1056	63	16	47	-47	-49	-55	-65	-79	-97	-119	-145	-175	-209	-247	-289	-335	-385	-439	-497	-559	-625	-695	-769	-847	-929	-1015	-1105	-1199	-1297	-1399	-1505	-1615	-1729
32	1056	1190	67	17	50	-50	-52	-58	-68	-82	-100	-122	-148	-178	-212	-250	-292	-338	-388	-442	-500	-562	-628	-698	-772	-850	-932	-1018	-1108	-1202	-1300	-1402	-1508	-1618	-1732
34	1190	1332	71	18	53	-53	-55	-61	-71	-85	-103	-125	-151	-181	-215	-253	-295	-341	-391	-445	-503	-565	-631	-701	-775	-853	-935	-1021	-1111	-1205	-1303	-1405	-1511	-1621	-1735
36	1332	1482	75	19	56	-56	-58	-64	-74	-88	-106	-128	-154	-184	-218	-256	-298	-344	-394	-448	-506	-568	-634	-704	-778	-856	-938	-1024	-1114	-1208	-1306	-1408	-1514	-1624	-1738
38	1482	1640	79	20	59	-59	-61	-67	-77	-91	-109	-131	-157	-187	-221	-259	-301	-347	-397	-451	-509	-571	-637	-707	-781	-859	-941	-1027	-1117	-1211	-1309	-1411	-1517	-1627	-1741
40	1640	1806	83	21	62	-62	-64	-70	-80	-94	-112	-134	-160	-190	-224	-262	-304	-350	-400	-454	-512	-574	-640	-710	-784	-862	-944	-1030	-1120	-1214	-1312	-1414	-1520	-1630	-1744
42	1806	1980	87	22	65	-65	-67	-73	-83	-97	-115	-137	-163	-193	-227	-265	-307	-353	-403	-457	-515	-577	-643	-713	-787	-865	-947	-1033	-1123	-1217	-1315	-1417	-1523	-1633	-1747
44	1980	2162	91	23	68	-68	-70	-76	-86	-100	-118	-140	-166	-196	-230	-268	-310	-356	-406	-460	-518	-580	-646	-716	-790	-868	-950	-1036	-1126	-1220	-1318	-1420	-1526	-1636	-1750
46	2162	2352	95	24	71	-71	-73	-79	-89	-103	-121	-143	-169	-199	-233	-271	-313	-359	-409	-463	-521	-583	-649	-719	-793	-871	-953	-1039	-1129	-1223	-1321	-1423	-1529	-1639	-1753
48	2352	2550	99	25	74	-74	-76	-82	-92	-106	-124	-146	-172	-202	-236	-274	-316	-362	-412	-466	-524	-586	-652	-722	-796	-874	-956	-1042	-1132	-1226	-1324	-1426	-1532	-1642	-1756
50	2550	2756	103	26	77	-77	-79	-85	-95	-109	-127	-149	-175	-205	-239	-277	-319	-365	-415	-469	-527	-589	-655	-725	-799	-877	-959	-1045	-1135	-1229	-1327	-1429	-1535	-1645	-1759
52	2756	2970	107	27	80	-80	-82	-88	-98	-112	-130	-152	-178	-208	-242	-280	-322	-368	-418	-472	-530	-592	-658	-728	-802	-880	-962	-1048	-1138	-1232	-1330	-1432	-1538	-1648	-1762
54	2970	3192	111	28	83	-83	-85	-91	-101	-115	-133	-155	-181	-211	-245	-283	-325	-371	-421	-475	-533	-595	-661	-731	-805	-883	-965	-1051	-1141	-1235	-1333	-1435	-1541	-1651	-1765
56	3192	3422	115	29	86	-86	-88	-94	-104	-118	-136	-158	-184	-214	-248	-286	-328	-374	-424	-478	-536	-598	-664	-734	-808	-886	-968	-1054	-1144	-1238	-1336	-1438	-1544	-1654	-1768
58	3422	3660	119	30	89	-89	-91	-97	-107	-121	-139	-161	-187	-217	-251	-289	-331	-377	-427	-481	-539	-601	-667	-737	-811	-889	-971	-1057	-1147	-1241	-1339	-1441	-1547	-1657	-1771

Figure 37. C004023 Table of Count of Odd Numbers Between Odd Compounds from C004001 Relative to End Point in 0620-Oblong Zones.

<https://1drv.ms/i/s!Arslv070x3Wjkcg8NDzwwAll2HPVDg?e=WL88S9>

For $n \geq 1$ and $k \geq 0$:

$$C004023horizontal = -2k^2 - (3n - 1) = -(2 * square) - (X \text{ mod } 3 = 2)$$

$$C004023vertical = -3n - 2k^2 + 1 = -(X \text{ mod } 3 = 2) - (2 * square)$$

The verticals are the integer numbers. So, this matrix is like <https://www.mersenneforum.org/showthread.php?t=28194> but now with a 2nd degree coefficient equal to 2.

Clearly $x = 18y^2 - 9y + 1$ is the CG that limits the primal sequences $x = 2y^2 + c$ to $c = \{5, 11, 29\}$.

13.4 C004024 Table of Count of Odd Numbers Between Odd Compounds from C004002 Relative to End Point in 0620-Oblong Zones

Using 0620-Oblong Zone start points for C004002 table elements:

even	Start Point (even +)	End Point (even +2) + (even +3)	# odds betw en oblon gs	C004024 Table of Count of Odd Numbers Between Odd Compounds from C004002 Relative to End Point in 0620-Oblong Zones																																
				(ODD Sq.) - k	n	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	
-2	2	0	3	0	0	0	4	12	24	40	60	84	112	144	180	220	264	312	364	420	480	544	612	684	760	840	924	1012	1104	1200	1300	1404	1512	1624	1740	
0	0	6	7	1	1	1	-5	-13	-25	-41	-61	-85	-113	-145	-181	-221	-265	-313	-365	-421	-481	-545	-613	-685	-761	-841	-925	-1013	-1105	-1201	-1301	-1405	-1513	-1625	-1741	
2	6	20	11	2	2	2	-2	-6	-14	-26	-42	-62	-86	-114	-146	-182	-222	-266	-314	-366	-422	-482	-546	-614	-686	-762	-842	-926	-1014	-1106	-1202	-1302	-1406	-1514	-1626	-1742
4	20	42	15	3	3	3	-3	-7	-16	-27	-43	-63	-87	-115	-147	-183	-223	-267	-315	-367	-423	-483	-547	-615	-687	-763	-843	-927	-1015	-1107	-1203	-1303	-1407	-1515	-1627	-1743
6	42	72	19	4	4	4	-4	-9	-17	-29	-45	-65	-89	-117	-149	-185	-225	-269	-317	-369	-425	-485	-549	-617	-689	-765	-845	-929	-1017	-1109	-1205	-1305	-1409	-1517	-1629	-1745
8	72	110	23	5	5	5	-5	-9	-17	-29	-45	-65	-89	-117	-149	-185	-225	-269	-317	-369	-425	-485	-549	-617	-689	-765	-845	-929	-1017	-1109	-1205	-1305	-1409	-1517	-1629	-1745
10	110	156	27	6	6	6	-6	-10	-18	-30	-46	-66	-90	-118	-150	-186	-226	-270	-318	-370	-426	-486	-550	-618	-690	-766	-846	-930	-1018	-1110	-1206	-1306	-1410	-1518	-1630	-1746
12	156	210	31	7	7	7	-7	-11	-19	-31	-47	-67	-91	-119	-151	-187	-227	-271	-319	-371	-427	-487	-551	-619	-691	-767	-847	-931	-1019	-1111	-1207	-1307	-1411	-1519	-1631	-1747
14	210	272	35	8	8	8	-8	-12	-20	-32	-48	-68	-92	-120	-152	-188	-228	-272	-320	-372	-428	-488	-552	-620	-692	-768	-848	-932	-1020	-1112	-1208	-1308	-1412	-1520	-1632	-1748
16	272	342	39	9	9	9	-9	-13	-21	-33	-49	-69	-93	-121	-153	-189	-229	-273	-321	-373	-429	-489	-553	-621	-693	-769	-849	-933	-1021	-1113	-1209	-1309	-1413	-1521	-1633	-1749
18	342	420	43	10	10	10	-10	-14	-22	-34	-50	-70	-94	-122	-154	-190	-230	-274	-322	-374	-430	-490	-554	-622	-694	-770	-850	-934	-1022	-1114	-1210	-1310	-1414	-1522	-1634	-1750
20	420	506	47	11	11	11	-11	-15	-23	-35	-51	-71	-95	-123	-155	-191	-231	-275	-323	-375	-431	-491	-555	-623	-695	-771	-851	-935	-1023	-1115	-1211	-1311	-1415	-1523	-1635	-1751
22	506	600	51	12	12	12	-12	-16	-24	-36	-52	-72	-96	-124	-156	-192	-232	-276	-324	-376	-432	-492	-556	-624	-696	-772	-852	-936	-1024	-1116	-1212	-1312	-1416	-1524	-1636	-1752
24	600	702	55	13	13	13	-13	-17	-25	-37	-53	-73	-97	-125	-157	-193	-233	-277	-325	-377	-433	-493	-557	-625	-697	-773	-853	-937	-1025	-1117	-1213	-1313	-1417	-1525	-1637	-1753
26	702	812	59	14	14	14	-14	-18	-26	-38	-54	-74	-98	-126	-158	-194	-234	-278	-326	-378	-434	-494	-558	-626	-698	-774	-854	-938	-1026	-1118	-1214	-1314	-1418	-1526	-1638	-1754
28	812	930	63	15	15	15	-15	-19	-27	-39	-55	-75	-99	-127	-159	-195	-235	-279	-327	-379	-435	-495	-559	-627	-699	-775	-855	-939	-1027	-1119	-1215	-1315	-1419	-1527	-1639	-1755
30	930	1056	67	16	16	16	-16	-20	-28	-40	-56	-76	-100	-128	-160	-196	-236	-280	-328	-380	-436	-496	-560	-628	-700	-776	-856	-940	-1028	-1120	-1216	-1316	-1420	-1528	-1640	-1756
32	1056	1190	71	17	17	17	-17	-21	-29	-41	-57	-77	-101	-129	-161	-197	-237	-281	-329	-381	-437	-497	-561	-629	-701	-777	-857	-941	-1029	-1121	-1217	-1317	-1421	-1529	-1641	-1757
34	1190	1332	75	18	18	18	-18	-22	-30	-42	-58	-78	-102	-130	-162	-198	-238	-282	-330	-382	-438	-498	-562	-630	-702	-778	-858	-942	-1030	-1122	-1218	-1318	-1422	-1530	-1642	-1758
36	1332	1482	79	19	19	19	-19	-23	-31	-43	-59	-79	-103	-131	-163	-199	-239	-283	-331	-383	-439	-499	-563	-631	-703	-779	-859	-943	-1031	-1123	-1219	-1319	-1423	-1531	-1643	-1759
38	1482	1640	83	20	20	20	-20	-24	-32	-44	-60	-80	-104	-132	-164	-200	-240	-284	-332	-384	-440	-500	-564	-632	-704	-780	-860	-944	-1032	-1124	-1220	-1320	-1424	-1532	-1644	-1760
40	1640	1806	87	21	21	21	-21	-25	-33	-45	-61	-81	-105	-133	-165	-201	-241	-285	-333	-385	-441	-501	-565	-633	-705	-781	-861	-945	-1033	-1125	-1221	-1321	-1425	-1533	-1645	-1761
42	1806	1980	91	22	22	22	-22	-26	-34	-46	-62	-82	-106	-134	-166	-202	-242	-286	-334	-386	-442	-502	-566	-634	-706	-782	-862	-946	-1034	-1126	-1222	-1322	-1426	-1534	-1646	-1762
44	1980	2162	95	23	23	23	-23	-27	-35	-47	-63	-83	-107	-135	-167	-203	-243	-287	-335	-387	-443	-503	-567	-635	-707	-783	-863	-947	-1035	-1127	-1223	-1323	-1427	-1535	-1647	-1763
46	2162	2352	99	24	24	24	-24	-28	-36	-48	-64	-84	-108	-136	-168	-204	-244	-288	-336	-388	-444	-504	-568	-636	-708	-784	-864	-948	-1036	-1128	-1224	-1324	-1428	-1536	-1648	-1764
48	2352	2550	103	25	25	25	-25	-29	-37	-49	-65	-85	-109	-137	-169	-205	-245	-289	-337	-389	-445	-505	-569	-637	-709	-785	-865	-949	-1037	-1129	-1225	-1325	-1429	-1537	-1649	-1765
50	2550	2756	107	26	26	26	-26	-30	-38	-50	-66	-86	-110	-138	-170	-206	-246	-290	-338	-390	-446	-506	-570	-638	-710	-786	-866	-950	-1038	-1130	-1226	-1326	-1430	-1538	-1650	-1766
52	2756	2970	111	27	27	27	-27	-31	-39	-51	-67	-87	-111	-139	-171	-207	-247	-291	-339	-391	-447	-507	-571	-639	-711	-787	-867	-951	-1039	-1131	-1227	-1327	-1431	-1539	-1651	-1767
54	2970	3192	115	28	28	28	-28	-32	-40	-52	-68	-88	-112	-140	-172	-208	-248	-292	-340	-392	-448	-508	-572	-640	-712	-788	-868	-952	-1040	-1132	-1228	-1328	-1432	-1540	-1652	-1768
56	3192	3422	119	29	29	29	-29	-33	-41	-53	-69	-89	-113	-141	-173	-209	-249	-293	-341	-393	-449	-509	-573	-641	-713	-789	-869	-953	-1041	-1133	-1229	-1329	-1433	-1541	-1653	-1769

Figure 38. C004024 Table of Count of Odd Numbers Between Odd Compounds from C004002 Relative to End Point in 0620-Oblong Zones.

<https://1drv.ms/i/s!Arslv070x3Wjkc9Jru5cI2h4tWAFQ?e=fDJYfu>

For $n \geq 1$ and $k \geq 0$:

$$C004024_{horizontal} = -2(n^2 - n) - k = -(2 * oblong) - (integer)$$

$$C004024_{vertical} = -k - 2(n^2 - n) = -(integer) - (2 * oblong)$$

13.5 C004025 Table of Count of Odd Numbers Between Odd Compounds from C004001 Relative to End Point in Odd Square Zones

Using Odd Square Zone start points for C004001 table elements:

Odd	Start Point (odd +2)	End Point (odd +2)	# odds betw en odd square	C004025 Table of Count of Odd Numbers Between Odd Compounds from C004001 Relative to End Point in Odd Square Zones																																
				(ODD Sq.) - k	n	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	
1	1	3	4	1	4	0	2	8	18	32	50	72	98	128	162	200	242	288	338	392	450	512	578	648	722	800	882	968	1058	1152	1250	1352	1458	1568	1682	
3	9	25	8	2	8	0	-1	-14	-20	-30	-44	-62	-84	-110	-140	-174	-212	-254	-300	-350	-404	-462	-524	-590	-660	-734	-812	-894	-980	-1070	-1164	-1262	-1364	-1470	-1580	-1694
5	25	49	12	3	12	0	-2	-18	-24	-34	-48	-66	-88	-114	-144	-178	-216	-258	-304	-354	-408	-466	-528	-594	-664	-738	-816	-898	-986	-1078	-1174	-1274	-1378	-1486	-1598	-1714
7	49	81	16	4	16	0	-3	-22	-28	-38	-52	-70	-92	-118	-148	-182	-220	-262	-308	-358	-412	-470	-532	-598	-668	-742	-820	-902	-988	-1078	-1172	-1270	-1372	-1478	-1588	-1702
9	81	121	20	5	20	0	-4	-26	-32	-42	-56	-74	-96	-122	-152	-186	-224	-266	-312	-362	-416	-474	-536	-602	-672	-746	-824	-906	-992	-1082	-1176	-1274	-1376	-1482	-1592	-1706
11	121	169	24	6	24	0	-5	-30	-36	-46	-60	-78	-100	-126	-156	-190	-228	-270	-316	-366	-420	-478	-540	-606	-676	-750	-828	-910	-996	-1086	-1180	-1278	-1380	-1486	-1596	-1710
13	169	225	28	7	28	0	-6	-34	-40	-50	-64	-82	-104	-130	-160	-194	-232	-274	-320	-370	-424	-482	-544	-610	-680	-754	-832	-914	-1000	-1090	-1184	-1282	-1384	-1490	-1600	-1714
15	225	289	32	8	32	0	-7</																													

Figure 39. C004025 Table of Count of Odd Numbers Between Odd Compounds from C004001 Relative to End Point in Odd Square Zones. <https://1drv.ms/i/s!Arslv070x3Wjkcg-Bk0peB4sbphexg?e=lgW0zU>

For $n \geq 1$ and $k \geq 0$:

$$C004025_{horizontal} = -2k^2 - 4n = -2(k^2 + 2n) = -2 * (square + even)$$

$$C004025_{vertical} = -4n - 2k^2 = -2(even + square)$$

All numbers are negative and even.

13.6 C004026 Table of Count of Odd Numbers Between Odd Compounds from C004002 Relative to End Point in Odd Square Zones

Using Odd Square Zone start points for C004002 table elements:

Odd	Start Point odd ²	End Point odd ²	# odds between odds	C004026 Table of Count of Odd Numbers Between Odd Compounds from C004002 Relative to End Point in Odd Square Zones																															
				(EVEN Sq.)	n	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30
				(ODD Sq.)	n ² :n	0	2	6	12	20	30	42	56	72	90	110	132	156	182	210	240	272	306	342	380	420	462	506	552	600	650	702	756	812	870
1	1	1	0	0	1	-3	-5	-13	-25	-41	-61	-85	-113	-145	-181	-221	-265	-313	-365	-421	-481	-545	-613	-685	-761	-841	-925	-1013	-1105	-1201	-1301	-1405	-1513	-1625	-1741
3	9	9	4	1	3	-5	-9	-17	-29	-45	-65	-89	-117	-149	-185	-225	-269	-317	-369	-425	-485	-549	-617	-689	-765	-845	-929	-1017	-1109	-1205	-1305	-1409	-1517	-1629	-1745
5	25	25	8	2	5	-7	-11	-19	-31	-47	-67	-91	-119	-151	-187	-227	-271	-319	-371	-427	-487	-551	-619	-691	-767	-847	-931	-1019	-1111	-1207	-1307	-1411	-1519	-1631	-1747
7	49	49	16	4	7	-9	-13	-21	-33	-49	-69	-93	-121	-153	-189	-229	-273	-321	-373	-429	-489	-553	-621	-693	-769	-849	-933	-1021	-1113	-1209	-1309	-1413	-1521	-1633	-1749
9	81	81	24	6	9	-11	-15	-23	-35	-51	-71	-95	-123	-155	-191	-231	-275	-323	-375	-431	-491	-555	-623	-695	-771	-851	-935	-1023	-1115	-1211	-1311	-1415	-1523	-1635	-1751
11	121	121	32	8	11	-13	-17	-25	-37	-53	-73	-97	-125	-157	-193	-233	-277	-325	-377	-433	-493	-557	-625	-697	-773	-853	-937	-1025	-1117	-1213	-1313	-1417	-1525	-1637	-1753
13	169	169	40	10	13	-15	-19	-27	-39	-55	-75	-99	-127	-159	-195	-235	-279	-327	-379	-435	-495	-559	-627	-699	-775	-855	-939	-1027	-1119	-1215	-1315	-1419	-1527	-1639	-1755
15	225	225	48	12	15	-17	-21	-29	-41	-57	-77	-101	-129	-161	-197	-237	-281	-329	-381	-437	-497	-561	-629	-701	-777	-857	-941	-1029	-1121	-1217	-1317	-1421	-1529	-1641	-1757
17	289	289	56	14	17	-19	-23	-31	-43	-59	-79	-103	-131	-163	-199	-239	-283	-331	-383	-439	-499	-563	-631	-703	-779	-859	-943	-1031	-1123	-1219	-1319	-1423	-1531	-1643	-1759
19	361	361	64	16	19	-21	-25	-33	-45	-61	-81	-105	-133	-165	-201	-241	-285	-333	-385	-441	-501	-565	-633	-705	-781	-861	-945	-1033	-1125	-1221	-1321	-1425	-1533	-1645	-1761
21	441	441	72	18	21	-23	-27	-35	-47	-63	-83	-107	-135	-167	-203	-243	-287	-335	-387	-443	-503	-567	-635	-707	-783	-863	-947	-1035	-1127	-1223	-1323	-1427	-1535	-1647	-1763
23	529	529	80	20	23	-25	-29	-37	-49	-65	-85	-109	-137	-169	-205	-245	-289	-337	-389	-445	-505	-569	-637	-709	-785	-865	-949	-1037	-1129	-1225	-1325	-1429	-1537	-1649	-1765
25	625	625	88	22	25	-27	-31	-39	-51	-67	-87	-111	-139	-171	-207	-247	-291	-339	-391	-447	-507	-571	-639	-711	-787	-867	-951	-1039	-1131	-1227	-1327	-1431	-1539	-1651	-1767
27	729	729	96	24	27	-29	-33	-41	-53	-69	-89	-113	-141	-173	-209	-249	-293	-341	-393	-449	-509	-573	-641	-713	-789	-869	-953	-1041	-1133	-1229	-1329	-1433	-1541	-1653	-1769
29	841	841	104	26	29	-31	-35	-43	-55	-71	-91	-115	-143	-175	-211	-251	-295	-343	-395	-451	-511	-575	-643	-715	-791	-871	-955	-1043	-1135	-1231	-1331	-1435	-1543	-1655	-1771
31	961	961	112	28	31	-33	-37	-45	-57	-73	-93	-117	-145	-177	-213	-253	-297	-345	-397	-453	-513	-577	-645	-717	-793	-873	-957	-1045	-1137	-1233	-1333	-1437	-1545	-1657	-1773
33	1089	1089	120	30	33	-35	-39	-47	-59	-75	-95	-119	-147	-179	-215	-255	-299	-347	-399	-455	-515	-579	-647	-719	-795	-875	-959	-1047	-1139	-1235	-1335	-1439	-1547	-1659	-1775
35	1225	1225	128	32	35	-37	-41	-49	-61	-77	-97	-121	-149	-181	-217	-257	-301	-349	-401	-457	-517	-581	-649	-721	-797	-877	-961	-1049	-1141	-1237	-1337	-1441	-1549	-1661	-1777
37	1369	1369	136	34	37	-39	-43	-51	-63	-79	-99	-123	-151	-183	-219	-259	-303	-351	-403	-459	-519	-583	-651	-723	-799	-879	-963	-1051	-1143	-1239	-1339	-1443	-1551	-1663	-1779
39	1521	1521	144	36	39	-41	-45	-53	-65	-81	-101	-125	-153	-185	-221	-261	-305	-353	-405	-461	-521	-585	-653	-725	-801	-881	-965	-1053	-1145	-1241	-1341	-1445	-1553	-1665	-1781
41	1681	1681	152	38	41	-43	-47	-55	-67	-83	-103	-127	-155	-187	-223	-263	-307	-355	-407	-463	-523	-587	-655	-727	-803	-883	-967	-1055	-1147	-1243	-1343	-1447	-1555	-1667	-1783
43	1849	1849	160	40	43	-45	-49	-57	-69	-85	-105	-129	-157	-189	-225	-265	-309	-357	-409	-465	-525	-589	-657	-729	-805	-885	-969	-1057	-1149	-1245	-1345	-1449	-1557	-1669	-1785
45	2025	2025	168	42	45	-47	-51	-59	-71	-87	-107	-131	-159	-191	-227	-267	-311	-359	-411	-467	-527	-591	-659	-731	-807	-887	-971	-1059	-1151	-1247	-1347	-1451	-1559	-1671	-1787
47	2209	2209	176	44	47	-49	-53	-61	-73	-89	-109	-133	-161	-193	-229	-269	-313	-361	-413	-469	-529	-593	-661	-733	-809	-889	-973	-1061	-1153	-1249	-1349	-1453	-1561	-1673	-1789
49	2401	2401	184	46	49	-51	-55	-63	-75	-91	-111	-135	-163	-195	-231	-271	-315	-363	-415	-471	-531	-595	-663	-735	-811	-891	-975	-1063	-1155	-1251	-1351	-1455	-1563	-1675	-1791
51	2601	2601	192	48	51	-53	-57	-65	-77	-93	-113	-137	-165	-197	-233	-273	-317	-365	-417	-473	-533	-597	-665	-737	-813	-893	-977	-1065	-1157	-1253	-1353	-1457	-1565	-1677	-1793
53	2809	2809	200	50	53	-55	-59	-67	-79	-95	-115	-139	-167	-199	-235	-275	-319	-367	-419	-475	-535	-599	-667	-739	-815	-895	-979	-1067	-1159	-1255	-1355	-1459	-1567	-1679	-1795
55	3025	3025	208	52	55	-57	-61	-69	-81	-97	-117	-141	-169	-201	-237	-277	-321	-369	-421	-477	-537	-601	-669	-741	-817	-897	-981	-1069	-1161	-1257	-1357	-1461	-1569	-1681	-1797
57	3249	3249	216	54	57	-59	-63	-71	-83	-99	-119	-143	-171	-203	-239	-279	-323	-371	-423	-479	-539	-603	-671	-743	-819	-899	-983	-1071	-1163	-1259	-1359	-1463	-1571	-1683	-1799

Figure 40. C004026 Table of Count of Odd Numbers Between Odd Compounds from C004002 Relative to End Point in Odd Square Zones. https://1drv.ms/i/s!Arslv070x3Wjkcg_cRIZoqxrLCFctg?e=y9kpmX

For $n \geq 1$ and $k \geq 0$:

$$C004026_{horizontal} = -2(n^2 - n) - (2k - 1) = -(2 * oblong) - (odd)$$

$$C004026_{vertical} = -2k - (2(n^2 - n) - 1) = -(even) - (2 * oblong - 1)$$

All elements of C004026 are odd.

This matrix demonstrates that the sequences of primal numbers $x = 2y^2 + 2y + c$, where $c = \{3,7,19\}$, are bounded by the quadratic $\{1,15,45\}$, which, in offset $f = 0$, has the equation $x = 8y^2 + 6y + 1$.

13.7 C004027 Table of Count of Odd Numbers Between Odd Compounds from C004001 Relative to End Point in Even Square Zones

Using Even Square Zone start points for C004001 table elements:

Even	Start Point even ²	End Point (even +2) ²	# odds between even squares	C004027 Table of Count of Odd Numbers Between Odd Compounds from C004001 Relative to End Point in Even Square Zones																															
				(ODD Sq.) - (EVEN Sq.)	k	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29
0	0	4	2	1	1	0	2	8	18	32	50	72	98	128	162	200	242	288	338	392	450	512	578	648	722	800	882	968	1058	1152	1250	1352	1458	1568	1682
2	4	16	6	2	3	-3	-5	-11	-21	-35	-53	-75	-101	-131	-165	-203	-245	-291	-341	-395	-453	-515	-581	-651	-725	-803	-885	-971	-1061	-1155	-1253	-1355	-1461	-1571	-1685
4	16	36	10	3	5	-5	-7	-13	-23	-37	-55	-77	-103	-133	-167	-205	-247	-293	-343	-397	-455	-517	-583	-653	-727	-805	-887	-973	-1063	-1157	-1255	-1357	-1463	-1573	-1687
6	36	64	14	4	7	-7	-9	-15	-25	-39	-57	-79	-105	-135	-169	-207	-249	-295	-345	-399	-457	-519	-585	-655	-729	-807	-889	-975	-1065	-1159	-1257	-1359	-1465	-1575	-1689
8	64	100	18	5	9	-9	-11	-17	-27	-41	-59	-81	-107	-137	-171	-209	-251	-297	-347	-401	-459	-521	-587	-657	-731	-809	-891	-977	-1067	-1161	-1259	-1361	-1467	-1577	-1691
10	100	144	22	6	11	-11	-13	-19	-29	-43	-61	-83	-109	-139	-173	-211	-253	-299	-349	-403	-461	-523	-589	-659	-733	-811	-893	-979	-1069	-1163	-1261	-1363	-1469	-1579	-1693
12	144	196	26	7	13	-13	-15	-21	-31	-45	-63	-85	-111	-141	-175	-213	-255	-301	-351	-405	-463	-525	-591	-661	-735	-813	-895	-981	-1071	-1165	-1263	-1365	-1471	-1581	-1695
14	196	256	30	8	15	-15	-17	-23	-33	-47	-65	-87	-113	-143	-177	-215	-257	-303	-353	-407	-465	-527	-593	-663	-737	-815	-897	-983	-1073	-1167	-1265	-1367	-1473	-1583	-1697
16	256	324	34	9	17	-17	-19	-25	-35	-49	-67	-89	-115	-145	-179	-217	-259	-305	-355	-409	-467	-529	-595	-665	-739	-817	-899	-985	-1075	-1169	-1267	-1369	-1475	-1585	-1699
18	324	400	38	10	19	-19	-21	-27	-37	-51	-69	-91	-117	-147	-181	-219	-261	-307	-357	-411	-469	-531	-597	-667	-741	-819	-901	-987	-1077	-1171	-1269	-1371	-1477	-1587	-1701
20	400	484	42	11	21	-21	-23	-29	-39	-53	-71	-93	-119	-149	-183	-221	-263	-309	-359	-413	-471	-533	-599	-669	-743	-821	-903	-989	-1079	-1173	-1271	-1373	-1479	-1589	-1703
22	484	576	46	12	23	-23	-25	-31	-41	-55	-73	-95	-121	-151	-185	-223	-265	-311	-361	-415	-473	-535	-601	-671	-745	-823	-905	-991	-1081	-1175	-1273	-1375	-1481	-1591	-1705
24	576	676	50	13	25	-25	-27	-33	-43	-57	-75	-97	-123	-153	-187	-225	-267	-313	-363	-417	-475	-537	-603	-673	-747	-825	-907	-993	-1083	-1177	-1275	-1377	-1483	-1593	-1707
26	676	784	54	14	27	-27	-29	-35	-45	-59	-77	-99	-125	-155	-189	-227	-269	-315	-365	-419	-477	-539	-605	-675	-749	-827	-909	-995	-1085	-1179	-1277	-1379	-1485	-1595	-1709
28	784	900	58	15	29	-29	-31	-37	-47	-61	-79	-101	-127	-157	-191	-229	-271	-317	-367	-421	-479	-541	-607	-677	-751	-829	-911	-997	-1087	-1181	-1279	-1381	-1487	-1597	-1711
30	900	1024	62	16	31	-31	-33	-39	-49	-63	-81	-103	-129	-159	-193	-231	-273	-319	-369	-423	-481	-543	-609	-679	-753	-831	-913	-999	-1089	-1183	-1281	-1383	-1489	-1599	-1713
32	1024	1156	66	17	33	-33	-35	-41	-51	-65	-83	-105	-131	-161	-195	-233	-275	-321	-371	-425	-483	-545	-611	-681	-755	-833	-915	-1001	-1091	-1185	-1283	-1385	-1491	-1601	-1715
34	1156	1296	70	18	35	-35	-37	-43	-53	-67	-85	-107	-133	-163	-197	-235	-277	-323	-373	-427	-485	-547	-613	-683	-757	-835	-917	-1003	-1093	-1187	-1285	-1387	-1493	-1603	-1717
36	1296	1444	74	19	37	-37	-39	-45	-55	-69	-87	-109	-135	-165	-199	-237	-279	-325	-375	-429	-487	-549	-615	-685	-759	-837	-919	-1005	-1095	-1189	-1287	-1389	-1495	-1605	-1719
38	1444	1600	78	20	39	-39	-41	-47	-57	-71	-89	-111	-137	-167	-201	-239	-281	-327	-377	-431	-489	-551	-617	-687	-761	-839	-921	-1007	-1097	-1191	-1289	-1391	-1497	-1607	-1721
40	1600	1764	82	21	41	-41	-43	-49	-59	-73	-91	-113	-139	-169	-203	-241	-283	-329	-379	-433	-491	-553	-619	-689	-763	-841	-923	-1009	-1099	-1193	-1291	-1393	-1499	-1609	-1723
42	1764	1936	86	22	43	-43	-45	-51	-61	-75	-93	-115	-141	-171	-205	-243	-285	-331	-381	-435	-493	-555	-621	-691	-765	-843	-925	-1011	-1101	-1195	-1293	-1395	-1501	-1611	-1725
44	1936	2116	90	23	45	-45	-47	-53	-63	-77	-95	-117	-143	-173	-207	-245	-287	-333	-383	-437	-495	-557	-623	-693	-767	-845	-927	-1013	-1103	-1197	-1295	-1397	-1503	-1613	-1727
46	2116	2304	94	24	47	-47	-49	-55	-65	-79	-97	-119	-145	-175	-209	-247	-289	-335	-385	-439	-497	-559	-625	-695	-769	-847	-929	-1015	-1105	-1199	-1297	-1399	-1505	-1615	-1729
48	2304	2500	98	25	49	-49	-51	-57	-67	-81	-99	-121	-147	-177	-211	-249	-291	-337	-387	-441	-499	-561	-627	-697	-771	-849	-931	-1017	-1107	-1201	-1299	-1401	-1507	-1617	-1731
50	2500	2704	102	26	51	-51	-53	-59	-69	-83	-101	-123	-149	-179	-213	-251	-293	-339	-389	-443	-501	-563	-629	-699	-773	-851	-933	-1019	-1109	-1203	-1301	-1403	-1509	-1619	-1733
52	2704	2916	106	27	53	-53	-55	-61	-71	-85	-103	-125	-151	-181	-215	-253	-295	-341	-391	-445	-503	-565	-631	-701	-775	-853	-935	-1021	-1111	-1205	-1303	-1405	-1511	-1621	-1735
54	2916	3136	110	28	55	-55	-57	-63	-73	-87	-105	-127	-153	-183	-217	-255	-297	-343	-393	-447	-505	-567	-633	-703	-777	-855	-937	-1023	-1113	-1207	-1305	-1407	-1513	-1623	-1737
56	3136	3364	114	29	57	-57	-59	-65	-75	-89	-107	-129	-155	-185	-219	-257	-299	-345	-395	-449	-507	-569	-635	-705	-779	-857	-939	-1025	-1115	-1209	-1307	-1409	-1515	-1625	-1739
58	3364	3600	118	30	59	-59	-61	-67	-77	-91	-109	-131	-157	-187	-221	-259	-301	-347	-397	-451	-509	-571	-637	-707	-781	-859	-941	-1027	-1117	-1211	-1309	-1411	-1517	-1627	-1741

Figure 41. C004027 Table of Count of Odd Numbers Between Odd Compounds from C004001 Relative to End Point in Even Square Zones.

https://1drv.ms/i/s!Arslv070x3WjkchAvyBFINwL_q1rBg?e=VZCt3p

For $n \geq 1$ and $k \geq 0$:

$$C004027_{horizontal} = -2k^2 - (2n - 1) = -(2 * square) - (odd)$$

$$C004027_{vertical} = 2n - (2k^2 + 1) = (even) - (2 * square + 1)$$

All elements of C004027 are odd.

13.8 C004028 Table of Count of Odd Numbers Between Odd Compounds from C004002 Relative to End Point in Even Square Zones

Using Even Square Zone start points for C004002 table elements:

Even	Start Point even ⁿ	End Point (even +2) ⁿ	# odds between even ^s	C004028 Table of Count of Odd Numbers Between Odd Compounds from C004002 Relative to End Point in Even Square Zones																															
				(EVEN Sq.) - (ODD Sq.)	n	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30
-2	4	0	-2	0	0	0	4	12	24	40	60	84	112	144	180	220	264	312	364	420	480	544	612	684	760	840	924	1012	1104	1200	1300	1404	1512	1624	1740
0	0	4	2	1	0	0	-4	-12	-24	-40	-60	-84	-112	-144	-180	-220	-264	-312	-364	-420	-480	-544	-612	-684	-760	-840	-924	-1012	-1104	-1200	-1300	-1404	-1512	-1624	-1740
2	4	16	6	2	0	0	-4	-12	-24	-40	-60	-84	-112	-144	-180	-220	-264	-312	-364	-420	-480	-544	-612	-684	-760	-840	-924	-1012	-1104	-1200	-1300	-1404	-1512	-1624	-1740
4	16	36	10	3	0	0	-4	-12	-24	-40	-60	-84	-112	-144	-180	-220	-264	-312	-364	-420	-480	-544	-612	-684	-760	-840	-924	-1012	-1104	-1200	-1300	-1404	-1512	-1624	-1740
6	36	64	14	4	0	0	-4	-12	-24	-40	-60	-84	-112	-144	-180	-220	-264	-312	-364	-420	-480	-544	-612	-684	-760	-840	-924	-1012	-1104	-1200	-1300	-1404	-1512	-1624	-1740
8	64	100	18	5	0	0	-4	-12	-24	-40	-60	-84	-112	-144	-180	-220	-264	-312	-364	-420	-480	-544	-612	-684	-760	-840	-924	-1012	-1104	-1200	-1300	-1404	-1512	-1624	-1740
10	100	144	22	6	0	0	-4	-12	-24	-40	-60	-84	-112	-144	-180	-220	-264	-312	-364	-420	-480	-544	-612	-684	-760	-840	-924	-1012	-1104	-1200	-1300	-1404	-1512	-1624	-1740
12	144	196	26	7	0	0	-4	-12	-24	-40	-60	-84	-112	-144	-180	-220	-264	-312	-364	-420	-480	-544	-612	-684	-760	-840	-924	-1012	-1104	-1200	-1300	-1404	-1512	-1624	-1740
14	196	256	30	8	0	0	-4	-12	-24	-40	-60	-84	-112	-144	-180	-220	-264	-312	-364	-420	-480	-544	-612	-684	-760	-840	-924	-1012	-1104	-1200	-1300	-1404	-1512	-1624	-1740
16	256	324	34	9	0	0	-4	-12	-24	-40	-60	-84	-112	-144	-180	-220	-264	-312	-364	-420	-480	-544	-612	-684	-760	-840	-924	-1012	-1104	-1200	-1300	-1404	-1512	-1624	-1740
18	324	400	38	10	0	0	-4	-12	-24	-40	-60	-84	-112	-144	-180	-220	-264	-312	-364	-420	-480	-544	-612	-684	-760	-840	-924	-1012	-1104	-1200	-1300	-1404	-1512	-1624	-1740
20	400	484	42	11	0	0	-4	-12	-24	-40	-60	-84	-112	-144	-180	-220	-264	-312	-364	-420	-480	-544	-612	-684	-760	-840	-924	-1012	-1104	-1200	-1300	-1404	-1512	-1624	-1740
22	484	576	46	12	0	0	-4	-12	-24	-40	-60	-84	-112	-144	-180	-220	-264	-312	-364	-420	-480	-544	-612	-684	-760	-840	-924	-1012	-1104	-1200	-1300	-1404	-1512	-1624	-1740
24	576	676	50	13	0	0	-4	-12	-24	-40	-60	-84	-112	-144	-180	-220	-264	-312	-364	-420	-480	-544	-612	-684	-760	-840	-924	-1012	-1104	-1200	-1300	-1404	-1512	-1624	-1740
26	676	784	54	14	0	0	-4	-12	-24	-40	-60	-84	-112	-144	-180	-220	-264	-312	-364	-420	-480	-544	-612	-684	-760	-840	-924	-1012	-1104	-1200	-1300	-1404	-1512	-1624	-1740
28	784	900	58	15	0	0	-4	-12	-24	-40	-60	-84	-112	-144	-180	-220	-264	-312	-364	-420	-480	-544	-612	-684	-760	-840	-924	-1012	-1104	-1200	-1300	-1404	-1512	-1624	-1740
30	900	1024	62	16	0	0	-4	-12	-24	-40	-60	-84	-112	-144	-180	-220	-264	-312	-364	-420	-480	-544	-612	-684	-760	-840	-924	-1012	-1104	-1200	-1300	-1404	-1512	-1624	-1740
32	1024	1156	66	17	0	0	-4	-12	-24	-40	-60	-84	-112	-144	-180	-220	-264	-312	-364	-420	-480	-544	-612	-684	-760	-840	-924	-1012	-1104	-1200	-1300	-1404	-1512	-1624	-1740
34	1156	1296	70	18	0	0	-4	-12	-24	-40	-60	-84	-112	-144	-180	-220	-264	-312	-364	-420	-480	-544	-612	-684	-760	-840	-924	-1012	-1104	-1200	-1300	-1404	-1512	-1624	-1740
36	1296	1444	74	19	0	0	-4	-12	-24	-40	-60	-84	-112	-144	-180	-220	-264	-312	-364	-420	-480	-544	-612	-684	-760	-840	-924	-1012	-1104	-1200	-1300	-1404	-1512	-1624	-1740
38	1444	1600	78	20	0	0	-4	-12	-24	-40	-60	-84	-112	-144	-180	-220	-264	-312	-364	-420	-480	-544	-612	-684	-760	-840	-924	-1012	-1104	-1200	-1300	-1404	-1512	-1624	-1740
40	1600	1764	82	21	0	0	-4	-12	-24	-40	-60	-84	-112	-144	-180	-220	-264	-312	-364	-420	-480	-544	-612	-684	-760	-840	-924	-1012	-1104	-1200	-1300	-1404	-1512	-1624	-1740
42	1764	1936	86	22	0	0	-4	-12	-24	-40	-60	-84	-112	-144	-180	-220	-264	-312	-364	-420	-480	-544	-612	-684	-760	-840	-924	-1012	-1104	-1200	-1300	-1404	-1512	-1624	-1740
44	1936	2116	90	23	0	0	-4	-12	-24	-40	-60	-84	-112	-144	-180	-220	-264	-312	-364	-420	-480	-544	-612	-684	-760	-840	-924	-1012	-1104	-1200	-1300	-1404	-1512	-1624	-1740
46	2116	2304	94	24	0	0	-4	-12	-24	-40	-60	-84	-112	-144	-180	-220	-264	-312	-364	-420	-480	-544	-612	-684	-760	-840	-924	-1012	-1104	-1200	-1300	-1404	-1512	-1624	-1740
48	2304	2500	98	25	0	0	-4	-12	-24	-40	-60	-84	-112	-144	-180	-220	-264	-312	-364	-420	-480	-544	-612	-684	-760	-840	-924	-1012	-1104	-1200	-1300	-1404	-1512	-1624	-1740
50	2500	2704	102	26	0	0	-4	-12	-24	-40	-60	-84	-112	-144	-180	-220	-264	-312	-364	-420	-480	-544	-612	-684	-760	-840	-924	-1012	-1104	-1200	-1300	-1404	-1512	-1624	-1740
52	2704	2916	106	27	0	0	-4	-12	-24	-40	-60	-84	-112	-144	-180	-220	-264	-312	-364	-420	-480	-544	-612	-684	-760	-840	-924	-1012	-1104	-1200	-1300	-1404	-1512	-1624	-1740
54	2916	3136	110	28	0	0	-4	-12	-24	-40	-60	-84	-112	-144	-180	-220	-264	-312	-364	-420	-480	-544	-612	-684	-760	-840	-924	-1012	-1104	-1200	-1300	-1404	-1512	-1624	-1740
56	3136	3364	114	29	0	0	-4	-12	-24	-40	-60	-84	-112	-144	-180	-220	-264	-312	-364	-420	-480	-544	-612	-684	-760	-840	-924	-1012	-1104	-1200	-1300	-1404	-1512	-1624	-1740

Figure 42. C004028 Table of Count of Odd Numbers Between Odd Compounds from C004002 Relative to End Point in Even Square Zones.

<https://1drv.ms/i/s!Arslv070x3WjkchBVZQpUKdfWZp7OQ?e=SsPffA>

For $n \geq 1$ and $k \geq 0$:

$$C004028_{horizontal} = -2(n^2 - n) = -2(oblone)$$

All elements of C004028 are even.

14 Some Results

From the 16 tables labeled C004011 to C004018 and C004021 to C004028, we can derive many insights. One of the more straightforward observations occurs when we specifically examine tables C004001 and C004015, alongside C004002 and C004028.

To aid in visualization, refer to the specific sequences of these tables as follows:

Odd	Start Point (odd²)	End Point (odd²+2)	# odds betw en odds squar	C004001 Vertical Odd Squares Minus Horizontal Even Squares: Comprehensive Mapping																																
				(ODD Sq.) - (EVEN Sq.)	k	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	
				2k	0	4	16	36	64	100	144	196	256	324	400	484	576	676	784	900	1024	1156	1296	1444	1600	1764	1936	2116	2304	2500	2704	2916	3136	3364		
				n	2n-1	square	0	4	16	36	64	100	144	196	256	324	400	484	576	676	784	900	1024	1156	1296	1444	1600	1764	1936	2116	2304	2500	2704	2916	3136	3364
1	1	9	4	1	1	1	1	-3	-15	-35	-63	-99	-143	-195	-255	-323	-399	-483	-575	-675	-783	-899	-1023	-1155	-1295	-1443	-1599	-1763	-1935	-2115	-2303	-2499	-2703	-2915	-3135	-3363
3	9	25	8	2	3	9	9	5	-7	-27	-55	-91	-135	-187	-247	-315	-391	-475	-567	-667	-775	-891	-1015	-1147	-1287	-1435	-1591	-1755	-1927	-2107	-2295	-2491	-2695	-2907	-3127	-3355
5	25	49	12	3	5	25	25	21	9	-11	-39	-75	-119	-171	-231	-299	-375	-459	-551	-651	-759	-875	-999	-1131	-1271	-1419	-1575	-1739	-1911	-2091	-2279	-2475	-2679	-2891	-3111	-3339
7	49	81	16	4	7	49	49	45	33	-19	-51	-95	-147	-207	-275	-351	-435	-527	-627	-735	-851	-975	-1107	-1247	-1395	-1551	-1715	-1887	-2067	-2255	-2451	-2655	-2867	-3087	-3315	
9	81	121	20	5	9	81	81	77	65	-27	-69	-123	-183	-249	-323	-405	-495	-595	-703	-819	-943	-1075	-1215	-1363	-1519	-1683	-1855	-2035	-2223	-2419	-2623	-2835	-3055	-3283		
11	121	169	24	6	11	121	121	117	105	-39	-99	-165	-237	-315	-400	-492	-591	-697	-811	-933	-1063	-1201	-1347	-1501	-1663	-1833	-2011	-2197	-2391	-2593	-2803	-3021	-3247	-3483		
13	169	225	28	7	13	169	169	165	153	-51	-119	-195	-277	-365	-459	-560	-667	-781	-903	-1033	-1171	-1317	-1471	-1633	-1803	-1981	-2167	-2361	-2563	-2773	-2991	-3217	-3453	-3699		
15	225	289	32	8	15	225	225	221	209	-63	-139	-225	-317	-415	-519	-629	-745	-867	-995	-1129	-1271	-1421	-1579	-1745	-1919	-2101	-2291	-2489	-2695	-2909	-3131	-3361	-3599	-3843		
17	289	361	36	9	17	289	289	285	273	-75	-159	-255	-357	-465	-579	-699	-825	-957	-1095	-1239	-1391	-1551	-1719	-1895	-2079	-2271	-2471	-2679	-2895	-3119	-3351	-3591	-3843	-4099		
19	361	441	40	10	19	361	361	357	345	-87	-179	-283	-391	-503	-621	-745	-875	-1011	-1153	-1301	-1455	-1615	-1781	-1953	-2131	-2315	-2505	-2703	-2909	-3123	-3345	-3575	-3813	-4059		
21	441	529	44	11	21	441	441	437	425	-99	-199	-307	-421	-539	-661	-789	-923	-1063	-1209	-1361	-1519	-1683	-1853	-2029	-2211	-2399	-2593	-2793	-2999	-3213	-3435	-3665	-3903	-4149		
23	529	625	48	12	23	529	529	525	513	-111	-219	-333	-453	-577	-705	-837	-973	-1115	-1263	-1417	-1577	-1743	-1915	-2093	-2277	-2467	-2663	-2865	-3073	-3287	-3507	-3733	-3965	-4203		
25	625	729	52	13	25	625	625	621	609	-123	-239	-361	-489	-621	-757	-897	-1041	-1191	-1347	-1509	-1677	-1851	-2031	-2217	-2409	-2607	-2811	-3021	-3237	-3459	-3687	-3921	-4161	-4407		
27	729	841	56	14	27	729	729	725	713	-135	-261	-393	-531	-673	-819	-969	-1123	-1281	-1443	-1611	-1785	-1965	-2151	-2343	-2541	-2745	-2955	-3171	-3393	-3621	-3855	-4095	-4341	-4593		
29	841	961	60	15	29	841	841	837	825	-147	-281	-421	-567	-717	-871	-1029	-1191	-1357	-1527	-1701	-1881	-2067	-2259	-2457	-2661	-2871	-3087	-3309	-3537	-3771	-4011	-4257	-4509	-4767		
31	961	1089	64	16	31	961	961	957	945	-159	-303	-453	-609	-769	-933	-1101	-1273	-1449	-1629	-1813	-2001	-2193	-2391	-2595	-2805	-3021	-3243	-3471	-3705	-3945	-4191	-4443	-4699	-4959		
33	1089	1225	68	17	33	1089	1089	1085	1073	-171	-323	-481	-645	-813	-985	-1161	-1341	-1523	-1707	-1893	-2083	-2277	-2475	-2679	-2889	-3105	-3327	-3555	-3789	-4029	-4275	-4527	-4783	-5043		
35	1225	1369	72	18	35	1225	1225	1221	1209	-183	-343	-509	-681	-857	-1037	-1221	-1409	-1601	-1795	-1993	-2195	-2401	-2611	-2825	-3045	-3271	-3503	-3741	-3985	-4235	-4491	-4753	-5021	-5295		
37	1369	1517	76	19	37	1369	1369	1365	1353	-195	-363	-537	-717	-901	-1089	-1281	-1477	-1677	-1881	-2089	-2301	-2517	-2737	-2961	-3191	-3427	-3669	-3917	-4171	-4431	-4697	-4969	-5247	-5531		
39	1521	1681	80	20	39	1521	1521	1517	1505	-207	-383	-565	-753	-945	-1141	-1341	-1545	-1753	-1965	-2181	-2401	-2625	-2853	-3085	-3321	-3563	-3811	-4065	-4325	-4591	-4863	-5141	-5425	-5715		
41	1681	1849	84	21	41	1681	1681	1677	1665	-219	-403	-593	-789	-991	-1197	-1407	-1621	-1839	-2061	-2287	-2517	-2751	-2989	-3231	-3477	-3729	-3987	-4251	-4521	-4797	-5079	-5367	-5661	-5961		
43	1849	2025	88	22	43	1849	1849	1845	1833	-231	-423	-621	-825	-1035	-1249	-1467	-1689	-1915	-2145	-2379	-2617	-2859	-3105	-3355	-3609	-3867	-4131	-4401	-4677	-4959	-5247	-5541	-5841	-6147		
45	2025	2209	92	23	45	2025	2025	2021	2009	-243	-443	-649	-861	-1079	-1301	-1527	-1757	-1991	-2229	-2471	-2717	-2967	-3221	-3479	-3741	-3999	-4263	-4533	-4809	-5091	-5379	-5673	-5973	-6279		
47	2209	2401	96	24	47	2209	2209	2205	2193	-255	-463	-677	-897	-1123	-1353	-1587	-1825	-2067	-2313	-2563	-2817	-3075	-3337	-3603	-3873	-4147	-4427	-4713	-5005	-5303	-5607	-5917	-6233	-6555		
49	2401	2601	100	25	49	2401	2401	2397	2385	-267	-483	-705	-933	-1165	-1401	-1641	-1885	-2133	-2385	-2641	-2901	-3165	-3433	-3705	-3981	-4263	-4551	-4845	-5145	-5451	-5763	-6081	-6405	-6735		
51	2601	2809	104	26	51	2601	2601	2597	2585	-279	-503	-735	-973	-1215	-1461	-1711	-1965	-2223	-2485	-2751	-3021	-3295	-3573	-3855	-4141	-4433	-4731	-5035	-5345	-5661	-5983	-6311	-6645	-6985		
53	2809	3025	108	27	53	2809	2809	2805	2793	-291	-523	-765	-1017	-1273	-1533	-1797	-2065	-2337	-2613	-2893	-3177	-3465	-3757	-4053	-4353	-4657	-4967	-5283	-5605	-5933	-6267	-6607	-6953	-7305		
55	3025	3249	112	28	55	3025	3025	3021	3009	-303	-543	-795	-1057	-1323	-1593	-1867	-2145	-2427	-2713	-3003	-3297	-3595	-3897	-4203	-4513	-4827	-5145	-5467	-5795	-6129	-6469	-6815	-7167	-7525		
57	3249	3481	116	29	57	3249	3249	3245	3233	-315	-563	-825	-1097	-1373	-1653	-1937	-2225	-2517	-2813	-3113	-3417	-3725	-4037	-4353	-4673	-4997	-5325	-5657	-5995	-6339	-6689	-7045	-7407	-7775		
59	3481	3721	120	30	59	3481	3481	3477	3465	-327	-583	-855	-1137	-1423	-1713	-2007	-2305	-2607	-2913	-3223	-3537	-3855	-4177	-4503	-4833	-5167	-5505	-5847	-6195	-6549	-6909	-7275	-7647	-8025		

Odd	Start Point (odd²)	End Point (odd²+2)	# odds betw en odds squar	C004015 Table of Count of Odd Numbers Between Odd Compounds from C004001 Relative to Start Point in Odd Square Zones																																
				(ODD Sq.) - (EVEN Sq.)	k	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	
				2k	0	1	4	9	16	25	36	49	64	81	100	121	144	169	196	225	256	289	324	361	400	441	484	529	576	625	676	729	784	841		
				n	2n-1	square	0	1	4	9	16	25	36	49	64	81	100	121	144	169	196	225	256	289	324	361	400	441	484	529	576	625	676	729	784	841
1	1	9	4	1	0	0	0	-2	-8	-18	-32	-50	-72	-98	-128	-162	-200	-242	-288	-338	-392	-450	-512	-578	-648	-722	-800	-882	-968	-1058	-1152	-1250	-1352	-1458	-1568	-1682
3	9	25	8	2	0	0	0	-2	-8	-18	-32	-50	-72	-98	-128	-162	-200	-242	-288	-338	-392	-450	-512	-578	-648	-722	-800	-882	-968	-1058	-1152	-1250	-1352	-1458	-1568	-1682
5	25	49	12	3	0	0	0	-2	-8	-18	-32	-50	-72	-98	-128	-162	-200	-242	-288	-338	-392	-450	-512	-578	-648	-722	-800	-882	-968	-1058	-1152	-1250	-1352	-1458	-1568	-1682
7	49	81	16	4	0	0	0	-2	-8	-18	-32	-50	-72	-98	-128	-162	-200	-242	-288	-338	-392	-450	-512	-578	-648	-722	-800	-882	-968	-1058	-1152	-1250	-1352	-1458	-1568	-1682
9	81	121	20	5	0	0	0	-2	-8	-18	-32	-50	-72	-98	-128	-162	-200	-242	-288	-338	-392	-450	-512	-578	-648	-722	-800	-882	-968	-1058	-1152	-1250	-1352	-1458	-1568	-1682
11	121	169	24	6	0	0	0	-2	-8	-18	-32	-50	-72	-98	-128	-162																				

compounds of row 5 that appear in table C004001. Indeed, the calculations $81 - 0$, $81 - 4$, $81 - 16$, and $81 - 36$ yield all the positive compounds of row $n = 5$ in C004001.

A similar process can be applied to the pair of tables C004002 and C004028, which exactly reflects the results from the cited study "Exploring Parabolic Patterns in the Map of Integers and Divisors (MID) Framework".

14.1 C004061 Bijection between positive values of C004001 and C004015

C004061 Bijection between positive values of C004001 and C004015 (including Primes)							
C004001	$4n+1$	C004001 Vertical Odd Squares Minus Horizontal Even Squares: Comprehen sive Mapping	C004015	C004015 Table of Count of Odd Numbers Betw een Odd Compounds from C004001 Relative to Start Point in Odd Square Zones	$C004015 / 2$	$C004015 / 2$ == -(Square Number)	$C004001 - 2 * C004015$ == Odd Square Number
C004001	$4n+1$	1	C004015	0	$C004015 / 2$	0	1
C004001	$4n+1$	5	C004015	-2	$C004015 / 2$	-1	9
C004001	$4n+1$	9	C004015	0	$C004015 / 2$	0	9
C004001	$4n+1$	9	C004015	-8	$C004015 / 2$	-4	25
C004001	$4n+1$	13	C004015	-18	$C004015 / 2$	-9	49
C004001	$4n+1$	17	C004015	-32	$C004015 / 2$	-16	81
C004001	$4n+1$	21	C004015	-2	$C004015 / 2$	-1	25
C004001	$4n+1$	21	C004015	-50	$C004015 / 2$	-25	121
C004001	$4n+1$	25	C004015	0	$C004015 / 2$	0	25
C004001	$4n+1$	25	C004015	-72	$C004015 / 2$	-36	169
C004001	$4n+1$	29	C004015	-98	$C004015 / 2$	-49	225
C004001	$4n+1$	33	C004015	-8	$C004015 / 2$	-4	49
C004001	$4n+1$	33	C004015	-128	$C004015 / 2$	-64	289
C004001	$4n+1$	37	C004015	-162	$C004015 / 2$	-81	361
C004001	$4n+1$	41	C004015	-200	$C004015 / 2$	-100	441
C004001	$4n+1$	45	C004015	-2	$C004015 / 2$	-1	49
C004001	$4n+1$	45	C004015	-18	$C004015 / 2$	-9	81
C004001	$4n+1$	45	C004015	-242	$C004015 / 2$	-121	529
C004001	$4n+1$	49	C004015	0	$C004015 / 2$	0	49
C004001	$4n+1$	49	C004015	-288	$C004015 / 2$	-144	625
C004001	$4n+1$	53	C004015	-338	$C004015 / 2$	-169	729
C004001	$4n+1$	57	C004015	-32	$C004015 / 2$	-16	121
C004001	$4n+1$	57	C004015	-392	$C004015 / 2$	-196	841
C004001	$4n+1$	61	C004015	-450	$C004015 / 2$	-225	961

Figure 45. C004061 Bijection between positive values of C004001 and C004015.

https://1drv.ms/i/s!Arslv070x3WjkchC_dUUx4X77ckmHA?e=EBgOwv

Figure C004061 illustrates a bijection between the positive values of C004001 and C004015. The values in C004001 represent all odd numbers in the form of $4n + 1$. Correspondingly, each

value in C004015 is in the form of twice that of a perfect square. These values quantify the count of odd numbers situated between the odd number from C004001 and an odd square number on the numerical line, which represents the starting point of an Odd Square Zone. Thus, every odd value in C004001 is distanced from an odd square on the numerical line by a value given by $2 * C004015$.

14.2 C004062 Bijection between positive values of C004002 and C004028

C004062 Bijection between positive values of C004002 and C004028 (including Primes)							
C004002	$4n-1$	C004002 Vertical Even Squares Minus Horizontal Odd Squares: Comprehensive Mapping	C004028	C004028 Table of Count of Odd Numbers Between Odd Compounds from C004002 Relative to End Point in Even Square Zones	$C004028 / 2$	$C004028 / 2 == -(Oblong Number) == -(2 * Triangular Number)$	$C004002 - 2 * C004028 == \text{Odd (Square minus 1) Number} \rightarrow \text{represent Even Square Number in Number Line}$
C004002	$4n-1$	3	C004028	0	$C004028 / 2$	0	3
C004002	$4n-1$	7	C004028	-4	$C004028 / 2$	-2	15
C004002	$4n-1$	11	C004028	-12	$C004028 / 2$	-6	35
C004002	$4n-1$	15	C004028	0	$C004028 / 2$	0	15
C004002	$4n-1$	15	C004028	-24	$C004028 / 2$	-12	63
C004002	$4n-1$	19	C004028	-40	$C004028 / 2$	-20	99
C004002	$4n-1$	23	C004028	-60	$C004028 / 2$	-30	143
C004002	$4n-1$	27	C004028	-4	$C004028 / 2$	-2	35
C004002	$4n-1$	27	C004028	-84	$C004028 / 2$	-42	195
C004002	$4n-1$	31	C004028	-112	$C004028 / 2$	-56	255
C004002	$4n-1$	35	C004028	0	$C004028 / 2$	0	35
C004002	$4n-1$	35	C004028	-144	$C004028 / 2$	-72	323
C004002	$4n-1$	39	C004028	-12	$C004028 / 2$	-6	63
C004002	$4n-1$	39	C004028	-180	$C004028 / 2$	-90	399
C004002	$4n-1$	43	C004028	-220	$C004028 / 2$	-110	483
C004002	$4n-1$	47	C004028	-264	$C004028 / 2$	-132	575
C004002	$4n-1$	51	C004028	-24	$C004028 / 2$	-12	99
C004002	$4n-1$	51	C004028	-312	$C004028 / 2$	-156	675
C004002	$4n-1$	55	C004028	-4	$C004028 / 2$	-2	63
C004002	$4n-1$	55	C004028	-364	$C004028 / 2$	-182	783
C004002	$4n-1$	59	C004028	-420	$C004028 / 2$	-210	899
C004002	$4n-1$	63	C004028	0	$C004028 / 2$	0	63
C004002	$4n-1$	63	C004028	-40	$C004028 / 2$	-20	143
C004002	$4n-1$	63	C004028	-480	$C004028 / 2$	-240	1023

Figure 46. C004062 Bijection between positive values of C004002 and C004028.

<https://1drv.ms/i/s!Arslv070x3WjkchDat3G6894Dq1sfg?e=HySfld>

Figure C004062 demonstrates a bijection between the positive values of C004002 and C004028. The values in C004002 are all odd numbers in the form of $4n - 1$. Correspondingly,

each value in C004028 is either twice that of an oblong number or four times that of a triangular number. These values represent the quantity of odd numbers existing between the odd number from C004002 and an odd number of the form of (square minus 1) on the numerical line. The odd (square minus 1) numbers signify the positions of even square numbers at the endpoint in Even Square Zones. Consequently, every odd value in C004002 is separated from an odd (square minus 1) on the numerical line by a value given by $2 * C004028$.

14.3 C004063 Bijection between all positive odd numbers

C004063 Bijection between all positive odd numbers								CENTRAL DIAGONAL
C004001 or C004002	$4n+1$ or $4n-1$	odd	C004015 or C004028	C004015 or C004028	C004015 / 2 or C004028 / 2	C004015 / 2 or C004028 / 2	C004001 – $2 * C004015$ or C004002 – $2 * C004028$	
C004001	$4n+1$	1	C004015	0	C004015 / 2	0	1	X
C004002	$4n-1$	3	C004028	0	C004028 / 2	0	3	X
C004001	$4n+1$	5	C004015	-2	C004015 / 2	-1	9	X
C004002	$4n-1$	7	C004028	-4	C004028 / 2	-2	15	X
C004001	$4n+1$	9	C004015	0	C004015 / 2	0	9	
C004001	$4n+1$	9	C004015	-8	C004015 / 2	-4	25	X
C004002	$4n-1$	11	C004028	-12	C004028 / 2	-6	35	X
C004001	$4n+1$	13	C004015	-18	C004015 / 2	-9	49	X
C004002	$4n-1$	15	C004028	0	C004028 / 2	0	15	
C004002	$4n-1$	15	C004028	-24	C004028 / 2	-12	63	X
C004001	$4n+1$	17	C004015	-32	C004015 / 2	-16	81	X
C004002	$4n-1$	19	C004028	-40	C004028 / 2	-20	99	X
C004001	$4n+1$	21	C004015	-2	C004015 / 2	-1	25	
C004001	$4n+1$	21	C004015	-50	C004015 / 2	-25	121	X
C004002	$4n-1$	23	C004028	-60	C004028 / 2	-30	143	X
C004001	$4n+1$	25	C004015	0	C004015 / 2	0	25	
C004001	$4n+1$	25	C004015	-72	C004015 / 2	-36	169	X
C004002	$4n-1$	27	C004028	-4	C004028 / 2	-2	35	
C004002	$4n-1$	27	C004028	-84	C004028 / 2	-42	195	X
C004001	$4n+1$	29	C004015	-98	C004015 / 2	-49	225	X
C004002	$4n-1$	31	C004028	-112	C004028 / 2	-56	255	X
C004001	$4n+1$	33	C004015	-8	C004015 / 2	-4	49	
C004001	$4n+1$	33	C004015	-128	C004015 / 2	-64	289	X
C004002	$4n-1$	35	C004028	0	C004028 / 2	0	35	
C004002	$4n-1$	35	C004028	-144	C004028 / 2	-72	323	X

Figure 47. C004063 Bijection between all positive odd numbers.

<https://1drv.ms/i/s!Arslv070x3WjkcxGIhqbCEcaHbVLzg?e=nLLBPi>

Figure C004063 above showcases a bijection between all positive odd numbers, while both Figures C004064 below illustrate the arrangement of positive odd numbers over the Central Diagonal, sorted by 'Odd' and ' $4n \pm 1$ ' respectively.

C004064 Bijection between positive odd numbers over the Central Diagonal							
C004001 or C004002	4n+1 or 4n-1	odd	C004015 or C004028	C004015 or C004028	C004015 / 2 or C004028 / 2	C004015 / 2 or C004028 / 2	C004001 - 2 * C004015 or C004002 - 2 * C004028
C004001	4n+1	1	C004015	0	C004015 / 2	0	1
C004002	4n-1	3	C004028	0	C004028 / 2	0	3
C004001	4n+1	5	C004015	-2	C004015 / 2	-1	9
C004002	4n-1	7	C004028	-4	C004028 / 2	-2	15
C004001	4n+1	9	C004015	-8	C004015 / 2	-4	25
C004002	4n-1	11	C004028	-12	C004028 / 2	-6	35
C004001	4n+1	13	C004015	-18	C004015 / 2	-9	49
C004002	4n-1	15	C004028	-24	C004028 / 2	-12	63
C004001	4n+1	17	C004015	-32	C004015 / 2	-16	81
C004002	4n-1	19	C004028	-40	C004028 / 2	-20	99
C004001	4n+1	21	C004015	-50	C004015 / 2	-25	121
C004002	4n-1	23	C004028	-60	C004028 / 2	-30	143
C004001	4n+1	25	C004015	-72	C004015 / 2	-36	169
C004002	4n-1	27	C004028	-84	C004028 / 2	-42	195
C004001	4n+1	29	C004015	-98	C004015 / 2	-49	225
C004002	4n-1	31	C004028	-112	C004028 / 2	-56	255
C004001	4n+1	33	C004015	-128	C004015 / 2	-64	289
C004002	4n-1	35	C004028	-144	C004028 / 2	-72	323
C004001	4n+1	37	C004015	-162	C004015 / 2	-81	361
C004002	4n-1	39	C004028	-180	C004028 / 2	-90	399
C004001	4n+1	41	C004015	-200	C004015 / 2	-100	441
C004002	4n-1	43	C004028	-220	C004028 / 2	-110	483
C004001	4n+1	45	C004015	-242	C004015 / 2	-121	529
C004002	4n-1	47	C004028	-264	C004028 / 2	-132	575
C004001	4n+1	49	C004015	-288	C004015 / 2	-144	625
C004002	4n-1	51	C004028	-312	C004028 / 2	-156	675
C004001	4n+1	53	C004015	-338	C004015 / 2	-169	729
C004002	4n-1	55	C004028	-364	C004028 / 2	-182	783
C004001	4n+1	57	C004015	-392	C004015 / 2	-196	841
C004002	4n-1	59	C004028	-420	C004028 / 2	-210	899
C004001	4n+1	61	C004015	-450	C004015 / 2	-225	961
C004002	4n-1	63	C004028	-480	C004028 / 2	-240	1023
C004001	4n+1	65	C004015	-512	C004015 / 2	-256	1089
C004002	4n-1	67	C004028	-544	C004028 / 2	-272	1155
C004001	4n+1	69	C004015	-578	C004015 / 2	-289	1225
C004002	4n-1	71	C004028	-612	C004028 / 2	-306	1295
C004001	4n+1	73	C004015	-648	C004015 / 2	-324	1369
C004002	4n-1	75	C004028	-684	C004028 / 2	-342	1443
C004001	4n+1	77	C004015	-722	C004015 / 2	-361	1521
C004002	4n-1	79	C004028	-760	C004028 / 2	-380	1599
C004001	4n+1	81	C004015	-800	C004015 / 2	-400	1681
C004002	4n-1	83	C004028	-840	C004028 / 2	-420	1763
C004001	4n+1	85	C004015	-882	C004015 / 2	-441	1849
C004002	4n-1	87	C004028	-924	C004028 / 2	-462	1935
C004001	4n+1	89	C004015	-968	C004015 / 2	-484	2025
C004002	4n-1	91	C004028	-1012	C004028 / 2	-506	2115
C004001	4n+1	93	C004015	-1058	C004015 / 2	-529	2209
C004002	4n-1	95	C004028	-1104	C004028 / 2	-552	2303
C004001	4n+1	97	C004015	-1152	C004015 / 2	-576	2401
C004002	4n-1	99	C004028	-1200	C004028 / 2	-600	2499
C004001	4n+1	101	C004015	-1250	C004015 / 2	-625	2601
C004002	4n-1	103	C004028	-1300	C004028 / 2	-650	2703
C004001	4n+1	105	C004015	-1352	C004015 / 2	-676	2809
C004002	4n-1	107	C004028	-1404	C004028 / 2	-702	2915
C004001	4n+1	109	C004015	-1458	C004015 / 2	-729	3025
C004002	4n-1	111	C004028	-1512	C004028 / 2	-756	3135
C004001	4n+1	113	C004015	-1568	C004015 / 2	-784	3249
C004002	4n-1	115	C004028	-1624	C004028 / 2	-812	3363
C004001	4n+1	117	C004015	-1682	C004015 / 2	-841	3481

Figure 48. C004064 Bijection between positive odd numbers over the Central Diagonal sorted by Odd. https://1drv.ms/i/s!Arslv070x3WjkcxH7Hko0JQvZZ_uhA?e=IijGtr

C004064 Bijection between positive odd numbers over the Central Diagonal							
C004001 or C004002	$4n+1$ or $4n-1$	odd	C004015 or C004028	C004015 or C004028	C004015 / 2 or C004028 / 2	C004015 / 2 or C004028 / 2	C004001 – $2 * C004015$ or C004002 – $2 * C004028$
C004001	$4n+1$	1	C004015	0	C004015 / 2	0	1
C004001	$4n+1$	5	C004015	-2	C004015 / 2	-1	9
C004001	$4n+1$	9	C004015	-8	C004015 / 2	-4	25
C004001	$4n+1$	13	C004015	-18	C004015 / 2	-9	49
C004001	$4n+1$	17	C004015	-32	C004015 / 2	-16	81
C004001	$4n+1$	21	C004015	-50	C004015 / 2	-25	121
C004001	$4n+1$	25	C004015	-72	C004015 / 2	-36	169
C004001	$4n+1$	29	C004015	-98	C004015 / 2	-49	225
C004001	$4n+1$	33	C004015	-128	C004015 / 2	-64	289
C004001	$4n+1$	37	C004015	-162	C004015 / 2	-81	361
C004001	$4n+1$	41	C004015	-200	C004015 / 2	-100	441
C004001	$4n+1$	45	C004015	-242	C004015 / 2	-121	529
C004001	$4n+1$	49	C004015	-288	C004015 / 2	-144	625
C004001	$4n+1$	53	C004015	-338	C004015 / 2	-169	729
C004001	$4n+1$	57	C004015	-392	C004015 / 2	-196	841
C004001	$4n+1$	61	C004015	-450	C004015 / 2	-225	961
C004001	$4n+1$	65	C004015	-512	C004015 / 2	-256	1089
C004001	$4n+1$	69	C004015	-578	C004015 / 2	-289	1225
C004001	$4n+1$	73	C004015	-648	C004015 / 2	-324	1369
C004001	$4n+1$	77	C004015	-722	C004015 / 2	-361	1521
C004001	$4n+1$	81	C004015	-800	C004015 / 2	-400	1681
C004001	$4n+1$	85	C004015	-882	C004015 / 2	-441	1849
C004001	$4n+1$	89	C004015	-968	C004015 / 2	-484	2025
C004001	$4n+1$	93	C004015	-1058	C004015 / 2	-529	2209
C004001	$4n+1$	97	C004015	-1152	C004015 / 2	-576	2401
C004001	$4n+1$	101	C004015	-1250	C004015 / 2	-625	2601
C004001	$4n+1$	105	C004015	-1352	C004015 / 2	-676	2809
C004001	$4n+1$	109	C004015	-1458	C004015 / 2	-729	3025
C004001	$4n+1$	113	C004015	-1568	C004015 / 2	-784	3249
C004001	$4n+1$	117	C004015	-1682	C004015 / 2	-841	3481
C004002	$4n-1$	3	C004028	0	C004028 / 2	0	3
C004002	$4n-1$	7	C004028	-4	C004028 / 2	-2	15
C004002	$4n-1$	11	C004028	-12	C004028 / 2	-6	35
C004002	$4n-1$	15	C004028	-24	C004028 / 2	-12	63
C004002	$4n-1$	19	C004028	-40	C004028 / 2	-20	99
C004002	$4n-1$	23	C004028	-60	C004028 / 2	-30	143
C004002	$4n-1$	27	C004028	-84	C004028 / 2	-42	195
C004002	$4n-1$	31	C004028	-112	C004028 / 2	-56	255
C004002	$4n-1$	35	C004028	-144	C004028 / 2	-72	323
C004002	$4n-1$	39	C004028	-180	C004028 / 2	-90	399
C004002	$4n-1$	43	C004028	-220	C004028 / 2	-110	483
C004002	$4n-1$	47	C004028	-264	C004028 / 2	-132	575
C004002	$4n-1$	51	C004028	-312	C004028 / 2	-156	675
C004002	$4n-1$	55	C004028	-364	C004028 / 2	-182	783
C004002	$4n-1$	59	C004028	-420	C004028 / 2	-210	899
C004002	$4n-1$	63	C004028	-480	C004028 / 2	-240	1023
C004002	$4n-1$	67	C004028	-544	C004028 / 2	-272	1155
C004002	$4n-1$	71	C004028	-612	C004028 / 2	-306	1295
C004002	$4n-1$	75	C004028	-684	C004028 / 2	-342	1443
C004002	$4n-1$	79	C004028	-760	C004028 / 2	-380	1599
C004002	$4n-1$	83	C004028	-840	C004028 / 2	-420	1763
C004002	$4n-1$	87	C004028	-924	C004028 / 2	-462	1935
C004002	$4n-1$	91	C004028	-1012	C004028 / 2	-506	2115
C004002	$4n-1$	95	C004028	-1104	C004028 / 2	-552	2303
C004002	$4n-1$	99	C004028	-1200	C004028 / 2	-600	2499
C004002	$4n-1$	103	C004028	-1300	C004028 / 2	-650	2703
C004002	$4n-1$	107	C004028	-1404	C004028 / 2	-702	2915
C004002	$4n-1$	111	C004028	-1512	C004028 / 2	-756	3135
C004002	$4n-1$	115	C004028	-1624	C004028 / 2	-812	3363

Figure 49. C004064 Bijection between positive odd numbers over the Central Diagonal sorted by $4n \pm 1$. <https://1drv.ms/i/s!Arslv070x3WjkcXle6TRxf-zENQyOQ?e=PSwepJ>

14.4 C004066 The C004015C004028 Sieve of Primes over Odd Integers

Figure C004065 showcases the bijection between all positive odd numbers and C004015 or C004028 excluding the elements over the Central Diagonal (primes).

C004065 Bijection between positive odd numbers excluding the Central Diagonal							
C004001 or C004002	$4n+1$ or $4n-1$	odd	C004015 or C004028	C004015 or C004028	C004015 / 2 or C004028 / 2	C004015 / 2 or C004028 / 2	C004001 - 2 * C004015 or C004002 - 2 * C004028
C004001	$4n+1$	9	C004015	0	C004015 / 2	0	9
C004002	$4n-1$	15	C004028	0	C004028 / 2	0	15
C004001	$4n+1$	21	C004015	-2	C004015 / 2	-1	25
C004001	$4n+1$	25	C004015	0	C004015 / 2	0	25
C004002	$4n-1$	27	C004028	-4	C004028 / 2	-2	35
C004001	$4n+1$	33	C004015	-8	C004015 / 2	-4	49
C004002	$4n-1$	35	C004028	0	C004028 / 2	0	35
C004002	$4n-1$	39	C004028	-12	C004028 / 2	-6	63
C004001	$4n+1$	45	C004015	-2	C004015 / 2	-1	49
C004001	$4n+1$	45	C004015	-18	C004015 / 2	-9	81
C004001	$4n+1$	49	C004015	0	C004015 / 2	0	49
C004002	$4n-1$	51	C004028	-24	C004028 / 2	-12	99
C004002	$4n-1$	55	C004028	-4	C004028 / 2	-2	63
C004001	$4n+1$	57	C004015	-32	C004015 / 2	-16	121
C004002	$4n-1$	63	C004028	0	C004028 / 2	0	63
C004002	$4n-1$	63	C004028	-40	C004028 / 2	-20	143
C004001	$4n+1$	65	C004015	-8	C004015 / 2	-4	81
C004001	$4n+1$	69	C004015	-50	C004015 / 2	-25	169
C004002	$4n-1$	75	C004028	-12	C004028 / 2	-6	99
C004002	$4n-1$	75	C004028	-60	C004028 / 2	-30	195
C004001	$4n+1$	77	C004015	-2	C004015 / 2	-1	81
C004001	$4n+1$	81	C004015	0	C004015 / 2	0	81
C004001	$4n+1$	81	C004015	-72	C004015 / 2	-36	225
C004001	$4n+1$	85	C004015	-18	C004015 / 2	-9	121
C004002	$4n-1$	87	C004028	-84	C004028 / 2	-42	255
C004002	$4n-1$	91	C004028	-4	C004028 / 2	-2	99
C004001	$4n+1$	93	C004015	-98	C004015 / 2	-49	289
C004002	$4n-1$	95	C004028	-24	C004028 / 2	-12	143
C004002	$4n-1$	99	C004028	0	C004028 / 2	0	99
C004002	$4n-1$	99	C004028	-112	C004028 / 2	-56	323
C004001	$4n+1$	105	C004015	-8	C004015 / 2	-4	121
C004001	$4n+1$	105	C004015	-32	C004015 / 2	-16	169
C004001	$4n+1$	105	C004015	-128	C004015 / 2	-64	361
C004002	$4n-1$	111	C004028	-144	C004028 / 2	-72	399
C004002	$4n-1$	115	C004028	-40	C004028 / 2	-20	195
C004001	$4n+1$	117	C004015	-2	C004015 / 2	-1	121
C004001	$4n+1$	117	C004015	-162	C004015 / 2	-81	441
C004002	$4n-1$	119	C004028	-12	C004028 / 2	-6	143
C004001	$4n+1$	121	C004015	0	C004015 / 2	0	121

Figure 50. C004065 Bijection between positive odd numbers excluding the Central Diagonal sorted by Odd. <https://1drv.ms/i/s!Arslv070x3WjkcxJQ3roqB9MnT8q3Q?e=XJuxM6>

C004065 Bijection between positive odd numbers excluding the Central Diagonal							
C004001 or C004002	$4n+1$ or $4n-1$	odd	C004015 or C004028	C004015 or C004028	C004015 / 2 or C004028 / 2	C004015 / 2 or C004028 / 2	C004001 - 2 * C004015 or C004002 - 2 * C004028
C004001	$4n+1$	9	C004015	0	C004015 / 2	0	9
C004001	$4n+1$	21	C004015	-2	C004015 / 2	-1	25
C004001	$4n+1$	25	C004015	0	C004015 / 2	0	25
C004001	$4n+1$	33	C004015	-8	C004015 / 2	-4	49
C004001	$4n+1$	45	C004015	-2	C004015 / 2	-1	49
C004001	$4n+1$	45	C004015	-18	C004015 / 2	-9	81
C004001	$4n+1$	49	C004015	0	C004015 / 2	0	49
C004001	$4n+1$	57	C004015	-32	C004015 / 2	-16	121
C004001	$4n+1$	65	C004015	-8	C004015 / 2	-4	81
C004001	$4n+1$	69	C004015	-50	C004015 / 2	-25	169
C004001	$4n+1$	77	C004015	-2	C004015 / 2	-1	81
C004001	$4n+1$	81	C004015	0	C004015 / 2	0	81
C004001	$4n+1$	81	C004015	-72	C004015 / 2	-36	225
C004001	$4n+1$	85	C004015	-18	C004015 / 2	-9	121
C004001	$4n+1$	93	C004015	-98	C004015 / 2	-49	289
C004001	$4n+1$	105	C004015	-8	C004015 / 2	-4	121
C004001	$4n+1$	105	C004015	-32	C004015 / 2	-16	169
C004001	$4n+1$	105	C004015	-128	C004015 / 2	-64	361
C004001	$4n+1$	117	C004015	-2	C004015 / 2	-1	121
C004001	$4n+1$	117	C004015	-162	C004015 / 2	-81	441
C004001	$4n+1$	121	C004015	0	C004015 / 2	0	121
C004002	$4n-1$	15	C004028	0	C004028 / 2	0	15
C004002	$4n-1$	27	C004028	-4	C004028 / 2	-2	35
C004002	$4n-1$	35	C004028	0	C004028 / 2	0	35
C004002	$4n-1$	39	C004028	-12	C004028 / 2	-6	63
C004002	$4n-1$	51	C004028	-24	C004028 / 2	-12	99
C004002	$4n-1$	55	C004028	-4	C004028 / 2	-2	63
C004002	$4n-1$	63	C004028	0	C004028 / 2	0	63
C004002	$4n-1$	63	C004028	-40	C004028 / 2	-20	143
C004002	$4n-1$	75	C004028	-12	C004028 / 2	-6	99
C004002	$4n-1$	75	C004028	-60	C004028 / 2	-30	195
C004002	$4n-1$	87	C004028	-84	C004028 / 2	-42	255
C004002	$4n-1$	91	C004028	-4	C004028 / 2	-2	99
C004002	$4n-1$	95	C004028	-24	C004028 / 2	-12	143
C004002	$4n-1$	99	C004028	0	C004028 / 2	0	99
C004002	$4n-1$	99	C004028	-112	C004028 / 2	-56	323
C004002	$4n-1$	111	C004028	-144	C004028 / 2	-72	399
C004002	$4n-1$	115	C004028	-40	C004028 / 2	-20	195
C004002	$4n-1$	119	C004028	-12	C004028 / 2	-6	143

Figure 51. C004065 Bijection between positive odd numbers excluding the Central Diagonal sorted by $4n \pm 1$. <https://1drv.ms/i/s!Arslv070x3WjkcXKp7fygplEGzo9cQ?e=k4rhiS>

Figure C004066 below presents the C004015C004028 Sieve of Primes over Odd Integers, further exploring the distribution and classification of prime numbers.

C004066 The C004015C004028 Sieve of Primes over Odd Integers									
Zero at Odd Squares	Zero at Odd (Square-1)	C004015 (Number of odds between Odd Integer and Odd Square)	C004028 (Number of odds between Odd Integer and Odd (Square-1))	Odd Integer	3 ≤ Positive Odd Divisors ≤ sqrt(Odd Integer)				
					3	5	7	9	11
0	-1			1					
-3	0			3					
-2	-5			5					
-1	-4			7					
0	-3	0		9	3				
-7	-2			11					
-6	-1			13					
-5	0		0	15	3				
-4	-9			17					
-3	-8			19					
-2	-7	-2		21	3				
-1	-6			23					
0	-5	0		25		5			
-11	-4		-4	27	3				
-10	-3			29					
-9	-2			31					
-8	-1	-6		33	3				
-7	0		0	35		5			
-6	-13			37					
-5	-12		-12	39	3				
-4	-11			41					
-3	-10			43					
-2	-9	-2,-18		45	3	5			
-1	-8			47					
0	-7	0		49		7			
-15	-6		-24	51	3				
-14	-5			53					
-13	-4		-4	55		5			
-12	-3	-32		57	3				
-11	-2			59					
-10	-1			61					
-9	0		0,-40	63	3		7		
-8	-17	-8		65		5			
-7	-16			67					
-6	-15	-50		69	3				
-5	-14			71					
-4	-13			73					
-3	-12		-12,-60	75	3	5			
-2	-11	-2		77			7		
-1	-10			79					
0	-9	0,-72		81	3		9		
-19	-8			83					
-18	-7	-18		85		5			
-17	-6		-84	87	3				
-16	-5			89					
-15	-4		-4	91			7		
-14	-3	-96		93	3				
-13	-2		-24	95		5			
-12	-1			97					
-11	0		0,-112	99	3		9		
-10	-21			101					
-9	-20			103					
-8	-19	-8,-32,-128		105	3	5	7		
-7	-18			107					
-6	-17			109					
-5	-16		-144	111	3				
-4	-15			113					
-3	-14		-40	115		5			
-2	-13	-2,-162		117	3		9		
-1	-12		-12	119		7			
0	-11	0		121					11
	-10			123	3				
	-9			125		5			
	-8			127					
	-7			129	3				
	-6			131					
	-5			133			7		
	-4			135	3	5		9	
	-3			137					
	-2			139					
	-1			141	3				
	0			143					11

Figure 52. C004066 The C004015C004028 Sieve of Primes over Odd Integers.

<https://1drv.ms/i/s!Arslv070x3WjkcXNdn9nyV4r8L6DOQ?e=AhMf3G>

15 Twin Prime Conjecture

Building upon the concept demonstrated in previous analyses and supported by the study "Exploring Parabolic Patterns in the Map of Integers and Divisors (MID) Framework" (available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10252480>, we apply the theory that the distribution of odd compound numbers follows a quadratic pattern. This conceptual framework is critical as we consider two parallel sequences of odd numbers, represented by n and $n + 2$, where n is odd.

C004067 The C004015C004028 Sieve of Primes over (Odd+2) Integers									
Zero at Odd Squares	Zero at Odd (Square-1)	C004015 (Number of odds between (Odd+2) Integer and Odd Square)	C004028 (Number of odds between (Odd+2) Integer and Odd (Square-1))	(Odd+2) Integer	$3 \leq$ Positive Odd Divisors $\leq$ sqrt(Odd Integer)				
					3	5	7	9	11
0	-1			3					
-3	0			5					
-2	-5			7					
-1	-4	-1		9	3				
0	-3			11					
-7	-2			13					
-6	-1		-1	15	3				
-5	0			17					
-4	-9			19					
-3	-8	-3		21	3				
-2	-7			23					
-1	-6	-1		25		5			
0	-5		-5	27	3				
-11	-4			29					
-10	-3			31					
-9	-2	-9		33	3				
-8	-1		-1	35		5			
-7	0			37					
-6	-13		-13	39	3				
-5	-12			41					
-4	-11			43					
-3	-10	-3		45	3	5			
-2	-9			47					
-1	-8	-1		49			7		
0	-7		-25	51	3				
-15	-6			53					
-14	-5		-5	55		5			
-13	-4	-33		57	3				
-12	-3			59					
-11	-2			61					
-10	-1		-1	63	3		7		
-9	0	-9		65		5			
-8	-17			67					
-7	-16	-51		69	3				
-6	-15			71					
-5	-14			73					
-4	-13		-13	75	3	5			
-3	-12	-2		77			7		
-2	-11			79					
-1	-10	-1		81	3			9	
0	-9			83					
-19	-8	-19		85		5			
-18	-7		-85	87	3				
-17	-6			89					
-16	-5		-5	91			7		
-15	-4	-99		93	3				
-14	-3		-25	95		5			
-13	-2			97					
-12	-1	-1		99	3			9	
-11	0			101					
-10	-20			103					
-9	-19	-9		105	3	5	7		
-8	-18			107					
-7	-17			109					
-6	-16		-145	111	3				
-5	-15			113					
-4	-14		-41	115		5			
-3	-13	-3		117	3			9	
-2	-12		-13	119			7		
-1	-11	-1		121					11
0	-10			123	3				
	-9			125		5			
	-8			127					
	-7			129	3				
	-6			131					
	-5			133			7		
	-4			135	3	5		9	
	-3			137					
	-2			139					
	-1			141	3				
	0			143					11

Figure 53. C004067 The C004015C004028 Sieve of Primes over (Odd+2) Integers.

<https://1drv.ms/i/s!Arslv070x3WjkcXO7I7w-QJIsRBwQQ?e=pfVQKh>

When we analyze the quadratic distribution patterns of odd compounds in n and $n + 2$, within these two sequences, we discern four possible configurations for each odd n : (compound & compound), (primal & compound), (compound & primal), and (primal & primal). The existence of infinite (primal & primal) pairs hinges on the insufficiency of any two quadratic equations of the forms $(ay^2 + by + c)$ and $(ay^2 + by + c + 2)$ to cover all integers on the numerical line comprehensively.

C004068 The C004015C004028 Sieve of Twin Primes							
Zero at Odd Squares	Zero at Odd (Square-1)	C004015 (Number of odds between Odd Integer and Odd Square)	C004028 (Number of odds between Odd Integer and Odd (Square-1))	C004015 (Number of odds between (Odd+2) Integer and Odd Square)	C004028 (Number of odds between (Odd+2) Integer and Odd (Square-1))	Odd Integer	(Odd+2) Integer
0	-1					1	3
-3	0					3	5
-2	-5					5	7
-1	-4			-1		7	9
0	-3	0				9	11
-7	-2					11	13
-6	-1				-1	13	15
-5	0		0			15	17
-4	-9					17	19
-3	-8			-3		19	21
-2	-7	-2				21	23
-1	-6			-1		23	25
0	-5	0			-5	25	27
-11	-4		-4			27	29
-10	-3					29	31
-9	-2			-9		31	33
-8	-1	-8			-1	33	35
-7	0		0			35	37
-6	-13				-13	37	39
-5	-12		-12			39	41
-4	-11					41	43
-3	-10			-3		43	45
-2	-9	-2,-18				45	47
-1	-8			-1		47	49
0	-7	0			-25	49	51
-15	-6		-24			51	53
-14	-5				-5	53	55
-13	-4		-4	-33		55	57
-12	-3	-32				57	59
-11	-2					59	61
-10	-1				-1	61	63
-9	0		0,-40	-9		63	65
-8	-17	-8				65	67
-7	-16			-51		67	69
-6	-15	-50				69	71
-5	-14					71	73
-4	-13				-13	73	75
-3	-12		-12,-60	-2		75	77
-2	-11	-2				77	79
-1	-10			-1		79	81
0	-9	0,-72				81	83
-19	-8			-19		83	85
-18	-7	-18			-85	85	87
-17	-6		-84			87	89
-16	-5				-5	89	91
-15	-4		-4	-99		91	93
-14	-3	-98			-25	93	95
-13	-2		-24			95	97
-12	-1				-1	97	99
-11	0		0,-112			99	101
-10	-21					101	103
-9	-20			-9		103	105
-8	-19	-8,-32,-128				105	107
-7	-18					107	109
-6	-17				-145	109	111
-5	-16		-144			111	113
-4	-15			-41		113	115
-3	-14		-40	-3		115	117
-2	-13	-2,-162			-13	117	119
-1	-12		-12	-1		119	121
0	-11	0				121	123
	-10					123	125
	-9					125	127
	-8					127	129
	-7					129	131
	-6					131	133
	-5					133	135
	-4					135	137
	-3					137	139
	-2					139	141
	-1					141	143
	0					143	

Figure 54. C004068 The C004015C004028 Sieve of Twin Primes.

https://1drv.ms/i/s!Arslv070x3WjkcxB_KssMZPyqGMzw?e=oSmEJo

The hypothesis that two quadratic sequences could cover all integers would contradict the observed distribution patterns, thus supporting the possibility of infinite twin prime pairs. This relationship is grounded in our quadratic model for the distribution of odd compounds, as demonstrated in our tables and detailed in the referenced study.

16 Goldbach Conjecture and Landau's Problem

Applying the same quadratic distribution principle to n and $n + 2$ extended to $n \pm 2k$ reveals similar patterns. In all cases, the quadratic sequences that model the compound numbers affirm that no two quadratic sequences can completely encompass all integers on the numerical line. This insight not only corroborates the findings from the Twin Prime analysis but also highlights the broader applicability of our quadratic distribution model to other longstanding conjectures in number theory, such as Goldbach's and Landau's.

17 Next Steps

For such a significant claim, continued validation through peer review, further empirical testing, and mathematical scrutiny in broader academic forums will be essential. These steps will help solidify the place of our findings within the established corpus of number theory.

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